

THE DISTRIBUTION OF STAR-FORMING GALAXIES IN INTERMEDIATE REDSHIFT
GALAXY CLUSTERS

by

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Abstract

In this thesis, we explore the distribution and properties of star-forming galaxies in six intermediate redshift ($0.3 < z < 1.0$) galaxy clusters. Our sample is drawn from the WIYN Long Term Variability Survey (WLTV) obtained with the Mini-Mosaic camera on the WIYN 3.5m telescope. We focus on a subset of six fields from this survey, for which the WIYN UBRIZ imaging is supplemented with narrow-band imaging that samples rest-frame [OII] λ 3727. The data analysis includes unique reduction procedures for the Mini-Mosaic camera, an algorithm to produce galaxy photometry with small systematic errors, and a hybrid photometric redshift method that produces small random and systematic errors. The WIYN imaging data is supplemented by imaging data from the WIYN 0.9m telescope and the Hubble Space Telescope archive.

The number density and distribution of Luminous Compact Blue Galaxies (LCBGs) are explored in six cluster fields. LCBGs are defined as enthusiastic star forming galaxies with the following properties: $M_B < -18.5$, $(B - V)_o < 0.5$, and $\bar{\mu}_e < 21$ mag arcsec $^{-2}$. The LCBGs are a significant cluster population (13–28%) with a distribution best described as shell-like. Reasonable assumptions about the lifetime and number density of the LCBGs indicate that cluster LCBGs must fade substantially to produce luminosity functions in these clusters that are comparable to cluster luminosity functions observed today. Combining the information about their number density and distribution with the exponential light profiles observed, cluster LCBGs are a likely progenitor population for dwarf elliptical galaxies.

The [OII] λ 3727 luminosity function for all star-forming galaxies in these clusters reveal an over-density of emission line galaxies relative to the field. The total star formation rate measured in a sample which includes intermediate redshift clusters from the literature displays no trend with redshift, mass, or x-ray properties. The mass-normalized total star formation rate does show a moderate to strong correlation with redshift and luminosity gap statistic. After correcting the mass-normalized total star formation rate by the mass-normalized global star formation rate at the redshift of the cluster, large star formation rates are only observed in clusters that have undergone recent major merger events identified by the luminosity gap statistic.

For Mom and Dad

For always encouraging me to ask why

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Understanding the transformation of primordial fluctuations in the matter density of the early Universe into the complex structures of galaxies seen today is still a fundamental problem facing modern astronomy. Many of the gross features of galaxies can be explained through a Λ CDM paradigm where galaxies grow through hierarchical merging, but the detailed mechanics that give rise to the myriad of relationships seen in the Universe, both now and in the past, still escape the grasp of astrophysical theory.

Observational astronomy can alleviate some of the current tension in the theoretical description of galaxy formation. Further constraints on theory can be provided through improved astronomical measurements. Better resolution, deeper imaging, and larger data sets have improved our understanding of such concepts as the galaxy luminosity function (Blanton et al. 2001, Madgwick et al. 2002), the Fundamental Plane (Bernardi et al. 2003), and the morphology-density relationship (Goto et al. 2003). Another way to explore these relationships is by looking further into the past to witness their evolution. Observations of the aforementioned relationships has recently been done by Faber et al. (2005), van Dokkum & Stanford (2003), and Postman et al. (2005).

In general, a strong constraint on the evolution of galaxies is created when the properties and distributions of galaxies observed today are tied to those that can be observed at higher redshifts. The large number of red galaxies seen at high redshift, for example, has tested the limits of the hierarchical merging scenario (Koo et al. 2005). Likewise, connecting the star forming galaxies seen in the past to the current population of galaxies provides a framework to test the possible processes

behind the prodigious drop in star formation seen since $z \sim 1$ (Lilly et al. 1996, Madau et al. 1996).

In this thesis, we study the star-forming population in six, intermediate-redshift clusters of galaxies in order to address the issues of galaxy evolution in different environments. We hope to construct a bridge between galaxies observed at earlier epochs and today through observations of the distribution of different populations. In particular, we focus on one of the most extreme star-bursting populations, seen only at intermediate redshifts, in an attempt to explain where these galaxies are today.

1.1 Luminous Compact Blue Galaxies

Luminous Compact Blue Galaxies (LCBGs) are the most rapidly evolving galaxy population at intermediate redshifts ($0.3 < z < 1$). These galaxies are luminous ($M_B \sim -20$), compact ($R_e \sim 2\text{kpc}$), and blue ($B - V \sim 0.35$) (Koo et al. 1994; Guzmán et al. 1997). With these properties, LCBGs provide a link between high-redshift Lyman-Break galaxies and present-day HII galaxies (Lowenthal et al. 1997). Their mass and number density decline in concert with the global star formation density of the Universe since $z \leq 1$, while extinction estimates place the star formation rates in some LCBGs above $40 M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Hammer et al. 2001). Despite the seeming importance of these objects in understand galaxy evolution today, their evolutionary fate remains unknown, i.e., what do they become by today? Are they a transition stage in the formation of spiral galaxies or the last burst of star formation seen in dwarf elliptical galaxies?

These two possible descendant populations have very different distributions in the local Universe. Dwarf ellipticals are found with much higher frequency in dense environments, such as clusters, than spiral galaxies (Ferguson & Binggeli 1994). To date, no systematic survey for LCBGs have been conducted in any cluster population, although Koo et al. (1997) did identify a handful of LCBGs in Cl0024 indicating that this area is ripe for study.

1.2 Galaxy Clusters

Some of the earliest signs of galaxy evolution were observed in changes of cluster populations with redshift: Butcher & Oemler (1978) claimed to find an increasing fraction of blue cluster galaxies at relatively modest redshifts ($z < 0.5$). Further evidence for the evolution of cluster galaxies has

been couched in terms of changes in the morphology-density relationship. In short, this relationship is a statement that early-type galaxies are observed to lie preferentially in high-density environments, while late-type galaxies appear to prefer low-density environments. Also, it has been observed that the average star formation rate is depressed in high-density environments in the nearby Universe (Balogh et al. 2000, Balogh et al. 2004) and the ratio of dwarf to giant galaxies increases in high density environments (Ferguson & Binggeli 1994). At $z = 0$, elliptical and S0 galaxies dominate the galaxy population in high galaxy density environments (Dressler 1980), whereas the S0 population gives way to spiral galaxies at higher redshifts (Dressler et al. 1997, Postman et al. 2005).

How these density relationships come about is still somewhat of a mystery. More pointedly, the problem is that there are too many explanations, and the puzzle is unraveling which, or which combination of possible paths have led to the population trends with environment that we see today. Although the massive elliptical population appears to have been passively evolving since $z \sim 3$ (Bower, Lucey, & Ellis 1992, Ellis et al. 1997, Stanford, Eisenhardt, & Dickinson 1998), many of the lower-mass galaxies show signs of recent star formation (Poggianti et al. 1999, Conselice et al. 2003). In a paradigm of hierarchical growth of structure, clusters will continually accrete material. Transforming a blue field population into a quiescent, passively-evolving population lying along the red sequence has been attributed to many different processes ranging from pre-processing (Zabludoff & Mulchaey 1998), ram-pressure stripping (Gunn & Gott 1972), galaxy harassment (Moore et al. 1996), tidal stripping (Merritt 1983), merging (Lavery & Henry 1994), and starvation (Larson, Tinsley, & Caldwell 1980). Understanding which of these processes are dominant, and in what regimes they are important, requires detailed observations of cluster populations across a broad range in redshift, and out to large cluster radii where the transition between cluster and field environment occurs.

1.3 WIYN Long Term Variability Survey

The data for this thesis is primarily drawn from the WIYN Long Term Variability Survey (WLTV), conducted with the WIYN 3.5m telescope. The survey is a study of 10 intermediate-redshift galaxy clusters sampled in 12 fields over a six year period. Two of these fields are devoid of regions of rich over-density along the sampled line-of-sight, providing a field referent for various aspects of our analysis. The primary observing plan involved UBRI-band imaging for each cluster,

over a field of view equivalent to their virial radius, achieving a depth of $R \sim 25$ each year. The yearly depth and time sequencing, while not germane to this work, was aimed at establishing variability and proper-motion data to be applied to the following projects in the future: (a) AGN detection through optical multi-colors and variability to $z \sim 4$; (b) identification of objects with large proper motions, such as dim solar system objects; (c) identification of halo white dwarfs via multi-colors and small proper motions; and (d) the detection and measurement of the supernova rate in field and cluster galaxies.

This thesis takes advantage of the great summed depth generated by the full course of the survey, and concentrates on the blue galaxy populations in the clusters. As part of this thesis, we have added two significant photometric components to the already exquisite data-set. (1) Gunn z-band imaging of each cluster was acquired to a depth of 23-23.5 mag. This addition extends the photometric redshifts to $z \sim 1.25$ and provides rest-frame B-band measurements for sources in all of the clusters. (2) Narrow-band imaging, sampling rest-frame [OII] λ 3727 at the cluster redshift, was acquired for six of the clusters. This was achieved through the design, manufacture and calibration of a custom filter set. The unique data provide a high-fidelity method to identify cluster emission-line objects and an estimate of the star formation occurring in those objects. The six clusters that are analyzed in this thesis are described below.

1.4 Galaxy Clusters in our Sample

Our sample is primarily selected from rich, well-studied galaxy clusters. The galaxy clusters range in redshift from 0.53 – 0.9 and typically have velocity dispersions around 1000 km/s. Each of the clusters has published spectroscopic redshifts for objects in the general field; most have published equivalent widths for cluster galaxies. Table 1.1 lists the positions for each field observed, named for its associated cluster. Here, we provide a brief description of each cluster.

- **MS0451** is a rich, well-studied cluster at $z = 0.53$ initially discovered by Stocke et al.(1991) in the Einstein Medium Sensitivity Survey and spectroscopically confirmed by Gioia & Luppino (1994). MS0451 is X-ray luminous (Donahue et al. 2003), with a large number of spectroscopically confirmed members (Ellingson et al. 1998). Mass estimates are available from the

velocity dispersion (Carlberg et al. 1996), X-ray data (Donahue et al. 2003), and a weak-lensing estimate (Clowe et al. 2000).

- **C10016** is one of the first clusters to display significant variations in the Butcher-Oemler value—the fraction of blue galaxies in a cluster – as compared to clusters at similar redshifts (Koo 1981). C10016 is a rich cluster at $z = 0.55$ with a large number of confirmed members (Ellingson et al. 1998, Dressler et al. 1999), and a major component of a super-cluster complex (Connolly et al. 1996). X-ray observations of the cluster reveal a luminous system with multiple substructures (Worrall et al. 2003) but with mass estimates comparable to other measurements (Smail et al. 1997, Carlberg et al. 1997, and Clowe et al. 2000).
- **C11322** was originally discovered by Gunn, Hoessel, & Oke (1986) and spectroscopically confirmed as a cluster by Oke, Postman & Lubin (1998) at $z = 0.75$. XMM-Newton observations of the cluster indicate it is under-luminous for its velocity dispersion compared to local galaxy clusters, but consistent with other high-redshift clusters (Lubin, Mulchaey, & Postman 2003).
- **C11325** is an area $\sim 7'$ to the east of the C11322 field which includes a structure at $z = 0.72$ (Oke, Postman & Lubin 1998). Beyond spectroscopic confirmation, no other information exists for this structure. In our data, it is not as visually impressive as the structure seen in our other cluster fields. Its value in this survey is a low-to-medium density volume at a redshift complementary to our other cluster fields.
- **MS1054** is a massive cluster at $z = 0.83$, which has been extensively studied both through HST imaging and spectroscopy (van Dokkum et al. 1999, Tran et al. 1999, Goto et al. 2005, Tran et al. 2005). Initially discovered as one of the highest-redshift sources in the EMSS (Stocke et al. 1991), MS1054 has been proven to be a massive cluster at high redshift on the basis of spectroscopic velocity dispersion measurements (Tran et al. 1999), X-ray luminosity (Donahue et al. 1998, Neuman & Arnaud 2000, Jeltama et al 2001, Gioia et al. 2004), and lensing-mass estimates (Luppino & Kaiser 1997, Clowe et al. 2000, Jee et al. 2005).
- **C11604**, at $z = 0.90$, is the highest redshift cluster in our sample (Oke, Postman, Lubin 1998). It is part of a super-cluster complex (Gal & Lubin 2004) and has X-ray properties inconsistent

with the measured velocity dispersion (Lubin et al. 2003). The errors on the mass from a weak-lensing estimate do not allow further constraints, other than confirmation of a massive structure at very high redshift (Margoniner et al. 2005).

Overall, our two low-redshift clusters are more massive than any of the high-redshift clusters in our sample. This is seen in the velocity dispersion, X-ray luminosity, and lensing masses (not included in Table 1). In comparison to local, rich clusters, the Coma cluster has a velocity dispersion of $\sigma = 1082 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (Colless & Dunn 1996) and an X-ray temperature of $T_x = 7.8 \text{ keV}$ (Honda et al. 1996). The Virgo cluster has a $\sigma = 1065 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (Conselice, Gallagher, & Wyse 2001) and $T_x = 2.2 \text{ keV}$ (Arnaud & Evrard 1999).

1.5 Contents Of this Thesis

In Chapter 2, we describe the observations, data reduction, and basic analysis of the imaging data from the WLTV survey. We describe a photometric technique that produces accurate photometry for all galaxies, regardless of profile shape. This uses a method that we refer as “adaptive-apertures.” We also develop a photometric-redshift method that is a hybrid of the template-matching and empirical training-set techniques now commonly found in the literature. Our hybrid technique produces both small systematic *and* random errors. We highlight these technical achievements by showing some of the basic measurements that can be made from this combination of high-quality data and high-precision analysis. These include a measurement of the cluster red-sequence color-magnitude relation, the cluster blue-galaxy fraction, and the luminosity function of the red cluster galaxies. These results provide some timely, and definitive conclusions on a recent debate about a possible deficit of faint, red galaxies in intermediate redshift clusters.

The identification and analysis of the LCBG population in the clusters is presented in Chapter 3. The LCBGs are identified through their rest-frame photometric properties. We measure the distribution of LCBGs and compare it to the red and blue cluster populations. We analyze their photometric indices (e.g., concentration and asymmetry), compare the number of LCBGs as a function of galaxy density, and discuss possible evolutionary scenarios for this extreme, star-forming cluster population.

In Chapter 4, we analyze the entire population of star-forming cluster galaxies. We do this through an analysis of the narrow-band imaging data. In addition to the measurement of the cluster [OII] λ 3727 luminosity function, we discuss the distribution of star-formation rates with density. Finally, we examine the star-formation rate integrated over the entire cluster emission-line population, and explore possible correlations of this integral with salient cluster properties such as redshift, mass, x-ray properties, and merging history.

We conclude in Chapter 5 with a summary of our results.

Throughout this work, we adopt $H_0 = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, $\Omega_{matter} = 0.3$, and $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$. All magnitudes are reported in the Vega system. Some common abbreviations used in this work: LF (luminosity function), BO (Butcher-Oemler galaxies, i.e. blue galaxies), OII ([OII] λ 3727), and EW (equivalent width).

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Table 1.1. Cluster Properties

Cluster	RA J2000	DEC J2000	z	σ (km s ⁻¹)	L_x^{bol} (erg s ⁻¹)	T_x (keV)	R_c (Mpc)	R_{200} (Mpc)	ref. ^a
MS0451	04:54:10.81	-03:00:56.85	0.538	1354	54×10^{44}	10	0.19	2.50	1
CL0016	00:18:33.52	+16:26:16.01	0.55	1230	32×10^{44}	8.9	0.22	2.25	2
CL1325	13:25:18.70	+30:09:57.09	0.72						3
CL1324	13:24:50.13	+30:11:18.49	0.75	1016	1.4×10^{44}	2.88	0.117	1.64	4
MS1054	10:56:59.50	-03:37:28.39	0.83	1170	20×10^{44}	8.6		1.81	5
CL1604	16:04:18.27	+43:04:38.42	0.90	982	2.0×10^{44}	2.51	0.14	1.46	6

^a References: (1) Faber et al. 1989, Ellingson et al. 1998, Donahue et al. 2005, Mahdavi & Geller 2001 (2) Faber et al. 1989, Ellingson et al 1998, Henry 2004 (3) Oke et al. 1998 (4) Lubin et al. 2002, Lubin et al. 2004 (5) Tran et al. 1999, Gioia et al. 2004 (6) Lubin et al. 2004, Gal & Lubin 2004.

Chapter 2

The WIYN Long Term Variability Study: Observations and Data Analysis for Six Intermediate Redshift Clusters

Abstract

We describe the basic observations, data reduction, and analysis for the imaging associated with the WIYN Long Term Variability (WLTV) study. The WLTV consists of a deep imaging data-set covering 0.4 deg^2 in twelve fields, sampling 10 rich, intermediate redshift ($0.3 < z < 1.0$) clusters. The data set primarily consists of broad-band imaging taken with the Mini-Mosaic camera on the WIYN 3.5 meter telescope located at Kitt Peak, AZ. We focus on a subset of six fields, for which the WLTV survey-data is supplemented with narrow on- and off-band imaging that samples rest-frame $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ and nearby spectral-continuum at the redshift of each cluster. We report the details of the observations and data analysis, which include unique procedures for the Mini-Mosaic data reduction, production of deep mosaic images, and photometric calibration. Supplementary calibration observations taken with the WIYN 0.9m telescope are described, as is the analysis of images from the Hubble Space Telescope archive.

The data analysis required for our scientific purposes are also described. Object detection was accomplished through the use of SExtractor. Photometry of our sources was performed either through aperture photometry or through “adaptive-aperture” photometry based on the curve of growth of individual galaxies. Adaptive aperture photometry minimizes the systematic errors related to galaxy photometry due to the variation in galaxy profiles. Photometric redshifts were determined for all objects through a hybrid of the template and training-set method. This method produces small systematic and random errors in the photometric redshift distribution. We also outline the different galaxy properties which we measure for all detected objects. These include image concentration, light-profile asymmetry, and projected space-density. Rest-frame properties are calculated for all objects. Corrections to observed parameters in the ground based data are made through comparisons to the HST data.

To demonstrate the high quality of the data and analysis, we make several basic measurements characterizing the red and blue cluster populations. The blue fraction measured for the clusters do increase as a function of redshift and are consistent with the wide range of values found in the literature for comparable clusters at similar redshifts. All fields with rich clusters display a strong luminosity-sequence of red galaxies at the cluster redshift, indicative of high-density environments.

We measure the luminosity function for red-sequence galaxies in each cluster. None of the clusters show any conclusive evidence for a deficit of galaxies to $M_B = -18.5$, in conflict with recent studies.

2.1 Introduction

Galaxy clusters provide astronomy with a unique laboratory to study the Universe. Clusters can be signposts in which to map out the cosmic density of the Universe, and also represent extreme environments in which some of the most distinctive relationships between populations of galaxies are observed. These features have inspired many surveys of both nearby (Butcher & Oemler 1978, Dressler 1980, Mazure et al. 1995, Poggianti et al 1999, Conselice, Gallagher, & Wyse 2001, Goto et al. 2003) and high redshift clusters (Yee et al. 1996, Dressler et al. 1997, Kodama et al. 2005, Postman et al. 2005, White et al. 2005). To these previous studies, we add a unique, imaging survey of 6 intermediate-redshift clusters. Due to its depth, breadth, and sampling in wavelength, this survey is well suited to study the populations in intermediate redshift clusters, and the trends these populations exhibit with local environment and redshift.

In the nearby Universe, galaxy populations of clusters are dominated by early type galaxies (Dressler 1980) along the so-called “red sequence,” the name for which derives from the tight color-magnitude relation observed for these galaxies (Visvanathan & Sandage 1977). Examination of the individual populations in nearby clusters indicate the most luminous galaxies display little star formation since $z \sim 2.5$ (Bower, Lucey, & Ellis 1992, Ellis et al. 1997, Stanford, Eisenhardt, & Dickinson 1998, Kelson et al. 2001, Poggianti et al. 1999, Conselice et al 2003). Observations of very high redshift ($z > 1$) clusters indicate the bright end of the color-magnitude relationship has only passively evolved since $z \sim 1.5$ (Stanford et al. 1997, Mullis et al. 2005, Stanford et al. 2005). However, recent bursts (≤ 5 Gyr) of star formation in the lower mass populations of clusters indicate not all galaxies have the same homogeneous star formation histories. Coupled with recent observations of a deficit in the red sequence at faint magnitudes in high redshift clusters (Nakata et al. 2001, Toft et al. 2004, de Lucia et al. 2005, Goto et al. 2005), it has been suggested that many of the galaxies seen along the red sequence may be recent additions, possibly driven onto the red sequence by a number of different processes at work in the cluster environment. However, the deficit seen in high redshift clusters may not be ubiquitous (Andreon 2006).

The blue populations of clusters have provided some of the earliest indications of galaxy

evolution: the increasing fraction of blue galaxies with redshift (Butcher & Oemler 1978, 1984; hereafter BO84). A substantial effort (Couch et al. 1994, Rakos & Schombert 1995, Ellingson et al. 2001, Martin et al. 2000, Tran et al. 2003, Finn et al. 2004) has been undertaken to understand the elusive blue galaxies in clusters and what this population – observed only in distant clusters – has become by today. So far, the blue-cluster population appears to consist of relatively low mass, young galaxies likely to end up along the red sequence after (and assuming) their star-bursting phase quenches (Couch et al. 1994, Barger et al. 1996, de Propris et al. 2003, Tran et al. 2003, Homeier et al. 2005, Crawford et al. 2006). Their final magnitudes, however, are unknown. If these blue galaxies in intermediate redshift clusters go through relatively little fading, they will remain near the bright end of the red sequence luminosity function by today. Quantifying a deficit of red galaxies as a function of luminosity and redshift thereby constrains the transformation mechanisms for these galaxies as a function of mass.

In this chapter, we discuss the observations, data reduction, and analysis of the WLTV data. The state-of-the art in cluster-population studies now demands high-precision both in terms of number statistics and random measurement errors. This statement is re-doubled for us, particularly in the area of photometry since our approach will be to capitalize on precision photometric redshifts. With appropriate precision *and* accuracy, this approach gives us an advantage over spectroscopic surveys in that we have complete distance and rest-frame information on flux-limited samples. Achieving high precision is based both on the data quality and the level, depth, and sophistication of the analysis. We therefore go to some length to describe our methods in detail.

In addition to the description of observations and reduction of the WIYN data in §2.2.1, we describe the observations and reductions of the supplementary data from the WIYN 0.9m (§2.2.2) and from the Hubble Space Telescope Archive (§2.2.3). The calibration of the WIYN data set is discussed in §2.3. In §2.4, we describe the process for object detection, estimating the completeness, and separating stars from galaxies. The photometric analysis of our data, including discussion of a process to measure the total magnitude from all types of objects with small systematic errors, is in §2.5. We measure photometric redshifts for all detected objects through a unique combination of template and training-set methods (§2.6). Further photometric properties derived from the ground-

and spaced-based data are described in §2.7. We present basic results on cluster populations in §2.8. These include the measurement of the color-magnitude relationships for cluster galaxies, the blue fraction of galaxies in these clusters, and the red-sequence cluster luminosity function.

2.2 Observations

2.2.1 WIYN 3.5m Observations

Observations were obtained with the WIYN ¹ 3.5m telescope’s Mini-Mosaic Camera. The Mini-Mo camera is constructed from two SITE 4096 × 2048 CCDs separated by a $\sim 10''$ gap. Mini-Mo has a pixel scale of 0.14 arcsec per pixel and $9.'6 \times 9.'6$ field of view. For this program, 75 partial-nights of observations² were obtained over a seven-year period from October 1999 through April 2005.

Primary observations were obtained in Harris UBRI filters for all clusters fields. Each year, we would attempt to obtain 4 images of ten minutes in the BRI and 4 images of 20 minutes in the U filter, although we were only able to accomplish this for one cluster over the entire course of the survey. Scheduling, weather, and/or instrumentation problems prevented us from full sampling, but this is not relevant to the analysis at hand. Most observations of individual fields followed a random dither pattern of offsets between subsequent observations of 15 – 30 arcseconds.

As part of this thesis, we also obtained Gunn z-band (Schneider, Gunn, & Hoessel 1983) observations of the clusters. The z-band data, obtained mainly in year four of the survey, increases the redshift limit of the photometric redshifts to $z \sim 1.25$ and provides a measurement of rest frame B band for all our cluster targets.

As the hall-mark of the thesis observations, we obtained narrow-band imaging in custom-designed filters for six of the highest redshift clusters in the WLTV sample. Six narrow-band filters (which we have named O1, O2, etc.) were tailored to measure $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ at the rest-frame of each

¹The WIYN Observatory is a joint facility of the University of Wisconsin-Madison, Indiana University, Yale University, and the National Optical Astronomy Observatories.

²This project began as a multi-institutional collaboration. Since 2001 (9 semesters), UW has allocated 50.5 nights for the program, of which 22 were generously granted for thesis observations of Glenn and Crawford. Seven of these 50.5 nights were completely unusable. The remaining time has come via application through the NOAO peer-review system and Director’s discretionary time.

cluster, and adjacent spectral continuum. A seventh, existing narrow-band filter (KP1512) was used to augment the spectral-continuum measurements. The details of the filter design, manufacture and calibration are found in Chapter 4. The emission line at $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ is an indicator of un-obscured star formation in galaxies. We will use the narrow-band observations to identify cluster galaxies, improve photometric redshifts, and measure star formation rates in cluster galaxies. The data reduction is identical for narrow- and broad-band images. Figure 2.1 summarizes the filter-set used in our survey.

2.2.1.1 Image Processing

In order to produce the high quality science data, we developed a mixture of standard and custom reduction software. The final algorithm produced images with little background variation ($< 1\%$) and stable photometry across the field of view of the chip. We outline the steps we have taken in order to produce reduced data, the reason for unique steps, and any quality issues that may arise from the process.

All data were pre-processed with an IDL task written by A. Saha in order to correct a pedestal affect in the over-scan region. This task would perform a line-by-line subtraction of the overscan region and replace with an average value for later processing by IRAF. In addition, this program would also identify ghosts caused by cross-talk of the amplifiers while reading out saturated objects. The pixels that were contaminated by the ghost images were replaced with large negative values and masked from subsequent use.

The following steps were accomplished within the IRAF mosaic CCD reduction package, MSCRED. Over-scan regions (now corrected) were subtracted from the image data and trimmed. For each night, a master bias was constructed from combining all the bias frames. Some bias frames had to be discarded, e.g., frames taken after the CCD was sitting un-used for a period of time (a built up charge on the CCD would appear as a gradient across the CCD), or frames taken when a bright source of light was in the dome (such as when the dome shutters were open during the day). In addition to bias frames, dome-flat corrections were applied to the science frames to correct for the pixel to pixel variations in the camera.

We then combined the multi-extension FITS format image (where each amplifier was an individual extension) into a single image. Due to early errors in the WCS header information in

Mini-Mo, we produced our own transformations based on astrometric measurements of the data. These transformations only apply to the translation of the chips from each other—not any rotation or magnification differences, which are accounted for when we create mosaic images. At this point, the images were cleaned for cosmic rays using the IRAF task IMCLEAN. The images were then grouped by filter, with the remaining reductions processed for each group.

Grouping of data by filter was done either at the night or run level, depending if enough data existed during a given night in a single filter. Despite the processing concluded by this phase, significant structure still remained in the background of these images. Since twilight flats are difficult to obtain at the WIYN telescope due to scattered light permitted by the open design of the WIYN structure, we produced sky flats based on our (dark sky) imaging data. Down to 3σ -significance above the sky variation, all pixels in our image data were masked. The sky-flat image was produced from a median combination of the masked images with a 2.5σ -clipping algorithm to remove any remaining variation between the frames. Some frames were removed by hand to further eliminate any structure in the sky flat, due usually to small offsets between subsequent frames or saturated stars. The sky-flat was spatially median-filtered with a 5×5 pixel kernel to remove any remaining small-scale structure, and the science data were corrected with the smoothed sky-flat.

Nonetheless, small scale variations still remained in the images corrected with the above sky-flats. Fringing was evident in the deep RIz images, as was scattered light in all bands. Again, because the WIYN telescope has a very open design to minimize the deleterious affects of thermal variations on image quality, depending on the position of the telescope, we observe gradients in the image background due to scattered light from the moon (making deep observations with the WIYN telescope during bright time virtually impossible), during twilight, and perhaps even due to glow from Tucson. In addition, nearby very bright stars would also leave distinct patterns on the data. We corrected fringing and scattered light together by making a "sky image" in a similar manner to the sky-flat described above, except the data were not spatially smoothed. Fringe and scattered-light corrections were applied to all images in all filters using standard IRAF routines in the ccdproc package. Where necessary, the "sky images" were also made for different telescope pointings. Occasionally, too few images were available to make clean sky images; and in these rare

cases, artifacts from the original images remained. If the sky structure affected a greater area of the image than the artifacts present in the sky-image, then the correction was applied, and regions with significant artifacts were removed (if possible) by hand, or masked. In some cases, a sky image from a run closest in date was used for any necessary corrections.

The final correction was to *subtract* a low-order (order 2) fit to the background of the data images. This was applied to each individual frame as the sky-image subtraction would leave a non-zero background level or, occasionally, gradients across the field. Bright objects were masked prior to surface-fitting. The amplitude of this correction is at the level of 0.5% of the original background level.

For each image a pixel mask was created. Bad pixels, columns, and other cosmetic defects on the CCD were flagged along with any artifacts introduced in the reduction process. Pixel regions affected by saturated stars (either the saturation itself or the ghost created by cross-talk between the amplifiers) were also masked. Finally, cosmic rays and asteroids were masked. Some of the masking was automated (cosmetic defects, ghosting), but every image was eventually examined, and masked, by hand.

2.2.1.2 Image Combination: Mosaics

For each band, we combined all the images in a filter for each field into a single deep mosaic. The total exposure time, seeing, and 50% stellar completeness (§4) for each cluster image is listed in Table 2.1. The final, effective area for the mosaics is roughly 11.6×11.6 due to the dithering of different frames, but we use an area of 9.3×9.3 for our data analysis. This area corresponds to a region of our data that has similar coverage in each mosaic and is complete in all of the bands. Since the same dither pattern was not followed for each filter during each observing run, regions beyond this area lack uniform depth in all bands. Furthermore, by only including this region, we exclude regions with only moderate depth (only a few images contributing to the pixels). Also, because we apply a weighting scheme to account for the different PSF from image to image instead of degrading all the images to a single value, regions with only a few images contributing can have much different stellar PSF than the interior regions. For the six fields presented in this thesis, the total area used for analysis corresponds to 0.14 sq. deg imaged in five broad band and two narrow band filters. The

final total area (including regions of lowered sensitivity) of the WLTV survey is expected to be 0.4 sq. deg imaged in five broad band filters.

The following steps were followed in order to produce these mosaics.

First, each image from a single exposure is split into two images corresponding to the two CCDs in the Mini-Mosaic system. This allowed for independent transformations to be calculated for each CCD. For example, a small rotation exists between the two chips, not taken into account by our earlier transformations. By transforming each chip individually, small ($< 1\%$) differences in magnification or rotation between the two chips, which may be caused by thermal variations or mechanical differences between runs over years, also can be corrected. This step is important because a 0.1% error in the solution across the face of a 4028 pixel CCD can cause a difference of 4 pixels or $\sim 0.5''$ in the centroid of a star.

In later runs with good seeing, we used a dither pattern that yielded a significant overlap region between the two chips (1-2'). Images with the most significant overlap would be used to create an astrometric reference image. All data would then be transformed onto this reference frame. In order to do this, ~ 100 stars would be automatically matched between each frame and the reference frame. Transformations would be calculated using the IRAF task GEOMAP, with typically errors in the transformation less than 0.3 pixels for each frame. Each image and mask would be transformed onto a single reference frame.

Second, for each image, a weight was calculated after they were normalized for differences in exposure time. Following Bershady, Lowenthal & Koo (1998), the weight was set so that

$$w = \frac{F}{\sigma_{sky} \times FWHM}, \quad (2.1)$$

where F is the average flux from an observed, fiducial star, σ_{sky} is the deviation of the sky background, and $FWHM$ is the full-width half-maximum of the stellar point spread function (F and $\sigma_{sky} \times FWHM$ have the same units, with the units for $FWHM$ in pixels). No other corrections were applied to the data, but images with deviantly poor transparency or bad image quality were removed.

Third, the data were combined into a single deep mosaic using a weighted, masked mean. Mosaics were visually inspected for artifacts, cosmic rays, or other defects that may have escaped the masking process: these defects were masked by hand. Furthermore, we checked by hand that the sky

background in each frame was leveled to the same value within $0.1\sigma_{sky}$. The processes was iterated until a clean, flat mosaic was produced. This image is used for photometry. We also produce a “weight image” by combining the masks with the same weights used for the mosaic. The final weight-image is produced by taking the square root of the initial weighted sum of masks, after normalizing the mean pixel value to unity. A detection image is produced by the product of the photometry image and the weight image, as it has the same background noise level (in counts) across the entire frame. The actual depth varies with position, as given by the weight image.

2.2.2 WIYN 0.9m Observations

For the purpose of photometric calibration, we observed our fields at the WIYN 0.9m telescope. Observations were obtained with the S2KB camera. The S2KB camera has a pixel scale of $0.6''$ per pixel and $20 \times 20'$ field of view. Poor weather conditions prevented us from observing on 43 of the 50 nights allocated at the 0.9m, and of the seven nights that we did open, only three could be considered photometric.

The data were reduced using standard IRAF CCD data reductions. First, over-scan regions and bias frames were subtracted from the images. Dome-flat images, taken either the day of or after the observations, corrected the variation in pixel sensitivity. Residuals from the dome-flat images were typically corrected from sky flat images taken near twilight. These reductions produced flat science images ($< 1\%$) after processing.

In order to calibrate our target data, we observed three Landolt (1992) standard fields five times a night. Fields were chosen to provide ample coverage for calculating solutions at a wide range of air masses, stellar colors, luminosity, and time of night. Solutions were calculated for each of the nights and we constructed a database of calibrated stars in each of the fields in a minimum of two bands.

2.2.3 HST WFPC2 and ACS Observations

The clusters were initially selected because, among other virtues, these fields had extant HST imaging. In addition to the original WFPC2 data, four of the clusters have ACS imaging as well. In Table 2.2 we list the details of the HST observations. For all of the HST imaging, the basic

data reductions were accomplished using the HST data reduction pipeline. Furthermore, we have primarily used WFPC2 association images for any analysis. The data were obtained from MAST³. Zeropoints for HST images were derived from information in the image headers or the appropriate HST handbook. The HST data is used for photometric calibration and for measuring image-structural properties of our galaxies, such as size, image-concentration, and asymmetry. Many of the sources detected in our WIYN images are unresolved in this ground-based data, despite superb seeing.

The classic chevron shape of WFPC2 images a $150'' \times 150''$ “L”-shaped field plus a smaller $34'' \times 34''$ square field. We have confined ourselves to the “L”-shaped region, where the pixel sampling is $0.1''$ per pixel. Most of the clusters were imaged in two filters and sometimes at several different regions within our WIYN Mini-Mo mosaics. For most clusters, “association images” were available; these are high-quality, astrometrically-mosaiced data. For a few clusters, association images did not exist and mosaics were created in the same manner as the WIYN data.

The Advanced Camera for Surveys (ACS) Wide Field Channel provides a $202 \times 202''$ field of view over two CCDs with a plate scale of $0.049''/\text{pixel}$. Three clusters (MS0451, Cl0016, Cl1604) have one pointing with ACS in two filters, while the majority of our WIYN image of MS1054 is sampled by multiple ACS pointings and filters. We have mosaiced the data in a similar procedure as the WIYN data.

2.3 Photometric Calibration

The WIYN Mini-Mo data were calibrated, fundamentally, by comparing the photometry of stellar objects in the Mini-Mosaic images (§4.1) to a number of referent standard sources to yield a set of tertiary standards in each program field. The referents included Landolt (1992) standard-stars or Massey et al. (1988) spectrophotometric stars observed during WIYN 3.5m and WIYN 0.9m telescope runs, program-field stars in HST images, and program-field sources with photometry published in the literature. Sources from the literature include Sloan Digital Sky Survey Data Release Four (SDSS-DR4; Adelman-McCarthy et al. 2006), and photometry from previous surveys of these regions (Ellingson et al. 1998, Postman et al. 1998, van Dokkum et al. 1999, Dietrich et al. 2006).

³The Multimission Archive at the Space Telescope Science Institute (MAST) is operated under STScI by the Association of Universities for Research in Astronomy, Inc., under NASA contract NAS5-26555.

All pre-existing photometry was transformed onto our filter system. Transformations as a function of color were calculated for the different filter sets using the Gunn & Stryker (1982) atlas of stars. All our photometry used for calibration purposes uses apertures corresponding to the so-called Petrosian magnitude scheme described in §5.2. This is useful because the SDSS-DR4 uses the same aperture scheme, and, more generally, for Gaussian light profiles these apertures enclose at least 99% of the total light.

Not all of the bands in all of the fields have the independent calibration described above. However, such calibration does exist for all BRI bands, some z, and a few U bands. This is summarized in Table 2.1. For bands which have an independent calibration source, we estimate the typical error in calibration via this source is below 1 – 5% depending on the quality of solutions or published data. Investigations of solutions for the zeropoint with position or CCD show no meaningful difference. This indicates that our reductions are capable of producing high-quality photometric images.

For the cases where independent calibration did not exist, calibration is accomplished by comparing the observed position of the stellar locus in color-color diagrams to those derived from the Gunn & Stryker atlas. Judicious choices of bands always allowed for unique determination of photometric zeropoint offsets in bands without independent calibration. Through this method, we estimate relative and absolute calibration uncertainties are below 5%, assuming no large metallicity differences between the Gunn-Stryker catalog and our field stars. As a demonstration, we present the stellar locus of observed Galactic stars with $18 < R < 22.5$ in all our fields in relevant two-color diagrams in Figures 2.2 to 2.4.

All of our magnitudes were corrected for galactic extinction using the Schegel et al. (1998) extinction values from NED⁴ for each pointing. The extinction correction for each galaxy was appropriately modified for color-terms in each band-pass by fitting a small set of model spectral energy distributions (SED) to the observed broad- and narrow-band magnitudes, and then calculating the necessary correction for both the broad and narrow bands. The difference in the correction between red and blue sources was relatively small in most bands, but was up to 0.05 magnitudes in the U-band.

⁴The NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database (NED) is operated by the Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, under contract with the National Aeronautics and Space Administration.

All magnitudes presented in this work are on the Vega system.

2.4 Source Detection

Object detection for each cluster was performed on individual “detection images” (mosaics, §2.1.2) and the sum of the UBRIZ mosaics images. The detection software used was the now-standard SExtractor by Bertin & Arnouts (1996). Detection criteria required objects to contain > 20 contiguous pixels above 1.5σ of the sky noise. The parameters were set after several iterations of detection using SExtractor on our fields and on simulated fields. The goal was to detect as many real objects as possible while minimizing contamination from noise. Object detection was performed in all bands for two reasons: (1) to detect objects that may be obscured in the red bands by saturated stars and (2) to detect objects that may only appear in one, or a sub-set of bands. In the work presented in this thesis, the R-band and narrow-band detections are the catalogs from which we draw our sources.

Detection completeness was determined via Monte Carlo simulations by re-inserting real objects back into the images. Objects for re-insertion were selected from bright sources in each image to represent a range of sizes and shapes. The objects were dimmed, and then reinserted into the fields. In each field, fifty objects were inserted at a time to prevent over-crowding in the image. The magnitudes for each object were assigned randomly within a half-magnitude range at a time. The process is iterated, so that 250 galaxies are re-inserted in each half-magnitude bin. The completeness for stellar objects in each band of each field is presented in Figure 2.5. The 50% completeness limits for each field and band are tabulated in Table 2.1. For the R-band image in each field, we present the completeness limits for objects with different sizes in Figure 2.6. The sizes chosen correspond roughly to the stellar PSF (smallest size), and $2\times$ and $3\times$ this value, which in turn correspond loosely to the lower, mid-point and upper-bound of the observed size distribution to the limits of our data. The detailed size values are dictated by the specific templates chosen for the completeness simulations.

An important requirement for our science is that we are complete in our source detection for the measurement of specific objects of interest. A majority of this study is focused on Luminous Compact Blue Galaxies, which, in Chapter 3, we define to have the following parameters: $M_B < -18.5$, $(B - V)_o < 0.5$, and $\bar{\mu}_e < 21$. We also compare LCBGs to other cluster populations, such as red galaxies, to the same limiting luminosity. According to the Fundamental plane, a spheroidal galaxy

with $M_B = -18.5$ would have a size $r_e = 1.25$ kpc (Shen et al. 2003). To show that we are complete for detecting these particular sources, we plot the observed magnitude-radius and magnitude-color distribution for all objects in each field in Figures 2.7 to 2.12. We over-plot the selection limits for these two classes of objects in our different fields. For the red galaxies, we assume the SED of an elliptical galaxy (Coleman, Wu, & Weedman 1980) for the K-correction, and for the LCBG, NGC4449 (Bruzual & Charlot 2003). We do not assume any evolution for the elliptical SED with redshift or changes in metallicity due to location along the cluster red sequence. For all the fields, we are complete for detecting LCBGs beyond $z \sim 1$, but we are likely missing some of the red galaxies to the luminosity limit of $M_B = -18.5$ at $z = 0.9$ if no color evolution occurs in the red population.

2.4.1 Star-Galaxy Separation

Galactic stars were identified and removed from subsequent analysis based on measurements of their (1) apparent size and (2) apparent colors.

(1) Apparent size: All stellar sources are expected to have a half-light radius consistent with the point-spread function (PSF). For each source, a weighted metric based on the absolute difference between $r_{0.5}$ and $r_{0.5}$ for the PSF in each band is calculated ($r_{0.5}$ is the half-light radius). The weighting is based on the $r_{0.5}$ of the PSF in such a sense that images with better seeing are weighted more heavily. Except at the mosaic edges, where a small number of images may be contributing to the mosaic, the PSF across the final mosaics is relatively uniform ($< 5\%$ variation across the image). Therefore, we do not assume any variation of the PSF with position while excluding areas with shallow depths from this analysis. A selection on the basis of image-structure alone, of course, will include AGN and un-resolved galaxies. The latter are of particular interest to the present study, and therefore we do not wish to exclude them.

(2) Apparent colors: We expect Galactic stars will also have colors consistent with the stars in the Gunn-Stryker (1982) atlas. A χ^2 fit is calculated for all objects in flux space between the Gunn-Stryker locus and the observed SED. The weighting for the χ^2 fit is set to a constant value so that we can differentiate between sources that would have similar values if the weighting were set by the flux errors: high signal to noise sources which have good fits because they match the stellar color distribution and low signal to noise sources that would have good fits because of their large

magnitude errors.

From these two measurements, we identify Galactic stars as objects with half-light radii consistent with the PSF and colors consistent with stars. The exact constraints used to identify stars by the two parameters (size and color) is determined from the HST imaging and varies between the different fields. Using the HST imaging, we estimate that we can reliably exclude Galactic stars based on our WIYN data to under 2% for $R < 22.5$. Below $R = 22.5$ mag we do not attempt to remove any stars; expectations for the stellar contamination at these magnitudes are 7% based on the HST data.

2.5 Photometry of Extended Sources

Photometry is the foundation on which most of extra-galactic astronomy is built. From the earliest measurements of counts of galaxies to recent comparisons of massive surveys, the techniques used to measure photometry can produce drastically different results (Cross et al. 2004). Many fundamental measurements depend on accurate photometry including galaxy counts, luminosity-size relationship, luminosity functions, color-magnitude diagrams, and surface brightness distributions (Cross et al. 2004, Chang et al. 2005, Graham et al. 2005) not to mention the many well know correlations that exist for galaxies between their photometric and spectroscopic characteristics. As such, providing accurate and precise photometry is critical for any analysis of imaging data. In this section, we describe the different photometric techniques we use for data analysis and the benefits of these techniques.

2.5.1 Photometric Methods

The simplest photometric method employs a fixed aperture. In this work, the sizes of fixed apertures are set to measure the flux for a pre-determined physical region or to maximize the signal to noise of a fiducial source. The advantage of aperture photometry is the ability to measure the same physical regions in different images and to minimize random errors using small apertures. Larger, fixed apertures will have larger random errors due to the inclusion of more sky, but these apertures will have smaller systematic errors. Due to the fixed nature of the apertures, aperture photometry cannot account for the variation seen in different populations of galaxies in size and shape, but they

can be set to measure the photometry for one class of objects (i.e. unresolved objects, galaxies at a certain redshift) very well.

Within our data set, aperture photometry is used for comparing magnitudes in different bands to model SEDs, e.g., for the calculation of photometric redshifts. The identification of emission line objects in our narrow-band data also uses a small aperture set to measure the flux at the maximum in signal to noise of the light profile for a galaxy with an exponential light-profile with $r_{0.5} = 8$ kpc at the redshift of each cluster, while the emission line flux is determined in a larger aperture set to include 99% of the light from the same source. Whenever aperture photometry is used to compare magnitudes from different bands, the magnitudes are measured in images that have been degraded to the worst seeing.

The second magnitude that we use is a Petrosian magnitude, (Petrosian 1976, Kron 1995) which depends on the Petrosian index, η . For our purposes, the Petrosian index is defined as

$$\eta(r) = I(r) / \langle I(r) \rangle, \quad (2.2)$$

where $\langle I(r) \rangle$ is the average surface brightness within r and $I(r)$ is the surface brightness at r . This definition is the inverse of the original definition by Petrosian (1976), and has the property where $\eta(r) = 1$ at the center of the galaxy and drops to zero at the edge. Following Bershady, Jangren, & Conselice (2000), we define the Petrosian magnitude as the magnitude within an aperture that is twice the size of the Petrosian radius, r_p . The Petrosian radius is defined as the radius where $\eta = 0.2$. We use the Petrosian magnitude for reporting colors of objects. To first order, the Petrosian magnitude is independent of redshift as it depends on the ratio of two surface brightnesses, but because it is based on profile shape, changes in the profile due to morphological K-corrections still apply. However, the real strength of Petrosian magnitudes vs. other variable aperture photometry such as Kron magnitudes (Kron 1980) is that the Petrosian radius only depends on light interior to this radius. This aspect leads to small random errors in the measurement of r_p . Nonetheless, the magnitude within $2r_p$, relative to a true, total magnitude, is still profile dependent. Although 99% of the light from an exponential profile is recovered within $2r_p$, only 82% of the light for an $r^{1/4}$ profile is measured within $2r_p$ (Graham et al. 2005).

Consequently, we decided to use a modified Petrosian magnitude to find our “total” magnitude.

This magnitude is used for reporting apparent magnitudes, calculating absolute magnitudes, and measuring luminosity functions. Corrections to the Petrosian magnitude have been calculated by Graham et al. (2005) as a function of concentration index (for definitions of the concentration index, see §2.7.2) in order to return a profile-independent total flux, but we prefer a total magnitude derived through an iterative process measuring real flux rather than a single correction applied to the initial photometric measurement. Our total magnitude is defined as the magnitude within $r = \epsilon r_P$, where ϵ is a profile dependent factor that can be calculated based on the concentration. With an appropriate value of ϵ , the same amount of the light from any profile can be measured. The price of the accuracy of this measurement is the substantial random error associated with the large apertures required to measure the total flux (caused by large contributions of the sky to the measured magnitude). The price is particularly high for sources with high image concentration (such as $r^{1/4}$ -law profiles), while for profiles which are close to exponential (or less concentrated), random errors are relatively small ($\epsilon < 2$). In the following section, we outline the exact algorithm used to calculate this magnitude.

2.5.2 Adaptive-Aperture Photometry: A New Algorithm for Calculating Total Magnitudes

Calculation of the total magnitude requires several steps and is an iterative process. Through iteration we are able to improve the removal of contaminating objects, improve sky subtraction, and provide a more precise estimate of ϵ due to improved measurements of the total magnitude and concentration index, which for our purposes depends on the total magnitude. For these comparison calculations, we use C_{2080} defined from the total magnitude for our measurement, whereas the “corrected magnitude” of Graham et al. (2005) uses C_{2080} based on a Petrosian magnitude. Throughout this work, the magnitude derived through the following algorithm is referred to as the “total magnitude.”

- Step 1. Construct the curve of growth (COG) of the light profile. To construct the COG, we use 50, logarithmically spaced, circular apertures from a radius of 0.067 to 14 arcsec with the PHOT task in DAOPHOT. The area of each aperture is estimated from the number of unmasked pixels. To prevent contamination, objects surround the target are masked. Mask sizes are computed from the isophotal area from the initial detection. If the masked area from one object overlaps the target’s masked area, the overlapping area is left unmasked. Bad pixels,

cosmetic defects, and blank regions are also masked.

- Step 2. Correct the COG. The curve of growth is corrected for poor sky subtraction and object contamination. Poor sky subtraction is corrected by requiring the COG to asymptote to a single value at large radii. On subsequent iterations, contaminating flux from nearby objects is subtracted from the COG. For all nearby objects (within $1'$ of the target), the amount of unmasked flux contributed to the COG was estimated by integrating over the intersection of the object's Sèrsic profile (§2.7.4) and each aperture in the COG. The parameters of the profile (n , r_e , and I_e) are determined from the half-light radius, concentration index, and total magnitude. The objects are subtracted after each iteration using the improved estimate for each object's parameters to improve the subtraction.
- Step 3. Measure characteristics. For each aperture, the surface brightness, average surface brightness, and η are calculated. We determine r_p from the η distribution and then calculate the total magnitude. For the first pass, $\epsilon = 2$ is used for the calculation of the total magnitude. Finally, we calculate $r_{0.5}$ and C_{2080} . All values are calculated through interpolating between different apertures in the curve of growth.
- Step 4. Repeat until convergence. Steps 2-3 were repeated until the magnitudes of the objects converged. For these later iterations, ϵ was set based on the concentration index.

The relationship between ϵ , such that the aperture encloses 99% of the light and the concentration index is plotted in Figure 2.13. This relationship is determined by simulating the Sèrsic equation for different values of n and calculating r_p , C_{2080} , and the radius enclosing 99% of the light. This figure is further discussed in §2.7.2. When calculating the total magnitude, we use an ϵ required to measure 98% of the light as this leads to much smaller random errors for objects with large concentrations. Tabulated values for ϵ as a function of concentration index and n for both the 98% and 99% total magnitudes are provided in Table 2.3.

2.5.3 Comparison of Different Photometric Methods

By assessing the errors associated with each photometric method, we can quantify the usefulness of the methods for different applications. In order to measure the errors, we simulated different

galaxy profiles by modeling a Sèrsic profile (§7.4, equation 6) with values of n ranging from 0.5-6. We measured the photometry over 1000 iterations at six different signal-to-noise levels (100, 50, 25, 10, 5, 3) measured at $r_{0.5}$. For each profile (except the aperture magnitudes), we assume $r_{0.5} = 5$ pixels, which in our data would correspond to $r_{0.5} = 0.70''$ in the WIYN data. We do not apply any degradation due to seeing. The noise errors are assumed to be Gaussian and are set to a typical value for an R-band image of $\sigma_{sky} = 5$ counts/pixel. We report the systematic and random errors in Figure 2.14 and highlight the errors for a Gaussian, exponential, and $r^{1/4}$ profile as represented by profiles with $n = 0.5, 1, \text{ and } 4$. In this Figure, the systematic error, Δm , is given such that a positive value represents an underestimation of the total flux. For comparison with data from MS0451, an unresolved object with $R \sim 25.4$ will have $S/N = 10$ at $r_{0.5} = 0.42''$ with slight variation in the other fields. We note that this is slightly beyond our 50% detection limit.

We test the following six different magnitudes: two fixed aperture magnitudes, a Petrosian magnitude, a Kron magnitude, a corrected Petrosian magnitude following Graham et al. (2005), and our total magnitude. We do not present the measurements for isophotal magnitudes due to their many deficiencies including cosmological effects (Blanton et al. 2001), sky surface brightness effects, and systematic errors associated with the magnitude, shape, signal to noise, and size of an object. One of the fixed apertures measures the flux within an aperture with the size set by the radius at which the signal to noise is maximized for a Gaussian object with a FWHM typical of our R-band seeing ($0.7''$). The other fixed aperture magnitude is set to recover 98% of the flux for an exponential light profile with $r_{0.5} = 1.24''$, the expected upper limit in size for a disk galaxy at $z = 0.55$ (Simard et al. 1997). The central surface brightness of the profiles is set so that the two above specified galaxies have a signal to noise at $r_{0.5}$ specified in each plot. The simulated objects for the aperture magnitude measurements have the same properties as these two given objects, except n varies from 0.5-6 (from left to right along the curve in the Figure) in steps of 0.5.

The Kron (1980) magnitude is similar to the Petrosian magnitude except it is defined as the flux within $2r_1$, where

$$r_1 = \frac{2\pi \int I(r)r^2 dr}{2\pi \int I(r)r dr}. \quad (2.3)$$

This equation is integrated until the object's surface brightness falls below 1% of the sky surface

brightness. This equation is appropriate for a 1-D profile. In SExtractor, a pseudo-Kron magnitude is employed, which uses an aperture of $2.5r_1$, and a slightly different form for the integral over 2-D (Bertin & Arnout 1998, Graham & Driver 2005). The corrected Petrosian magnitude is a Petrosian magnitude with a correction based on the concentration index of the profile (Graham et al. 2005). A correction is applied to both the magnitude and $r_{0.5}$. The “total flux” used for the definition of the concentration index is important to calculating the value of this correction. For these simulations, we use C_{2080} calculated from the Petrosian magnitude.

As can be seen in Figure 2.14, the small aperture magnitudes have small random errors with large systematic errors, whereas the larger aperture magnitudes have smaller systematic errors but larger random errors⁵. The significant variation in the sizes and shapes of any galaxy population makes aperture magnitudes inappropriate for measuring total fluxes as only an extremely large aperture would measure a comparable flux between different objects. However, the low random error and consistency in sampling the galaxy’s flux in the same physical region between bands makes aperture magnitudes ideal for calculating magnitudes for measuring photometric redshifts or fitting model spectral energy distributions. By sampling the same region, the same stellar populations are integrated. With smaller apertures the observed SEDs will be less affected by contaminating flux from neighboring sources. Further, the small errors allow greater discrimination between different SED models. Nonetheless, aperture magnitudes fail to sample the same region unless accurate alignment of the images exists and the seeing differences between the images is taken into account (Holwerda 2006). Our images have been aligned to sub-pixel accuracy and all of the images are degraded to the image with the worst seeing prior to measuring the aperture photometry.

As a large amount of recent galaxy surveys depend on the SExtractor “auto magnitude” (which is almost identical to the Kron magnitude defined here), it should be noted the improved performance of Petrosian magnitudes over Kron magnitudes. Both sources have systematic errors associated with large apertures, but the Petrosian magnitudes have smaller random errors at a given signal to noise and for a fixed profile shape with degrading signal to noise. Most of this difference

⁵Random errors for the large apertures would be smaller than those for the variable-aperture techniques if the simulated object was the same size as the object used in the other simulations. Random errors of the magnitudes simulated here depend on the assumed size, sampling, central surface brightness, and σ_{sky} of the simulations.

can be attributed to the nature of calculating r_1 vs. r_η : r_η only depends on information interior to the radius, whereas r_1 depends on exterior information. The definition of r_1 is isophotal in nature, and hence, r_1 suffers many of the same faults as isophotal magnitudes—even if they are reduced by hiding the isophotal nature in the integral of the size instead of a direct measurement—including a strong dependence on redshift (Blanton et al. 2001) and significant affects of sky noise at large radii. While it is possible to circumvent many of these failings (Bershady et al. 1994), such improvements have not been incorporated into SExtractor. Since Petrosian magnitudes have been integrated into SExtractor, we would suggest making them the default magnitude system if no further analysis exists. For the apparent colors reported in our work, we use Petrosian magnitudes because they provide a metric measurement for all galaxies with small random errors.

The only magnitudes that provide low systematic errors regardless of the profile shape are the corrected Petrosian magnitudes and total magnitudes. The two magnitudes seem to perform reasonable well down to low signal to noise ($S/N \sim 10$). The corrected Petrosian magnitude can be affected by small offsets in the concentration index especially at large C_{2080} where the correction is relatively large ($> 20\%$). For example, the steepness of the $C_{2080} - F_p/F_{tot}$ curve in Figure 2.13 for C_{2080} measured from the Petrosian magnitude can lead to dramatically different corrections for small changes in Petrosian C_{2080} . The total magnitudes do not suffer from this same fate because small errors in C_{2080} are a second order affect in the measurement of the total flux: an oversized aperture will still only measure the amount of flux within it and it will not overestimate the total magnitude due to too large an aperture. However, the total magnitude suffers from much worse random errors at low signal to noise due to the large apertures used to measure the flux. On the other hand, the total magnitude scheme is the best-performing method for objects with small n down to $S/N \sim 10$ due to the smaller radius used to measure the total flux. The high accuracy of the total magnitudes and small precision for exponential galaxies are the primary reasons for adopting it to calculate the true magnitudes for our sources.

2.5.3.1 Caveats

None of this analysis has included the affects of poor sky subtraction, crowding, color gradients, sampling, seeing, or irregular profiles. We make a few comments towards directing future work.

Poor sky subtraction and crowding (different objects very close together) will affect the methods with the largest final apertures the most. Our analysis (not presented here) indicates that leading galaxy photometry software (SExtractor, FOCAS) do very poorly in crowded fields. A significant source of this error is due to the allocation of the flux of a pixel: most packages allocate all of the pixels flux to a single object rather than dividing into different sources. Alternatively, DAOPHOT, which was designed for crowded field stellar photometry, fails to account for the different profiles and shapes of galaxies (indeed, it was not designed to do so). Our method of subtracting contaminating objects by realistic estimates of their shape increases the performance in crowded regions for all types of photometry.

Seeing and sampling will affect the measurement of the photometry in a number of ways, but one non-obvious way is in the measurement of the concentration index. Large seeing and small sampling (the kpc/pix ratio is large) will lead to an underestimation of the concentration index (§7.2).

Color gradients and any changes in the profile shape with bandpass will obviously affect photometry compared between different bands depending on the changes. The different distribution of stellar populations can make a galaxy unrecognizable when compared between the rest-frame Far-UV to Near-IR with irregular morphology tracing star formation dominating the UV and smooth distribution of older stellar populations in the IR. Sensible comparison of these different bands is only provided by total fluxes (which recover all the light from a source) or fixed apertures (which recover the light from a specific region). Finally, corrected Petrosian magnitudes can not account for complex light profiles due to truncation or changes in the light profile at large radii, irregular morphology, or underlying low surface brightness components.

2.6 Photometric Redshifts

Photometric redshifts provide a inexpensive method for determining the redshifts for a large sample of objects from photometry (Koo 1985). The two main methods for the measurement of photometric redshifts are template fitting and empirical training sets.

In the template fitting technique (Koo 1985, Gwyn & Hartwick 1996, Connolly et al. 1999, Fernandez-Soto et al 1999, Benítez 2000, Bolzonella, Miralles, & Pello 2000), the redshift is determined by comparing the observed multi-band magnitudes to sample of model SEDs suitably inte-

grated over the relevant band-passes. This comparison is done in a χ^2 sense, with a global minimum searched for over the parameter-space of redshift and SED-type. The model SEDs can either be from observed spectra (Coleman, Wu, & Weedman 1980, Kinney et al. 1996, Jansen et al. 2000) or created via stellar population synthesis models (e.g. Fioc & Rocca-Volmerange 1997, Leitherer et al. 1999, Bruzual & Charlot 2003). The template method can be used at all redshifts and for any colors, without any existing spectroscopic redshifts, to the extent that the templates span the required range of rest wavelength. This method is also limited by how well the model SEDs cover the full range of observed galaxy SEDs. In addition, small errors in calibration of the imaging photometry (including photometric zeropoints and accurate response functions of the atmosphere, telescope, filter, and CCD) can lead to significant systematic errors.

In the empirical method (Connolly et al. 1995, Brunner, Connolly, & Szalay 1999, Csabai et al. 2003), a polynomial function is fit to the observed relationship between spectroscopic redshift and apparent, multi-band magnitudes of a sample of galaxies. These galaxies are a training set which serve to map out the hyper-surface relating apparent magnitude and color to redshift. The benefits of the empirical relationship are small systematic errors due to calibration and random errors constrained by the data itself. However, the empirical method is only applicable over redshift and color regimes where the spectroscopic sample is complete. Both methods can be improved by the inclusion of Bayesian priors (Benítez 2000, Benítez et al. 2004), involving the magnitudes of galaxies, volume of space, luminosity functions, or sizes of galaxies, which may or may not bias the results (Benítez et al. 2004).

For our data set, we do have a large sample of spectroscopic redshifts for each of our fields (no published spectroscopic redshifts exist for the C11325 field, but the field itself and the filters used overlap with the C11322 field). For this reason, we have developed a photometric redshift technique that is a hybrid of the empirical and template methods. Previous work in this area (Budavári et al 2000, Csabai et al. 2003) has shown that a hybrid method can improve the performance of photometric redshifts.

2.6.1 Hybrid Procedure

Our photometric redshift method is a hybrid between the template fitting method and training set method similar to Csabai et al. (2003). We create a theoretical galaxy catalog using a set of observed (Kinney et al. 1996, Coleman, Wu, & Weedman 1980) and model galaxy spectra (Bruzual & Charlot 2003). Each spectra was redshifted in steps of $\Delta z = 0.01$ and convolved with our filter set to produce a database of model magnitudes from $z = 0 - 5$. Extragalactic extinction (due to neutral-hydrogen absorption along the line-of-sight) was applied to the magnitudes for high redshift sources, following the prescription of Madau (1995). Although this formulation is neither mathematically correct nor astrophysically accurate (Bershady et al. 1999), it is close enough for our current purposes, and has the expedient benefit of being simple to apply. For each of our clusters, we have approximately 100 spectroscopic redshifts within the field of view (Ellingson et al. 1998, Postman et al. 1998, Dressler et al. 1999, Tran et al. 1999). For each training set galaxy, we find the point in the database with the same redshift and the best fit to the observed SEDs. The fitting is done in magnitude space and the weighting is based on the observed photometric errors. Once the entire training set has been matched, we then calculate the shift in magnitude space required for the database in order to minimize the difference between the observed SEDs and the model SEDs. For unmatched points, the amplitude of the shift is averaged over all matched points with a weighting based on the distance between the matched point and unmatched point in magnitude and redshift space. Spectroscopic sources with high signal to noise are also given more weight. Effectively, the shape of the database in magnitude space is forced to conform to the observed magnitude distribution of the spectroscopic sample. The final step is to smooth the database along iso- z contours to minimize catastrophic shifts introduced during this process. This smoothed database is then applied to our full catalog of objects to calculate the photometric redshift.

To give an example of the effect on the database, we plot the before and after distribution of a simple database in color-color space in Figure 2.15 and in color-redshift space in Figure 2.16. This database has been constructed from only 7 template spectra which have been interpolated by a factor of 10 in color space. As can be seen, the database is shifted and rotated slightly to match the observed distribution of the spectroscopic sample (over plotted in the graph). A much larger template sample

and finer interpolation between models is used in the actual measurement of photometric redshifts.

2.6.2 Performance of the Hybrid Technique

Within our own data, we can test the reliability of the measurement from the large, published spectroscopic data-set available for sources in our fields. To test our method, we measured the photometric redshift for each galaxy with a spectroscopic redshift through the following process. In each catalog of spectroscopic training objects, we would remove one object, use the remaining galaxies as training galaxies, measure the photometric redshift of the excluded object, and then repeat for all the other objects in the catalog. In Figure 2.17, we present the comparison between spectroscopic and photometric measurements for the full spectroscopic sample of 568 objects. These measurements are made for the photometry that includes the narrow-bands. We find the sample has a dispersion of $\sigma_z = 0.05$ and offset of -0.002 once 3σ clipping algorithm is applied to eliminate sources with catastrophic errors. We do find that approximately 10% percent of the sample suffer from catastrophic errors, but we have not cleaned the sample of sources with poor astrometry or photometry. We expect this cleaning will remove about 10% of the catastrophic errors (1% of the sample); the majority of sources with catastrophic errors appear to be very blue galaxies with near-degeneracies in multi-color space for similar SEDs at disparate redshifts. This is a fundamental limitation of any of these photometric-redshift methods. In Figure 2.18, we plot the histogram of the difference between the photometric and spectroscopic redshift. The errors in the photometric redshift are non-Gaussian due to the broad wings at a very low level, but the central peak has a $FWHM = 0.04$, which would correspond to a Gaussian error of $\sigma = 0.017$!

Splitting our sample into the red and blue populations (Figure 2.19), the measured error in our sample as a function of signal to noise is close to the predicted value based on simulations of the effects of random photometric errors. The populations have been split by their apparent color with red galaxies having $B - I > 3$. For reference, an Sb galaxy is expected to have a color of $B - I = 3.25$ at $z = 0.55$. Each point represents the average dispersion and signal-to-noise of the population in each field. Having the narrow-band imaging increases the precision for both blue and red galaxies. The finer spectral sampling of the narrow-band imaging provides smaller errors even for galaxies without a specific spectral feature (emission or absorption) being sampled.

The error in the photometric redshift of each source is calculated through Monte Carlo simulations. The magnitudes in each band are re-calculated after applying the photometric error in each band, and then the photometric redshift is determined through the same manner as above. This process is repeated 100 times for each object. The error for red objects is better behaved than for blue objects, which tend to scatter to high redshifts ($z > 2$) due to the afore-mentioned degeneracies in color-redshift space. Inclusion of NIR data or Bayesian priors would reduce the degree of these degeneracies, thereby decreasing the occurrence of catastrophic errors.

2.6.3 Cluster Membership

Cluster membership is defined by a truncated probability distribution. We calculate the probability of an object being a cluster member following the prescription of Brunner and Lubin (2000). The redshift of each object is recalculated 100 times after applying the observed error distribution to its photometry. The probability of being in the cluster, $P(z)$, is then the number of times the absolute difference between the calculated photometric redshift and cluster redshift is less than the 1σ of the photometric redshift error. In Figure 2.20, we present the probability for all galaxies with $R < 24$ in the MS0451 field to be cluster members. Spectroscopic cluster members are indicated by large filled squares.

For each cluster we select a cutoff probability, $P(z)$, such that a galaxy is considered to be a cluster member if it has a probability above this threshold *and its photometric redshift is within ± 0.1 of the cluster redshift*. The latter criteria is a hard cut-off which does not vary with cluster. The probability cut-off value balances the effects of contamination due to field sources and missing bona fide cluster sources. We chose thresholds such that we are identifying 90% of the spectroscopically confirmed cluster sources with admitting only 10% contaminating sources (again based on statistics of spectroscopically confirmed sources). The exact value of $P(z)$ is set for each field and varies between 0.1 and 0.4; different filter-sets produce different distributions at different redshifts. No correction is applied to account for the different probabilities as a function of color. This has potentially significant ramifications for measurement of, e.g., the blue fraction.

The cluster membership calculated as we have described here is used in all ensuing analysis in this Chapter and Chapter 3. In Chapter 4, however, we use additional information from narrow-band

filters to further constrain the cluster membership of emission-line galaxies.

2.7 Other Galaxy Properties

Images of galaxies offer far more than the integrated light and color of galaxies. Light profiles offer an additional wealth of information on the internal structure of galaxies, and hence their form and evolution. For example, the correlation of galaxy size and luminosity appears to evolve between $z = 1$ and today (Simard et al. 1999, Ravindranath et al. 2004, McIntosh et al. 2005), perhaps providing direct evidence for galaxy growth with time. The concentration index and Sèrsic index both relate to the shape of a galaxy’s profile, and thereby stand as quantitative proxies (if not better alternatives for) classical morphology (Bershady et al. 2000). Recent interactions and mergers possibly can be assessed in the asymmetry of galaxies (Conselice, Bershady, & Gallagher 2000). We have measured indices of galaxy size, concentration and asymmetry for all objects in all of our images, with the specific methods described below. With the exception of image size, HST images are necessary for exploring concentration and asymmetry given the depth and angular size of typical objects in our survey. We have used the HST data to provide corrections, where necessary, for measurements made with the lower-resolution WIYN data.

In addition to the above surface-photometric quantities, we add another important galaxy property that can be derived from imaging data, namely local space-density. We couch this density in terms of the Σ_{10} parameter defined below. Other properties, such as star-formation rates and emission-line equivalent widths, are described in Chapter 4.

2.7.1 Size

We define the size of galaxies via two methods: the Petrosian radius, r_p , and the half-light radius, $r_{0.5}$. Recall r_p is the radius at which $\eta = 0.2$. Since it only depends on measurements of the curve of growth, it is very precise, but can only be compared between galaxies of similar profile shapes. The half light radius, $r_{0.5}$, is calculated as the radius at which the flux is one-half the total flux. Because of its dependency on the total flux, $r_{0.5}$ suffers from the same errors as the measurement of the total flux, although in our system, it should be free of profile-dependent errors.

2.7.2 Image Concentration

The concentration index has had many different definitions, but we follow Bershady et al. (2000), in turn motivated by Kent (1984), and adopt

$$C_{2080} = 5 \log(r_{20}/r_{80}), \quad (2.4)$$

where r_n is the radius in which $n\%$ of the light is enclosed. Our concentration index depends on the total flux, whereas previous measurements of the concentration index have used the Petrosian magnitude for the total flux. As the Petrosian magnitude systematically underestimates the total magnitude for galaxies with large concentration indexes, the concentration index estimated via the Petrosian magnitude is smaller for a galaxy with large concentration as seen in Figure 2.13. For comparison, we also plot C_{5090} , the concentration index using radii including 50% and 90% of the light, which is used by the SDSS (Blanton et al. 2001).

The concentration index is related to the profile shape and can be used as a proxy for morphology. For the purpose of comparison with previous studies, we use the C_{2080} index for measurements of our sample. In this definition, a Gaussian, exponential, and $r^{1/4}$ profile will have values of $C_{2080} = 2.15, 2.80, 5.27$.

In Figure 2.21, we compare the concentration index measured for all objects in the ACS field-of-view of the MS0451 cluster to simulations of the effects of pixel sampling. In the ACS data, large measured concentrations are not found for galaxies with small apparent sizes. A smooth envelope defines the upper limit at any radius. We suspect this trend is due to a sampling effect: Bershady et al. (2000) have warned about the deleterious effects of poor sampling on measuring image-concentration, specifically suggesting this quantity be measured for objects larger than $r_{0.5} > 0.3''$ in HST WFPC-2 images.

To better understand the limits of measuring image-concentration in our superior ACS data, we generated simulations of the effects of degraded sampling on the measurement of C_{2080} for two light-profiles with Sèrsic index $n = 1$ and 3.8. In effect, we decrease $r_{0.5}$ while keeping the pixel scale a constant. As can be seen, the measured index of the more concentrated object displays a trend of slow decline before rapidly falling off below $r_{0.5} \sim 4$ pixels. Regardless of initial concentration value, all profiles with intrinsic $C_{2080} > 3$ eventually display this asymptotic behavior. The reason for this

rapid turnover is that the r_{20} (20%) radius is approaching 1 pixel in size, which makes an accurate value difficult to measure. However, many objects have sizes below $r_{0.5} > 0.3''$, where measurement of C_{2080} becomes significantly degraded. When interpreting our results we consider the possibility that their true concentration index is much larger.

2.7.3 Asymmetry

Our asymmetry index uses the definition of Conselice, Bershady, & Jangren (2000):

$$A = \frac{\Sigma I_o - I_{180}}{2\Sigma I_o} - B_{180}, \quad (2.5)$$

where I_o is the pixel intensity and I_{180} is the intensity in a pixel corresponding to a 180° rotation from that pixel. B_{180} is a correction for the average asymmetry of the background.

As prescribed by Conselice et al., when measuring the asymmetry, we allow the light-profile center to be a free parameter within r_p , which allows for much smaller values of A , in some cases, than when the center is fixed by, e.g., the centroid of the light distribution. For most galaxies, the center found via minimizing rotation asymmetry is very similar to the light centroid, but for cometary galaxies the two can be significantly different. In contrast to other studies, we find the required centering calculation which minimizes the rotational asymmetry is a primary weakness of this method, especially for high redshift sources. This is because there are frequent occurrences of local minima in asymmetry as a function of center location.

The asymmetry measurement also suffers from sampling issues. Conselice et al. (2000) suggest a minimum sampling of 0.5 kpc per resolving element. Lotz et al. (2004) suggest any sampling coarser than 1 kpc/pix will result in poor measurement of the asymmetry value. Many of our sources have diameters which are approaching these values – to within a factor of a few. Consequently, we take this into account when interpreting the asymmetry value.

2.7.4 Sersic Parameters

The range of light-profile shapes of galaxies are inadequately described simply by limiting cases of $r^{1/4}$ -law or exponential light distributions, or some combination thereof. However, the light distribution can be well represented for almost all galaxies by a more general $r^{1/n}$ parameterization.

The Sèrsic model (1963, 1968) describes the intensity profile of a galaxy as:

$$I(r) = I_e \exp[-b_n((r/r_e)^{1/n} - 1)]. \quad (2.6)$$

In this equation, I_e is the intensity of the galaxy at r_e and r_e is the effective radius.⁶ The value of b_n is dependent on n and can be calculated from $\Gamma(2n) = 2\gamma(2n, b_n)$, where $\gamma(2n, b_n)$ is the incomplete gamma function (Graham & Driver 2005). After calculating the curve of growth for the galaxies, we fit a Sèrsic profile to the light distribution and solve for n by setting $r_e = r_{0.5}$.

2.7.5 Local Density: the Σ_{10} Parameter

Following the definition of Dressler (1980), we calculate a local density based on the distance, R_{10} , to the tenth nearest neighbor:

$$\Sigma_{10} = \frac{10}{\pi R_{10}^2}. \quad (2.7)$$

We use our photometric redshifts to limit contamination, and strictly define Σ_{10} to include galaxies with $M_B < -18.5$. For any individual galaxy, our value of Σ_{10} is likely to have significant errors due to photometric redshifts inability to isolate small-scale structure along the line of sight (Cooper et al. 2005). However, the value of Σ_{10} is more accurate for cluster sources because of the smaller amount of contamination and provides a good estimate for comparison between different environments. Σ_{10} for sources near the edge of our fields will be overestimated due to incomplete spatial coverage.

2.7.6 Rest-Frame Properties

Absolute magnitudes, radii, rest-frame surface-brightness and colors were calculated for all objects using photometric or spectroscopic redshifts. K-correction calculations adopt method 4 of Bershadsky (1995). Rest-frame colors are estimated from the aperture photometry by fitting a large sample of model SEDs (Bruzual & Charlot 2003) and interpolating over the best-fitting models. Half-light radii were measured in the band closest to rest-frame B, and corrected for PSF effects by quadrature subtraction of the stellar half-light radius following Phillips et al. (1997). Rest frame surface brightnesses in the HST and WIYN images were calculated following this formulation:

$$\bar{\mu}_e = m_b + 5\log_{10}(r_{0.5}) + 2.5\log_{10}(2\pi) - 10\log_{10}(1+z) \quad (2.8)$$

⁶ r_e is equivalent to $r_{0.5}$.

The measured surface brightness in the WIYN images were corrected for seeing using measurements from the overlapping regions with the HST data. WIYN-based surface brightnesses have a 1.5 mag dispersion due to seeing-correction effects on the measured radii.

2.8 Results

We present some basic results that can be derived from our data set, and compared to other studies, including recent studies of some of the same clusters. We provide two classic tests: (1) the color-magnitude relationship of cluster galaxies in our fields; and (2) and the Butcher-Oemler fraction for these clusters. We also investigate the timing involved in the build-up of the red-galaxy sequence in luminosity. Recent work has suggested that the extension of a tight, red-galaxy color-magnitude sequence down to intermediate-to-low mass (i.e., intermediate-to-low luminosity) is a relatively recent phenomenon in clusters. We measure the red-galaxy luminosity function shape in our intermediate-redshift clusters, relative to nearby-cluster red-galaxy luminosity functions, and compare our results to these recent, controversial studies.

2.8.1 Cluster Color-Magnitude Relation

The well-defined red-sequence of galaxies found in rich, nearby, galaxy clusters is populated with systems that appear to be relatively quiescent in terms of star-formation. Indeed, the most luminous cluster galaxies, located at the tip of the red sequence, appear to have little star formation since $z \sim 3$ (Ellis et al. 1997, Stanford et al. 1998, Poggianti et al. 2001). The apparently ubiquitous presence of a red sequence in regions of high galaxy density has been used to identify clusters in optical surveys (e.g., most recently by Gladders & Yee 2005); many of the clusters in our sample were originally identified by the large density of red galaxies (Koo 1981; Gunn, Hoessel & Oke 1986). While the presence of a red sequence in clusters has been confirmed up to $z \sim 1.5$ (Stanford et al. 1997), the extent of the red sequence in luminosity has been limited by the depth of data available. In this section, we present the rest-frame color magnitude relationship for each of our fields derived from the WIYN data and compare it to measurements from the literature.

The rest-frame B-V vs M_B color-magnitude diagram (Figure 2.22) for each of the clusters within a projected $R = 1$ Mpc displays the strong red sequence observed in rich clusters in most of

our fields. Our choice of B-V vs M_B is predicated on our desire to apply the standard Butcher-Oemler red:blue galaxy division (below). Other choices of rest-frame bands are more suitable for comparison to previous measurements. We only plot cluster galaxies identified by having $\delta z = 0.1$ about the cluster redshift, and a significant probability of being in the cluster. The rest-frame properties were calculated as described in §2.7. Most of the clusters exhibit a red sequence indicative of a high-density region, although no red sequence is observed along the Cl1325 line of sight. Recall, from Chapter 1, that Cl1325 is the one field absent a spectroscopically-confirmed rich cluster. We conclude, based on the absence of a strong, red sequence that indeed this region of possible over-density has nowhere near the densities of a rich cluster.

For each field, we fit a line to the red sequence through an iterative process of requiring galaxies to have colors with 0.2 mags of the red sequence. The measured slope for the sample only including galaxies with spectroscopic redshifts is not significantly different for any of the fields with observed red sequences (i.e., excluding the Cl1325 field).

Comparisons between the clusters reveal differences in their red sequences. In particular, while both Cl0016 and MS0451 have strong red sequences, the Cl0016 red sequence is redder than that in the MS0451 field; neither red sequence is well-fit by the other's red sequence. The differences are exhibited in the *apparent* colors of the sources as well, so the offset is not a by-product of the rest-frame calculations (these two clusters are at comparable redshift). There are also trends with redshift. The high-redshift cluster red-sequences are all bluer than the low redshift ones. However, Cl1322 and Cl1604 sequences are significantly bluer than MS1054, which is at an intermediate redshift. Color-magnitude relationships derived from the ACS field of view for MS1054 and Cl1604 show qualitatively-similar trends (Andreon 2006, Homeier et al. 2006). These results indicate that variations in the red sequence normalization in color depend on more than redshift.

While calculating the rest-frame colors, we fit model stellar populations to each of the cluster galaxies. Although the degeneracy between age, metallicity and reddening make accurate ages nearly impossible, we can qualitatively compare the relative ages of the populations between the two clusters if we assume the galaxies have similar extinctions and metallicities. In all of the clusters, the bright galaxies ($M_B < -19$) are well fit by single-burst populations that have been passively evolving

since $z > 3$. The galaxies in MS0451 appear to be slightly younger than the galaxies in Cl0016 by approximately 10%. The galaxies in MS1054 at $z = 0.83$ have the same formation age as galaxies in Cl0016, but the galaxies in the two other high redshift, low mass clusters appear to be much younger.

Overall, a trend for higher formation age for more massive clusters is observed in our data. Akin to “downsizing,” this trend between formation age and mass has been observed in other samples (Cowie et al. 1996, Kuntschner et al. 2002, Bell et al. 2003, McIntosh et al. 2005, Tanaka et al. 2005, Thomas et al. 2005). However, the observed difference between the color-magnitude relationship for Cl0016 and MS0451, which is seen even in the apparent magnitudes, is in conflict with this result as MS0451 is the more massive cluster by every indication (velocity dispersion, X-ray luminosity and temperature, lensing estimate) but richness (Clowe et al. 2000). Improved age estimates from spectroscopic indices are required to verify this result, but one possible explanation is that the formation time is set by the total bound mass of a system. Cl0016 is known to be part of a supercluster complex (Connolly et al. 1996), whereas extended structure around MS0451 has not yet been seen. The larger structure of Cl0016 could have caused the initial collapse to occur at very early times, and although we observed it as a less massive structure than MS0451 at $z \sim 0.55$, it could be a more massive cluster once the entire system fully virializes.

2.8.2 Cluster Blue Fraction

The earliest indications of an evolving cluster population were the measurement of the fraction of blue cluster-galaxies by Butcher & Oemler (1978, 1984). The increasing blue fraction seen in clusters has been confirmed by a number of studies (Couch & Sharples 1987, Rakos & Schombert 1995, Ellingson et al. 2001, de Propris et al. 2003, Goto et al. 2003, Tran et al. 2005), although different measurement techniques, definitions of blue fractions, and cosmic variance have led to conflicting results (Koo 1981; Andreon & Ettorii 1999, Andreon, Lobo, & Iovino 2004). We explore the blue fraction in our clusters and compare with several different measurements, noting that our measurements, like most in the literature, suffer from a variety of biases, humorously, but provocatively summarized by Koo (1987).

The blue fraction, f_b , is defined in a similar manner as BO84. The fraction is the ratio of blue cluster galaxies to total galaxies within a set radius that are brighter than $M_B < -19.5$. Blue

galaxies are described as all galaxies 0.2 mags bluer than the ridge line of the red sequence, which was determined above, and are indicated by a blue line in Figure 2.22. For each cluster, we plot the fraction within a projected radius of $R = 0.5$ Mpc – close to the original definition in BO84. Again, cluster objects are identified by having redshifts within $\delta z = 0.1$ of the cluster redshift and a high probability of being a cluster member. No field sample is statistically subtracted from our data.

Field-subtraction will not significantly change our results *if* we adopt the mean number of field objects as estimated from simulations from the field luminosity function at these redshifts: The number of identified cluster objects is much larger than the comparable number of field objects estimated under this assumption. However, our values for the blue fraction are likely to be overestimations ranging from 5% for the rich clusters at $z \sim 0.55$ to 20% for the poorer high redshift clusters, such as Cl1322 and Cl1604. This has to do with the fact that the photometric redshifts for blue galaxies have larger random errors than for red galaxies. As such, if the high-density cores of rich clusters, dominated by the red cluster sequence, are embedded in low-to-medium density sheets or filaments filled predominantly with blue galaxies (e.g., Koo’s Sicilian Pizza model-à-Erice), our blue-fraction could be a significant over-estimate of what truly lies within the cluster. Conversely, if we were to estimate the “field fraction” in adjacent regions to our cluster centers, the vagaries of large-scale structure could conspire (in any individual case) to yield a field correction that is even too high. We return to this possibility below.

In Figure 2.23 we plot the blue fraction, f_b , for each cluster. In addition, we also plot data from the literature, calculated within similar cluster-centric radii. We do observe a “Butcher & Oemler effect” for our clusters, with the highest redshift clusters having the largest fraction of blue galaxies.⁷ For each cluster, we list the blue fraction measured within three cluster-centric radii, along with measurements from the literature in Table 2.4. For most clusters, the measurement of the blue fraction agrees well with previous measurements despite different techniques used to calculate the blue fraction.

Cl0016 was one of the first clusters discovered to conflict with the BO effect (Koo 1981) and is often cited as an example of an “anti-BO” cluster. However, this may be due to contamination of the

⁷It should be noted that our highest redshift clusters are also our lowest-mass clusters, and hence the Sicilian Pizza-model bias may be particularly pronounced here.

field sample used to statistically subtract from the cluster sample, due to large-scale structure. The “field” in the original work for Cl0016 was offset from the cluster center by 9’ to the north. Examining the distributions of large scale structure of Cl0016 from Tanaka et al. (2005) indicates that this region contains several groups at the redshift of the cluster. Recent measurements of the blue fraction from either spectroscopic redshifts (Ellingson et al. 2001) or using “improved” field-subtraction (de Propris et al. 2003) reveal a much smaller deficit when compared to previous measurements. However, we note that spectroscopic definitions of the BO-effect are not the same as the original photometric BO-effect (Koo’s “moving-target” effect). It is also the case that some of the more recent measurements of the cluster blue-fraction, supposedly utilizing “improved” field subtraction, find negative values for f_b for some clusters (see Table 2.4). This is a statistical probability, but an un-physical result; it indicates that the measurement of f_b , as found in the extant literature, remains problematic.

We note the blue-galaxy fraction for any cluster is *smallest* when measured within the smallest projected radius. This is consistent with expectations of the morphology-density relationship, which we pursue in later Chapters. The result also indicates a more fruitful avenue of measurement is a differential measurement of the blue-galaxy fraction as a function of radius and/or projected surface-density. In clusters at low and high redshift, the early type galaxies have less extended distributions as compared to the late types at both low (Biviano et al. 1997, Conselice et al. 2001) and high redshifts (Crawford et al. 2006), and so the change with aperture size for the blue fraction can be interpreted by the rapid decrease in the red population with cluster radius since the blue population is only slowly decreasing with radius. Due to the different distributions in both space and velocity for the blue and red populations, the BO effect has often been attributed to the infall of field galaxies (Balogh et al. 2000, Tran et al. 2005), which the spatial distribution of galaxies supports. Further interpretations of the distribution of blue galaxies is saved for the remainder of this thesis.

2.8.3 Red Cluster Luminosity Functions

Several authors (de Lucia et al. 2004, Goto et al. 2005, Tanaka et al. 2005) have recently reported a deficit of faint, red-sequence galaxies in intermediate redshift clusters. Typical measurements are couched in terms of dwarf-to-giant ratios (following different definitions) and referenced to local-cluster measurements. These comparisons reveal an paucity of “dwarf,” red-sequence galax-

ies at intermediate redshift. It should be noted their definition for “dwarf galaxy” only extends to their magnitude limit of around $M_B \sim -18.5$; luminous galaxies are defined to be brighter than $M_B \sim -19.5$. A more canonical definition of “dwarf galaxy” would be for luminosities at or below $0.01 L^*$, or roughly $M_B \sim -15.5$. Regardless, Andreon (2006) do not observe a deficit of red, cluster galaxies when comparing MS1054 with the Coma cluster, down to comparable luminosity limits as the above studies. In particular, the luminosity function (LF) of the red sequence showed no meaningful difference from the Coma cluster at faint magnitudes. The depth of our WIYN data is comparable to these other studies, and allows an independent assessment of the faint-end of the red-galaxy cluster luminosity function.

Using the rest-frame B magnitudes and selecting cluster objects using photometric redshifts as before, we calculate the red-sequence, B-band luminosity function for all cluster fields. Red galaxies are defined as galaxies with $\Delta(B - V)_0 < 0.2$, where $\Delta(B - V)_0$ is the difference between the ridge line of the color-magnitude relationship and the object’s color. In Figure 2.24, we plot the luminosity function for each cluster within $R = 1Mpc$. We have not corrected the data for field contamination and have not normalized the data for area or volume.

We compare the shape of the observed LF with previously measured LFs for local and intermediate redshift clusters. All of the LFs are parameterized by Schechter functions with values listed in Table 2.5. For the local populations, we use the B-band luminosity function from Tanaka et al. (2005) for red galaxies based on the SDSS data. We apply a small evolutionary correction to the cluster LF to account for the color evolution for a passively evolving stellar population (with formation ages derived in §8.1) between $z = 0$ and the redshift of the cluster. The cluster LF is added, with a normalization left as a free model parameter, to the field LF of red galaxies at the redshift of each cluster. The field LF is normalized for the appropriate volume sampled by our cluster-membership selection process. We use the field LF from Faber et al. (2005). Hence, the only free parameter is the normalization of the cluster LF. This parameter is set by requiring the observed LF and model LF to match over the magnitude range where we are complete for detection of red galaxies. For each cluster we apply the R-band incompleteness as a function of size to the total model LF. The galaxy size (important here for the size-dependence of the completeness correction) is predicted from the

local magnitude-size relationship for red galaxies (Shen et al. 2003). We also account for the difference between the apparent R-band magnitude of an object and the absolute B-band magnitude by applying a k-correction based on a model SED of a single-burst stellar population (again, with an age constrained by the modeling in §8.1). We account for the slope in the color magnitude relationship by selecting three different models that best match the SEDs of objects at $M_B = -21, -19,$ and -17 . We carry out this process for each cluster. For MS0451 and Cl0016, we repeat the process using the cluster red-sequence LF measured for Cl0016 by Tanaka et al. (2005). For MS1054, we carry out a similar analysis using cluster red-sequence LFs measured for MS1054 itself (Andreon 2006), and for another rich cluster at a similar redshift (RXJ0153 at $z=0.83$; Tanaka et al. 2005).

To a magnitude of $M_B = -17.5$, the $z \sim 0.55$ clusters show little evidence of any deficit. The difference between the local LF with $\alpha = -0.9$ and the measured LF for Cl0016 by Tanaka et al. with $\alpha = -0.64$ is indistinguishable at our completeness limits for both clusters (although we only show the fit to the Cl0016 cluster), and we find no deficit to $M_B = -18.5$ where we are complete. As such, any recent additions to the cluster must not change the shape of the red sequence if these clusters are going to be similar to local galaxy clusters.

For the $z \sim 0.75$ fields, we find no evidence for a cluster in the Cl1325 field as it is well fit by the field LF alone, but the Cl1322 cluster is well fit by the local galaxy cluster LF to $M_B = -18.5$ before our incompleteness makes any further measurement impossible. To the limit of our data in Cl1604, the LF is well fit by the local cluster luminosity function. However, we do note that the bright end of the LF in Cl1604 appears to have an excess; over all, the red-sequence in this cluster appears to be unusual. Relative to the other clusters in our sample, the red sequences in Cl1322 and Cl1604 are not very rich. This observation is in agreement with the lower velocity dispersions and cluster masses for these samples.

The MS1054 cluster is best fit by the Tanaka et al. (2005) LF with a faint-end slope of $\alpha = -0.64$ for RXJ0153, but the difference is negligible compared to the other LFs. Andreon (2006) found no deficit to $M_B = -17.5$ after a statistical field subtraction from the HST ACS data of the field, while Goto et al. (2005) did find a deficit from examining the same data but relying only on the spectroscopic sample. Improved analysis of our photometric redshifts by including publicly

available NIR data along with the narrow-band data may further refine the identification of cluster objects, but observations to fainter magnitudes are required to properly constrain the faint end of the luminosity function in MS1054.

2.9 Summary

We have observed six intermediate redshift galaxy clusters as part of the WIYN Long Term Variability survey. These clusters were selected as well-studied systems with public data available over a wide range of wavelengths and from a number of different facilities. New observations were obtained from the WIYN 3.5m telescope to measure variability of sources in these fields over a 5-7 year period in UBRI bands. As part of this thesis, we have added Gunn z and narrow-band observations sampling rest-frame [OII] λ 3727 at the clusters' redshifts. These additional observations provide measurements of rest-frame properties to $z \sim 1.3$, increase the reliability of the photometric redshifts, and provide a method for identifying and measuring the SFR from emission-line cluster objects.

In addition to the WIYN 3.5m observations, the analysis presented here is supplemented from data two other sources. WIYN 0.9m observations were attempted in order to provide calibrate photometry for stellar sources in our fields. HST ACS and WFPC2 observations provide morphology for many of our sources, which are poorly resolved in the ground based images despite excellent seeing at the WIYN 3.5m.

We have detailed the data reduction and analysis for our data set. Non-standard reductions techniques were applied to the WIYN Mini-Mosaic CCD data to produce high-quality, photometrically calibrated images. The data were mosaiced in order to produce deep images of each cluster in each band. Calibration of the data was accomplished through comparisons within our own data set (0.9m observations, standards taken during observing runs on WIYN), comparisons to photometry published in the literature, and by matching the photometry of observed stars with expected stellar colors. We have outlined the detection process for our images and provided a thorough analysis of the limitations of our data set.

We have devised a new scheme that produces accurate photometry for galaxies of all light-profile shapes and sizes. We accomplish this by computing an aperture size based on an iterative-

estimate of the metric size (formulated in terms of the Petrosian index η) and the shape of the light profile shape (formulated in terms of a concentration index, C_{2080}). Compared to other techniques, the random errors associated with this method are relatively large at low signal-to-noise (defined for the integrated light within the half-light radius) for objects with large concentration values. For this reason, fixed aperture magnitudes or Petrosian magnitudes are used for computing colors, photometric redshifts, or SED fits. For each source, we calculate the photometric redshift based on a hybrid of the template and training-set method. We have combined the two techniques to minimize systematic and random errors in the redshift measurement. In addition, we also highlight the different photometric parameters we measure for each galaxy such as size, concentration, asymmetry, and local density.

Finally, we highlight some of the basic measurements that are possible given the high quality of our data and analysis. Most of the fields display the strong red sequence typically seen in rich nearby clusters. On average, the luminous red galaxies appear to be a single burst population that has been passively evolving since $z < 2.5$, but differences exist between clusters even at a given epoch. The clusters appear to display similar trends in blue fraction with redshift as the original BO84 study, albeit extending to higher redshift. Our measured cluster blue-galaxy fractions fall within the wide range of existing, published values, although outstanding issues remain (with all measurements) concerning measurement biases.

The luminosity function for the red sequence in each cluster shows little to no deficit to $M_B = -18.5$. In other words, the LF shape is indistinguishable from a local-cluster red-galaxy LF. Of course, we can not rule out any deficit below this magnitude limit – the magnitude-limit of our data. The normalization of red-galaxy cluster LF is lower for the low-mass clusters than for the high mass clusters, as expected. No systematic differences exist between the shape of the cluster LF and other cluster properties. These clusters, observed at intermediate redshifts corresponding to look-back times of roughly 5-8 Gyr, are still expected to gain a significant amount of mass between the observed epoch and today (Eke, Navarro, & Frenk 1998). Our result implies the addition of galaxies must occur in such a manner to leave the *shape* of the red-galaxy luminosity function unchanged down to $M_B = -18.5$.

We have only begun to scratch the surface of the possible analysis capable with the wealth of data for these clusters. Further investigation of the blue cluster populations is pursued in the following chapters, but a significant amount of work can still be done with the total cluster populations including improved analysis of the stellar populations and morphology. More importantly, we have not explored the variability data available with our data set, which we hope will provide extensive information about the stellar populations through supernovae rates and the identification of cluster and field AGN.

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Table 2.1. WLTV Mosaics For Fields with Narrow-Band Imaging

Band	λ (\AA)	FWHM (\AA)	Exp. Time (sec)	Seeing (arcsec)	Lim Mag ^a	Cal. Method ^b
MS0451						
U	3673	450	14400	0.99	24.73	
B	4393	980	16800	0.94	26.08	L9
KP1512	5287	250	5400	0.75	24.98	MW
O1	5736	85	13200	0.74	24.71	MW
R	6561	1520	9000	0.73	25.23	L9
I	8206	1730	11400	0.82	23.95	HST
z	9100	1193	14400	1.00	23.04	HST
Cl0016						
U	3673	450	19800	0.97	24.83	
B	4393	980	10800	0.95	25.86	L9
KP1512	5287	250	10800	0.79	25.26	MW
O1	5736	85	9600	0.64	24.67	MW
O2	5767	85	18000	0.81	24.55	MW
R	6561	1520	7800	0.68	25.63	L9
I	8206	1730	9000	0.62	24.52	HST
z	9100	1193	13200	0.77	23.05	HST
Cl1325						
U	3673	450	21600	0.94	24.39	L9, S
B	4393	980	9600	0.82	25.87	W9, L9, S
R	6561	1520	10800	0.67	25.58	L9, S
O3	6417	85	10800	1.05	23.71	MW
O4	6529	83	6600	1.13	23.46	MW
I	8206	1730	9000	0.65	24.45	L9, S
z	9100	1193	10800	0.60	23.05	S

Table 2.1—Continued

Band	λ (\AA)	FWHM (\AA)	Exp. Time (sec)	Seeing (arcsec)	Lim Mag ^a	Cal. Method ^b
C11322						
U	3673	450	16800	1.13	24.39	L9, S
B	4393	980	9000	0.92	25.61	W9, L9, S
R	6561	1520	12600	0.73	25.58	L9,S, HST
O3	6417	85	6600	1.14	23.63	MW
O4	6529	83	14400	1.00	23.95	MW
I	8206	1730	12600	0.69	24.45	L9,S,HST
z	9100	1193	10800	0.86	23.05	S
MS1054						
U	3673	450	21900	0.87	25.29	
B	4393	980	11400	0.90	25.83	L9, LIT
R	6561	1520	10200	0.81	25.48	HST, LIT
O5	6824	93	21600	0.83	24.22	MW
O6	7079	100	6000	0.88	23.58	MW
I	8206	1730	7200	0.88	23.79	L9, HST, LIT
z	9100	1193	13200	0.86	23.40	HST
C11604						
U	3673	450	21900	0.87	25.29	S
B	4393	980	11400	0.90	25.83	S
R	6561	1520	10200	0.81	25.48	W9, S,HST
O5	6824	93	21600	0.83	24.22	MW
O6	7079	100	6000	0.88	23.58	MW
I	8206	1730	7200	0.88	23.79	W9, S,HST
z	9100	1193	13200	0.86	23.40	S

^aThe limiting magnitude is reported for the 50% completeness limit of a stellar object.

^bThe calibration method used to calculate the zeropoint. The abbreviations stand for: LW (Landolt (1992) standards taken at WIYN 3.5m), L9 (tertiary standards made from Landolt standards observed at WIYN 0.9m), MW (Massey et al. 1998 spectrophotometric standards observed at the WIYN 3.5m), HST (ACS images in the field in the corresponding band), S (Sloan Digital Sky Survey data available), and LIT (literature sources used). If no abbreviation is listed, the zeropoint was calculated from matching the Gunn-Stryker stellar locus.

Table 2.2. HST Archival Observations

Cluster	RA (J2000)	DEC (J2000)	Camera	Filter	Exp. Time sec
MS0451	04:54:10.9	-03:01:07.1	ACS	F775W	2440
MS0451	04:54:10.9	-03:01:07.1	ACS	F850LP	2560
MS0451	04:54:11.46	-03:00:57.2	ACS	F555W	4410
MS0451	04:54:13.71	-03:00:23.0	WFPC2	F702W	10400
CL0016	00:18:32.8	16:26:07.0	ACS	F775W	2440
CL0016	00:18:32.8	16:26:07.0	ACS	F850LP	2540
CL0016	00:18:33.25	16:25:42.3	WFPC2	F555W	12600
CL0016	00:18:45.08	16:27:09.9	WFPC2	F814W	4600
CL0016	00:18:45.08	16:27:09.9	WFPC2	F555W	4600
CL0016	00:18:21.38	16:25:02.6	WFPC2	F814W	4600
CL0016	00:18:21.38	16:25:02.6	WFPC2	F555W	4600
CL0016	00:18:32.78	16:22:32.6	WFPC2	F814W	4600
CL0016	00:18:32.78	16:22:32.6	WFPC2	F555W	4600
CL0016	00:18:54.68	16:25:39.2	WFPC2	F814W	10800
CL0016	00:18:54.68	16:25:39.2	WFPC2	F555W	10800
CL0016	00:18:27.63	16:21:20.4	WFPC2	F450W	8400
CL0016	00:18:27.63	16:21:20.4	WFPC2	F814W	4700
Cl1325	13:25:17.72	30:09:44.0	WFPC2	F814W	18800
Cl1322	13:24:50.13	30:11:18.5	WFPC2	F606W	16000
Cl1322	13:24:50.13	30:11:18.5	WFPC2	F814W	32000

Table 2.2—Continued

Cluster	RA (J2000)	DEC (J2000)	Camera	Filter	Exp. Time sec
MS1054	10:56:50.76	-03:37:14.1	ACS	F606W	2025
MS1054	10:56:50.76	-03:37:14.1	ACS	F775W	4340
MS1054	10:56:50.76	-03:37:14.1	ACS	F850LP	4440
MS1054	10:56:57.80	-03:35:13.1	ACS	F606W	2025
MS1054	10:56:57.80	-03:35:13.1	ACS	F775W	4340
MS1054	10:56:57.80	-03:35:13.1	ACS	F850LP	4440
MS1054	10:57:05.17	-03:36:47.2	ACS	F606W	2025
MS1054	10:57:05.17	-03:36:47.2	ACS	F775W	4340
MS1054	10:57:05.17	-03:36:47.2	ACS	F850LP	4440
MS1054	10:56:59.12	-03:38:58.5	ACS	F606W	2025
MS1054	10:56:59.12	-03:38:58.5	ACS	F775W	4340
MS1054	10:56:59.12	-03:38:58.5	ACS	F850LP	4440
MS1054	10:57:20.61	-03:35:27.5	ACS	F606W	1890
MS1054	10:57:20.61	-03:35:27.5	ACS	F814W	1980
MS1054	10:57:09.33	-03:33:26.4	ACS	F606W	1890
MS1054	10:57:09.33	-03:33:26.4	ACS	F814W	1980
MS1054	10:57:19.85	-03:31:23.0	ACS	F606W	1890
MS1054	10:57:19.85	-03:31:23.0	ACS	F814W	1980
MS1054	10:57:16.23	-03:38:48.4	ACS	F606W	1890
MS1054	10:57:16.23	-03:38:48.4	ACS	F814W	1980
MS1054	10:56:53.85	-03:31:58.1	ACS	F606W	1890
MS1054	10:56:53.85	-03:31:58.1	ACS	F814W	1980
MS1054	10:56:44.10	-03:34:01.5	ACS	F606W	1890
MS1054	10:56:44.10	-03:34:01.5	ACS	F814W	1980
MS1054	10:56:38.21	-03:36:58.3	ACS	F606W	1890
MS1054	10:56:38.21	-03:36:58.3	ACS	F814W	1980
MS1054	10:56:44.46	-03:40:05.2	ACS	F606W	1890
MS1054	10:56:44.46	-03:40:05.2	ACS	F814W	1980
Cl1604	16:04:24.77	43:04:52.0	ACS	F606W	4840
Cl1604	16:04:24.77	43:04:52.0	ACS	F814W	4840
Cl1604	16:04:23.88	43:00:11.6	WFPC2	F814W	19200

Table 2.3. Concentration-based Photometric Corrections^a

n	C_{2080}	C_{2080}^{Pet}	C_{5090}	$\epsilon(98\%)$	$\epsilon(99\%)$	F_p/F_{tot}
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
0.5	2.15	2.14	1.30	1.21	1.32	0.999
0.75	2.49	2.49	1.58	1.40	1.58	0.998
1	2.80	2.78	1.83	1.61	1.83	0.994
1.5	3.34	3.26	2.24	2.13	2.52	0.974
2	3.80	3.63	2.60	2.79	3.41	0.947
4	5.27	4.50	3.72	7.66	10.42	0.828
6	6.41	4.99	4.58	18.78	27.01	0.722
8	7.33	5.31	5.24	39.25	55.53	0.63

^aConcentration indexes are defined as $C_{xy} = -5\log(r_x/r_y)$

where r_x is the radius where the flux is x percent of the total flux

^b(1) n is defined in the Sèrsic equation. A Gaussian, exponential, and $r^{1/4}$ profile are given by $n = 0.5, 1$, and 4 . (2) Concentration index calculated from the total magnitude. (3) C_{2080}^{Pet} calculated where the “total” flux is given by the Petrosian magnitude. (4) C_{5090} is calculated from the total magnitude but is similar to the concentration index used by the SDSS. (5) $\epsilon(98\%)$ is the value used in our calculations of the total flux. It represents the factor needed to multiply r_p by in order to measure 98% of the flux. (6) $\epsilon(99\%)$ is the factor required to multiply r_p by in order to measure 99% of the flux. (7) Fraction of total flux measured within $2r_p$.

Table 2.4. Blue fraction for WLTV clusters

Cluster	z	f_b 0.5 Mpc	f_b 0.5 R_{200}	f_b 1.5 Mpc	lit.
MS0451	0.53	0.16 ± 0.04	0.33 ± 0.03	0.33 ± 0.04	$0.31^d, 0.197^c$
Cl0016	0.55	0.30 ± 0.05	0.37 ± 0.04	0.35 ± 0.04	$0.02^a, 0.37^b, 0.15^c, 0.16^d$
Cl1325	0.72	0.70 ± 0.28	0.80 ± 0.11	0.70 ± 0.20	
Cl1322	0.75	0.58 ± 0.15	0.61 ± 0.08	0.60 ± 0.12	$0.72^b, -0.2^d$
MS1054	0.83	0.32 ± 0.08	0.51 ± 0.06	0.41 ± 0.06	0.013^d
Cl1604	0.90	0.55 ± 0.17	0.57 ± 0.07	0.46 ± 0.11	$0.80^b, -0.31^d$

^aBlue fraction within $R \sim 0.5$ Mpc from Butcher & Oemler 1984

^bBlue fraction within $R \sim 0.5$ Mpc from Rakos & Schombert 1995

^cBlue fraction within $0.5R_{200}$ from Ellingson et al. 2001

^dBlue fraction within $R = 0.5$ Mpc from de Propris et al. 2003

Table 2.5. Red Luminosity Functions for Clusters and the Field

Environment	z	M_b^* ^a	α	Φ^* ^b Mpc^3	ref.
Field	0.5	-20.83	-0.5	1.771×10^{-3}	Faber et al. (2005)
Field	0.7	-21.05	-0.5	1.763×10^{-3}	Faber et al. (2005)
Field	0.9	-21.02	-0.5	1.317×10^{-3}	Faber et al. (2005)
Cluster	0.00	-20.27	-0.90	...	Tanaka et al. 2005
Cl0016	0.55	-20.15	-0.64	...	Tanaka et al. 2005
RXJ0153	0.83	-20.99	-0.69	...	Tanaka et al. 2005
MS1054	0.83	-21.00	-0.80	...	Andreon 2006

^aValues from Tanaka et al (2005) were convert to B-band from V-band, but no other corretions have been applied to the reported M_B^* .

^bValues of Φ^* are set for each cluster by requiring the bright end of the model LF function to match the observed LF.

Fig. 2.1.— Transmission curves for the broad- and narrow-band filters used in this survey. The transmission functions for the filters have been convolved with the response function of the CCD and the transmission of the atmosphere, and are normalized to unity for 100% transmission.

Fig. 2.2.— Color-color diagram for stellar objects in our fields. Symbols for each field are provided in the key. The solid line is the stellar locus calculated from the Gunn & Stryker atlas (1982) for dwarfs; the dashed curve gives the same relation for giants. The calibration of the U-band data for most fields involved matching the stellar locus in this plane.

Fig. 2.3.— Same as Figure 2.2 except for $B-R$ vs $R-I$. These bands were calibrated by independent methods for all fields, as described in the text.

Fig. 2.4.— Same as Figure 2.2 except for $R-I$ vs $I-z$. The z -band was calibrated by a mix of standard observations at the WIYN 3.5m observatory, SDSS data, and by matching the stellar locus.

Fig. 2.5.— Completeness for unresolved objects in each band for each field. The bands are represented by different lines: U (blue dotted), B (cyan short dashed), R (red solid), I (green long dashed), and z (black dot-dashed). Each field is labeled in the plot.

Fig. 2.6.— Completeness in the R-band for each field for objects of different sizes. Curves are labeled for each half-light radius (arcsec). These sizes correspond roughly to the stellar PSF, and $2\times$ and $3\times$ this value.

Fig. 2.7.— Completeness estimates for different cluster populations for the apparent color-magnitude distribution (top) and apparent size-magnitude distribution (bottom) for the field of MS0451, a cluster at $z = 0.538$. All objects detected in the WIYN Mini-Mosaics images are plotted as grey open squares. The red curve represents the change in apparent color, magnitude, and size for an early type galaxy as a function of redshift, assuming $M_B = -18.5$, $r_e = 1.25$ kpc, and an elliptical SED. The blue curve represents the change in color, size, and magnitude for a galaxy that qualifies at the limits of our definition of an LCBG in surface brightness and color, also at $M_B = -18.5$. Squares indicate the location of these objects at each cluster redshift in our survey, ranging from $z = 0.5$ to $z = 0.9$ (left to right). In the top panel, the cyan lines represent the 50% (solid) and 90% (dashed) detection limits of the B-band data. In the bottom panel, the green lines represent the surface brightness levels at which we are 50% (solid) and 90% (dashed) complete. For detection, the MS0451 is complete to $M_B < -18.5$ for both early types and LCBGs, but will be missing some early types at $z = 0.90$ to the faintest magnitudes if no evolution occurs in this population.

Fig. 2.8.— Same as Figure 2.7 except for Cl0016 at $z = 0.55$. The data are complete for all cluster populations and LCBGs beyond $z = 1.0$, but only 50% complete at $z = 0.90$ for field red galaxies.

Fig. 2.9.— Same as Figure 2.7 except for Cl1325 at $z = 0.72$. The data are complete for all cluster populations and LCBGs beyond $z = 1$, but only 50% complete for field red galaxies beyond $z = 0.83$.

Fig. 2.10.— Same as Figure 2.7 except for Cl1322 at $z = 0.75$. The data are complete for all cluster populations and LCBGs beyond $z = 1.0$, but only 50% complete at $z = 0.90$ for field red galaxies.

Fig. 2.11.— Same as Figure 2.7 except for MS1054 at $z = 0.83$. The data are complete for all cluster populations and LCBGs beyond $z = 1.0$, but only 50% complete at $z = 0.90$ for field red galaxies.

Fig. 2.12.— Same as Figure 2.7 except for Cl1604 at $z = 0.90$. The data are complete for all cluster populations and LCBGs beyond $z = 1.0$, but only 50% complete at $z = 0.90$ for field red galaxies.

Fig. 2.13.— Image-concentration versus Sèrsic index n (bottom), photometry-aperture scale factor ϵ (middle), and fractional flux within r_p (top). We plot the relationship for C_{2080} and C_{5090} defined from our total magnitude (solid and dotted lines, respectively), and C_{2080} defined from the Petrosian magnitude (dashed line). The concentration index, regardless of how its measured, correlates very well with n ; the concentration index can be used to produce reliable corrections to the total magnitude from its relationship either with ϵ , the factor required to multiply r_p by to measure a total flux, or F_p/F_{tot} . The C_{2080} measured from our total magnitude provides a more reliable correction than C_{2080} measured from the Petrosian magnitude due to the slower rate of change with the different corrections at large concentration. Different trade-offs exist between the C_{2080} and C_{5090} indexes as the former is more susceptible to sampling errors while the later performs more poorly at lower S/N.

Fig. 2.14.— Simulated systematic and random errors for different photometric techniques as a function of light-profile shape and signal-to-noise (S/N). Each of the colored lines represents the simulated errors for objects with $r_{0.5} = 5$ pixels, a S/N at the half-light radii given in the panel, and a range of light profiles with Sèrsic index between $0.5 < n < 6$. The different photometric techniques are Petrosian magnitudes (black line), Kron magnitudes (blue line), corrected Petrosian magnitudes as described by Graham et al. (2005, green line), and total magnitudes as described in the text (red line). Selected profiles with $n = 0.5$, 1, and 4 are highlighted (triangle, box, and circle, respectively). In addition, we also plot the error measured by two aperture magnitudes as described in the text. The large aperture is the grey dashed line while the small aperture is the grey dotted line. The aperture magnitudes are for galaxies with sizes different from the models. The systematic error, Δm , is such that positive values are underestimations of the total flux. The corrected magnitude provide profile-independent magnitudes, but have larger random errors than either fixed aperture magnitudes or Petrosian magnitudes.

Fig. 2.15.— Illustration of hybrid photometric-redshift training process. The training shifts the initial model templates to match the observed color distribution of real galaxies to correct for calibration errors or template incompleteness. The grey color distribution is the original template colors, the red squares are the transformed template, and the black triangles are the full training set. We only show the color distribution up to $z = 1.5$ for clarity.

Fig. 2.16.— Same as Figure 2.15 except showing the two colors as a function of redshift.

Fig. 2.17.— Comparison between spectroscopic and photometric redshifts for the full sample of galaxies with spectroscopic redshifts in our survey fields. Photometric redshifts are produced using the full complement of bands available and by using our hybrid photometric redshift technique. Symbols for each cluster are the same as in Figure 2.2. The technique produces very accurate photometric redshifts with relatively small dispersion.

Fig. 2.18.— Histogram of difference between photometric and spectroscopic redshifts. The dispersion for the sample is $\sigma_z = 0.05$ after excluding a small fraction (10%) in the non-Gaussian wings of the distribution.

Fig. 2.19.— Random error distribution for our photometric redshifts as a function of signal-to-noise using just broad-band photometry (open symbols) and a combination of broad- and narrow-bands (filled symbols). The signal to noise is calculated at the half-light radii in the R-band images. Galaxies in the MS0451 field are represented by squares; Cl0016, circles; Cl1322, diamonds; MS1054, pentagons; and Cl1604, triangles. Curves represent simulations of the random redshift errors (1σ) caused by random photometric errors for two spectra representing the red and blue populations. In the simulations, the photometric errors are set to be constant across different bands. While this does not reflect the true error distribution of our data, it is a suitable approximation. Some of the variation seen at large S/N between the model predictions and the real data may be due to systematic differences between our final template database and the real SED distributions of galaxies, despite the efforts of the training process. However, errors do improve at all S/N with the addition of more (particularly narrow) bands.

Fig. 2.20.— Probability of cluster membership as a function of photometric redshift for the MS0451 cluster at $z = 0.538$. The grey points represent the measurement of photometric-redshift and $P(z)$ for all sources with $R < 24$, while the red squares are objects with spectroscopic redshifts, placed at the location of their spectroscopic redshifts. The vertical solid line represents the cluster redshift, while the two dashed lines represent offsets of ± 0.1 from this value. The horizontal line at $P(z) = 0.1$ represents the $P(z)$ cut-off for cluster membership. A cluster must be above the horizontal line and within the dashed lines to be considered a cluster member.

Fig. 2.21.— Image-concentration versus radius for data in the F775W-band HST/ACS image of MS0451. The two lines represent simulations of the measured concentration index as a function of size for two different light profiles (Sèrsic index $n = 1, 3.8$). As galaxies become smaller, their image-concentration becomes progressively smaller, particularly for objects with intrinsically more concentrated light-profiles. Proper interpretation of the measured concentration index requires an assessment of the sampling of the data relative to the size of the object. Note that the ACS pixel size is roughly 0.049 arcsec, near the lower terminus of the measured data points.

Fig. 2.22.— Rest-frame color magnitude relationship for each cluster within $R=1$ Mpc of the cluster center. The calculation of the rest-frame properties are discussed in the text. For each cluster, the best fit line to the cluster red sequence is plotted as a solid black line. The dotted blue line represents the division between red and blue galaxies based on the definition from BO84. In the CI1325 field, no significant red sequence is observed, and so the best fit to the red sequence from CI1322 field is plotted.

Fig. 2.23.— Blue fraction for each of our clusters within $R=0.5$ Mpc of the cluster center. In addition to our clusters (filled squares), we plot several blue fractions measured from the literature: BO84 (open circles), Rakos & Schombert (1995, open squares), and de Propris et al. (2003, dashed line). We plot the best-fit line to the BO84 data and extend it to $z = 1$ in order to compare to our data

Fig. 2.24.— Red-sequence cluster luminosity-functions for each of our clusters-fields, as measured within a projected radius of $R=1$ Mpc of the nominal cluster center. The symbols are as in Figure 2.2. Cluster galaxies are selected via their photometric redshifts, as described in the text. In each panel, we plot the expected field-luminosity function of red galaxies from Faber et al. (2005, grey line). In addition, the local-cluster luminosity function from Tanaka et al. (2005), transformed to the redshift of Cl0016, Cl1322, MS1054, and Cl1604 are plotted as a solid black line. Luminosity functions measured by Tanaka et al. (2005) for Cl0016 at $z = 0.55$ and another rich cluster at $z = 0.83$ (RXJ0153, not in our sample) are plotted as blue lines in the appropriate plots. The LF for MS1054 from Andreon (2006) is plotted as a red line in the $z \sim 0.83$ panel. Dashed lines represent the model cluster LFs after convolution with our incompleteness function. There is no conclusive evidence for a deficit in the LF for any of the cluster to $M_B = -18.5$.

Chapter 3

Luminous Compact Blue Galaxies in Intermediate Redshift Galaxy Clusters: A Significant But Extreme Butcher-Oemler Population

Abstract

We identify a population of Luminous Compact Blue Galaxies (LCBGs) in six intermediate-redshift cluster fields from the WIYN Long-Term Variability Survey (WLTV): MS0451.6-0305 ($z = 0.538$), Cl 0016+1609 ($z = 0.55$), Cl 1325+3010 ($z=0.72$), Cl 1322+3027 ($z=0.755$), MS1054.3-0321 ($z=0.823$), Cl 1604+1609 ($z=0.90$). Five of these are moderate-to-rich massive clusters. LCBGs are selected via their photometric characteristics identified in WIYN and Hubble Space Telescope images. The field and cluster LCBGs display main similarities in terms of luminosity, size, surface brightness, concentration, and asymmetry; but the cluster LCBGs do display lower star formation rates than their field counterparts. We analyze their surface densities and clustering properties to find they compose a statistically significant portion (42% and 53%) of the so-called “Butcher-Oemler” galaxies in both clusters, and their spatial distributions are best characterized by a shell model. The enhancement of the projected space-density of LCBGs with $M_B < -18.5$ in the clusters relative to the field is 3-10 times higher than the BO population as a whole, but 2 times lower than the red population, except in the core where LCBGs are absent. Assuming some fading, a natural descendant would be small, low-luminosity galaxies found preferentially in today’s clusters, such as dEs. If one assumes a reasonable lifetime for the LCBG phase, LCBGs must fade below $M_B=-18.5$ to produce luminosity functions in these clusters that are comparable to cluster luminosity functions observed today.

3.1 Introduction

The number of blue, star forming galaxies increases in all environments at intermediate redshifts ($0.3 < z < 1.0$). In the field, there is a dramatic rise in the space-density of luminous ($M_B \sim -20$), compact ($R_e \sim 2\text{kpc}$), and blue ($B - V \sim 0.35$) galaxies known as LCBGs (Koo et al. 1994; Guzmán et al. 1997). These galaxies produce stars at such a tremendous rate ($1 - 40 M_\odot \text{yr}^{-1}$, Hammer et al. 2001) they provide a substantial fraction of the star formation in the universe at $0.4 < z < 1$ (Guzmán et al. 1997). In clusters, Butcher & Oemler (1978, 1984; hereafter BO) claimed the fraction of blue galaxies increases with redshift. Blue cluster galaxies have been classified as a mix of normal galaxies absent in local clusters, morphologically disturbed, and star forming galaxies (Oemler, Dressler, & Butcher 1997). Recent studies indicate star forming galaxies in intermediate redshift clusters are typically small, disk-like (de Propris et al. 2002; Lotz, Martin, & Ferguson 2003; Finn, Zaritsky, & McCarthy 2003) and falling into the cluster (Balogh, Navarro, & Morris 2001; Homeier et al. 2004; Tran et al. 2005) in groups and clumps (Kodama et al. 2002). While several studies exist for LCBGs in the field and Koo et al. (1997) have identified a handful of LCBGs in CL0024, no thorough census of LCBGs in clusters has been completed. In an initial, systematic census, Crawford et al. (2006) explored the relative frequency and density-dependence of LCBGs in two WLTV clusters: MS 0451 and Cl 1604. Here we triple the statistics of this effort, which permits us to extend the analysis of cluster-LCBGs and better assess their niche as a progenitor population.

Field LCBGs and cluster star-forming galaxies have been proposed as the progenitors of dwarf elliptical (dE) galaxies (Koo et al. 1994; Guzmán et al. 1997; Koo et al. 1997; Martin et al. 2000) or low-mass S0's (Tran et al. 2005). The line widths and physical sizes of field and cluster LCBGs are consistent with those of dwarf elliptical galaxies (or field “dEs” like NGC205). Recent bursts inferred from the stellar histories of local dwarf ellipticals (Grebel, Gallagher, & Harbeck 2004) and in nearby clusters (Poggianti et al. 2001; Conselice, Gallagher, & Wyse 2003) support a fading scenario.

However, the high masses (Phillips et al. 1997; hereafter P97), high metallicities (Kobulnicky & Zaritsky 1999), large extinctions (Hammer et al. 2001), and centrally concentrated star-bursts (Barton and van Zee 2001) seen in some LCBGs make them plausible candidates to be a burst phase

of more massive spiral galaxies. Both dE’s and more massive bulges are accreted populations in local clusters (Conselice et al. 2001; Biviano et al. 2002), but they have very different morphology-density relationships (Ferguson & Binggeli 1994). Understanding the prevalence and distribution of LCBGs in clusters should constrain their role as a progenitor population.

In this Chapter we present the photometric and image-structural properties, density, and clustering of LCBGs in the fields of six clusters between $0.5 < z < 0.9$. Five of these are moderate-to-rich clusters, while the sixth (Cl 1325) is more likely a super-position of groups between $0.4 < z < 0.7$. As such, this tertiary field is useful to explore low-to-moderate densities at redshifts complementary to the bona-fide clusters. Overall, the cluster redshifts span an epoch where the dynamical mass of field LCBGs changes rapidly (P97), and are sufficiently disparate to permit the derivation of complementary field samples using the same data. Details of the photometric data analysis (image processing, calibration, detection, photometry, and characterization of the light-profile shapes) are presented in Chapter 2. Star-formation measurements, based on rest-frame [OII] λ 3727 narrow-band imaging are presented in Chapter 4. The balance of this Chapter is organized as follows: We detail the identification of LCBGs in §3.2 and compare the number of LCBGs we would detect under previous selection descriptions. In §3.3, the number density and distribution of LCBGs is described. In §3.4, we compare the photometric properties of LCBGs to the field and other samples. We look at the enhancement of LCBGs in §3.6 and discuss the evolutionary fate of LCBGs in §3.7. Throughout this Chapter, we adopt $H_0 = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, $\Omega_{matter} = 0.3$, and $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$.

3.2 Identification of LCBGs

We define LCBGs here as “enthusiastic” star forming galaxies, by which we mean that the star-formation intensity is roughly $0.1 \text{ M}_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-2}$ within their half-light radii. Anything substantially below this enters the “normal” regime, as defined by nearby, late-type galaxies on the Hubble sequence; about 10 times higher star-formation intensities corresponds to the star-burst regime. It is straight-forward to show, using standard stellar population-synthesis models (e.g., Bruzual & Charlot), for a galaxy with the appropriately scaled constant star formation history the following conditions apply at any given age between 10^8 and 10^{10} yr: $0 < (B - V) < 0.4$ in the rest-frame, $\bar{\mu}_e(B) \sim 20.5$ also in the rest-frame, and $L_{bol} = 10^9 L_\odot$ within the half-light radius. Anything redder

or lower surface-brightness implies star-formation rates entering the “normal” regime. Accounting for the modest amounts of extinction and reddening observed in intermediate redshift field sources (Kobulnicky & Zaritsky 1999, Hoyos et al. 2004), corresponding to $E(B-V) = 0.1$, yields the following empirical selection limits: rest-frame $(B - V) < 0.5$ and $\bar{\mu}_e(B) < 21 \text{ mag arcsec}^{-2}$. The selection region for LCBGs is plotted in Figure 3.1. This region is mostly devoid of objects in local surveys (e.g., Werk et al. 2004, Garland et al. 2004) and is purposely constructed to identify actively star forming galaxies that are extreme compared to the local universe in clusters or the field. For comparison with other LCBG samples and to differentiate them from “dwarf” galaxies (at least in luminosity)¹ we also require LCBGs to have $M_B < -18.5$.

Galaxies were selected from the ground-based data set. We estimate, based on extant HST data, this selection misses $\sim 5\%$ of the bona-fide LCBGs (primarily due to the error in the size measurement), while introducing the same percentage of false classifications. We identified “cluster” galaxies in our sample – including LCBGs – as having (i) a photometric redshift within ± 0.1 of the cluster’s redshift, and (ii) a reasonable probability based on comparison to the spectroscopic sample to be at the cluster redshift based on the individual photometric error and measurements from the training set (Brunner and Lubin 2000). Cluster centers and redshifts are tabulated in Chapter 1.² Within 1 Mpc of the clusters’ centers, we find 93 candidate LCBGs (the numbers within R_{200} are given for each cluster in Figures 3.2-3.4). Eight objects are confirmed as cluster members through spectroscopic redshifts, and 61 are confirmed by having strong emission (equivalent width, W_o , greater than 10 \AA) in the “on” narrow-band image, which samples rest-frame $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$. We have 7 objects that are identified as cluster LCBGs, but have spectroscopic redshifts that place them outside of the cluster (but still within a redshift of 0.1 of the cluster), and weak $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ emission, consistent with their emission being near the edge of the narrow-band band-pass. The remaining 17 objects require spectroscopic follow-up to confirm cluster membership, but overall the reliability of the LCBG sample appears to be very good: at least 74% are confirmed to be bona-fide cluster

¹Throughout this work, we quantify giant or luminous galaxies as all objects with $M_B < -18.5$

²For Cl 1325 note there are no published spectroscopic redshifts, so we rely entirely on the cluster redshift and astrometric identification provided by Oke, Postman, Lubin (1998). Their published redshift histogram for this field shows peaks in the spectroscopic distribution with these redshifts (and numbers): 0.40 (11), 0.62 (7), 0.67 (7), 0.72 (12), 0.92 (7), 1.07 (11), 1.20 (3).

objects, and at least 82% are confirmed to be in cluster and periphery.

We select two other groups of luminous ($M_B < -18.5$) cluster galaxies in our data, red and blue, to compare to the LCBG population. We fit the color-magnitude relationship in both clusters, splitting the population according to the classic definition of the Butcher-Oemler effect (Butcher & Oemler 1978, 1984): $|\Delta(B - V)_0| > 0.2$ are “BO” galaxies, *which include the LCBG population*. The remainder are defined as the “red cluster sequence.” Blue fractions for each cluster are defined simply as the ratio of the number of BO to the number of all cluster galaxies within some specified luminosity and radial limits. These are discussed in more detail in other chapters, but in short, our blue fractions are consistent with previous measurements for the same clusters (Crawford et al. 2006).

Tables, images, and astrometric maps of all three cluster populations will be part of the electronic publication of this thesis in peer-reviewed journals. Tables will contain positions, photometric redshifts, M_B , rest-frame $B - V$, $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ line-fluxes and EQW, and their respective errors, with extant spectroscopic data also included.

3.2.1 Comparison to previous studies

Our selection differs from previous selections of compact, star-forming galaxies at intermediate redshifts found in the literature, but by having ground-based and HST data, we can compare the number of compact star forming galaxies that would be found using different selection schemes. We have done this by reanalyzing the selection in MS0451 as a detailed example. We’ve chosen a 0.0031 deg^2 sub-field in the WIYN-imaged area that has deep HST Advanced Camera for Surveys (ACS) imaging in the $F775W$ band, a broad band-pass centered near 775 nm. In this area we use the WIYN data to select 21 LCBGs to $R < 25$ mag with photometric redshifts between 0.3 and 1.0 using the exact definitions in §2. This depth is sufficient to detect all sources in the ACS data. As the detailed comparison below shows, the heterogeneity of the various selection schemes is significant. This implies specific comparison of LCBG samples require careful attention to the selections applied.

LCBG-like galaxies were originally identified by Koo & Kron (1988) in a search for QSOs in a wide-field, deep, multi-band photographic imaging survey. The QSOs were selected as stellar-like objects with $B_J < 22.5$ and colors lying away from the stellar locus in photographic $UJFN$

multi-color diagrams. Follow-up spectroscopy identified 25% of the QSO candidates had very narrow emission-lines consistent with HII-like galaxies at intermediate redshifts, i.e., these were not active galactic nuclei. These objects, classified as compact, narrow emission-line galaxies (CNELGs), lie in a narrow region of color with apparent $B - V < 0.8$ and $U - B < -0.2$. These colors place them outside the stellar locus and at the blue tip of the galaxy apparent-color sequence at this apparent depth. By virtue of their selection requirement that they have stellar-like light-profiles, they form a more compact and high surface-brightness subset of the general LCBG sample defined here. Of the 21 nominal LCBGs we find in the MS0451 ACS field, 12 would have been identified as QSO candidates by Koo & Kron (1988) based on their location in our UBR two-color diagram and their appearance as unresolved in our WIYN images degraded to their seeing (1.75 arcsec FWHM; Koo, Kron, & Cudworth 1986). A subset of 6 of these 12 are in the CNELG region of color-space. Only one object would be found applying the same magnitude limit and it appears too red in U-B to be classified as a CNELG. To the same depth and seeing of Koo & Kron (1988), we find 6 objects that would qualify as QSO candidates by their definition. The galaxies found in the Koo & Kron sample have, on average, a lower redshift than the cluster sample explored here.

In P97, galaxies are selected for their high surface-brightness profiles in red HST images of the Hubble Deep-Field Flanking Fields (HDF-FF). The galaxies were selected with the requirements of $I_{814} < 23.74$ mag, $\langle \mu \rangle \leq 22.24$ mag arcsec⁻², and $r_{0.5} < 0.5''$, where $r_{0.5}$ is the half-light radius, and $\langle \mu \rangle$ is the mean, apparent surface-brightness within $r_{0.5}$ in the I_{814} band. A small correction is applied to account for the different bandpasses. The final sample of star forming galaxies were identified as having colors consistent with HII galaxies. The precise distinction is not clear, but for simplicity we choose our rest-frame color cut of $(B - V) < 0.5$ as a reasonable approximation. Applying the P97 HDF-FF photometric selection (above) with the requirement that rest-frame $(B - V) < 0.5$ yields 44 galaxies within the HST Advanced Camera for Surveys (ACS) field of view in MS0451. As an aside, this surface-density can be compared to an expected 20 compact galaxies that P97 would find in a similar area based on the surface-density they find in the HDF-FF; this indicates a significant enhancement of LCBGs in the cluster field-of-view relative to the HDF-FF. In terms of a cross-comparison of selection, however, only 18 of the 49 selected sources would be identified

as LCBGs in our definition. This culling is due to our absolute magnitude and rest-frame surface brightness limits. In this sense, our selection is more restrictive to sources that are luminous and with higher-intensity star-formation ($M_{\odot} \text{ kpc}^{-2}$). The three sources missed are all suspected high redshift sources that have fainter magnitudes ($< 0.25 \text{ mag}$) than the P97 limit. The un-selected objects from the P97 selection are primarily too faint to be selected as LCBGs.

Hammer et al. (2001) used a very different definition to define compact, star-forming galaxies. Relying on the spectroscopic sample of the Canada-France Redshift Survey (CFRS), they defined luminous, compact galaxies as having a small concentration parameter ($\Delta I \equiv m_I(10.65 \text{ kpc}) - m_I(3.6 \text{ kpc}) \leq 0.75$, where m_I is the I -band magnitude within the specified metric aperture), $M_B < -20$, and a large $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ rest-frame equivalent width: $W_o([\text{OII}]) \geq 15 \text{ \AA}$. Assuming the larger aperture magnitude is near total, by inspection the concentration requirement corresponds to a galaxy size of $r_{0.5} \leq 3.6 \text{ kpc}$. These metric sizes assume $q_0 = 0.5$ and $H_0 = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. For our adopted cosmology the half-light size limit is 4.3 kpc . A review of published, tabulated properties reveals the CFRS sources tend to be larger and redder galaxies than those selected from other LCBG samples. We find 42% of the 21 cluster LCBGs in the MS0451 ACS field satisfy the W_o criterion, based on the narrow-band imaging in Chapter 4. Of this 42%, only 25% satisfy the magnitude (M_B) requirement as well. All 21 LCBGs have $r_{0.5} \leq 3.6 \text{ kpc}$, so the concentration criterion imposes no further diminution of the sample. In the same field of view as MS0451, we would expect to find 21 LCBGs via our selection scheme and 5 via the magnitude and size selection scheme of Hammer et al. (2001) with only 2 objects overlapping. The other three objects in the Hammer et al. sample fail the surface brightness test. These objects are luminous, but do not have the concentrated star formation seen in the LCBG population. These are more likely to be normal, luminous spiral galaxies, but spectroscopic would be required to confirm the low star formation inferred in these galaxies because they have no detected $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ emission from the narrow-band data.

Recent identification of LCBGs by Werk et al. (2004), Garland et al. (2004), and Noeske et al. (2006) are very similar to our classification scheme with two exceptions: (1) a redder color limit of rest-frame $(B - V) < 0.6$ and (2) the requirement that $r_{0.5} < 3.5 \text{ kpc}$ (for Noeske et al. 2006). Their surface-brightness and luminosity cuts are similar-to-identical. Since MS0451 ACS field

LCBG sources have $r_{0.5} < 3.5$, the additional size cut has no consequence for the comparison here. The salient difference is in the color selection. Extending the selection to rest-frame $(B - V) < 0.6$ increases the LCBG sample from 21 to 32 in the same field of view and depth. Recall, we have chosen the bluer color limit based on the theoretical constraint of the bolometric luminosity and star-forming intensity for a constant star-formation rate, described in the previous section; the rest-frame $(B - V) < 0.6$ is a more ad hoc prescription, and clearly includes sources with lower star-formation intensity.

3.3 The Number Density and Distribution of Cluster LCBGs

We plot the surface density of galaxies in Figures 3.2 to 3.4 as a function of radius from the cluster center (defined as the brightest cluster galaxy). The data extend to a radius where our completeness is still uniform in the WIYN images. Two basic results emerge. (1) All populations clearly show evidence of clustering, even in the case of Cl 1325, albeit the signal is significantly weaker as one might expect. (2) LCBGs form a statistically significant population in the verified clusters: $13 \pm 2\%$ to $28 \pm 2\%$ of the total population at $R = 1.5$ Mpc for the low ($z < 0.6$) and high ($z > 0.6$) redshift clusters, and $38 \pm 5\%$ to $50 \pm 4\%$ of the BO galaxies for the same samples (The reported errors are based on the number statistics, but non-Gaussian errors from cluster-membership uncertainties contribute as well). For comparison, we estimate LCBGs constitute approximately 8% and 26% of all field galaxies blue enough to be classified as “BO” at $z = 0.5$ and 0.9 .

We model the projected distribution of the LCBG, BO and red cluster populations with a King profile (King 1972), two spherical-shell density profiles, and a uniform (flat) distribution. The King radius is set to the scale radius of the X-ray profile for each cluster (Schindler 1999, Donahue et al. 2003, Lubin et al. 2004). Spherical-shell models are empty inside of the X-ray scale radius (“shell”) or half this value (“half-shell”), and then both decline as a King profile with a 1 Mpc core radius. The King model fits all of the populations well in a χ^2 sense, except in Cl1325. In this field, we assumed as center based on the coordinates from Oke et al.(1998) and the total and red populations were only well fit by the uniform distribution. For all clusters the red population is best fit by the King model; the BO populations are best fit by the half-shell model in all fields (including Cl1325). The LCBGs in MS0451, Cl0016, and MS1054 are best fit by the shell model, whereas the Cl1322, Cl1325, and

Cl1604 LCBGs are best fit by the half-shell model. If LCBGs are distributed as a King profile, there is a 95% probability we would detect ≥ 1 LCBG in the inner 0.15 Mpc region of MS0451. In any cluster, the absence of sources within the X-ray core radii as compared to the King distribution is observed to 97% confidence. Therefore, LCBGs do not appear to exist in central cluster regions – in agreement with Homeier et al. (2005) findings for star forming galaxies in Cl0152 ($z=0.84$). In general, the higher mass, more concentrated clusters (MS0451, Cl0016, MS1054) tend to have a more significant core deficit, but enlarging the cluster sample would be critical to differentiating the effects of richness and redshift.

3.4 Morphology of LCBGs

Given the small apparent sizes of LCBGs at the cluster redshifts, the detailed light profiles of the cluster LCBGs are accessible only with HST imaging. Here we focus on the quantitative morphological properties of LCBGs in the cluster cores. The measurements are described in detail in Chapter 2. Typically the HST coverage with ACS is in the range of 1.28-1.57 kpc at the cluster redshift, or 25 – 50% of R_{200} .

The small sizes and high luminosities of LCBGs are evident in Figure 3.5: Virtually all of the sources are above the average relationship for local disk galaxies (Shen et al. 2003). This is anticipated given their selection (§2 and Figure 1). For the most part, the cluster LCBGs are comparable in size and luminosity to other compact star forming galaxies at intermediate redshift (P97). They are larger and brighter than local H II galaxies (Gallego et al. 1997), while somewhat smaller and fainter than Lyman-break galaxies (Lowenthal et al. 1998). Some of these trends are due to the selection effects imposed by apparent magnitude limits (e.g., the low-luminosity Lyman-break galaxies are too faint to detect) and accessible volumes (e.g., the intrinsically rare high-luminosity H II galaxies require very large surveys to find). Nonetheless, these apparent trends are likely indicative of evolving luminosity functions, as seen now in many spectroscopic redshift surveys over the past decade, particularly in the blue-galaxy population.

Due to the unique ACS imaging over a wide area in the field of MS 1054, we are able to look at the detailed properties of LCBGs in the outer regions of this cluster. As seen in Figure 5, the LCBGs in the wings of MS 1054 ($1.5 < r < 2.5$ kpc, where $R_{200} = 1.81$ Mpc for this cluster) exhibit sizes and

luminosities that are enhanced relative to the core LCBG populations in the intermediate redshift clusters. They are reminiscent of the most extreme field LCBG populations at these redshifts, and extend almost up to the Lyman-break galaxy regime. Spectroscopic confirmation will be required to confirm these are cluster sources and not lower redshift interlopers due to the errors in photometric redshifts, but 65% of the sources do show evidence for strong [OII] λ 3727 emission ($W_o > 10 \text{ \AA}$). If indeed most are bona-fide cluster or cluster-periphery members, this may be suggestive of a dimming and truncation of the population associated with a transition from field to cluster, i.e., an associated quenching and stripping process during accretion.

Many of these galaxies display the high asymmetries, as seen in Figure 3.6, associated with merging or disturbed galaxies. All of the sources in this plot are sampled at levels that should produce reasonable values for the asymmetry. As compared to other samples of LCBGs, the cluster LCBGs seem to have a greater range in asymmetries with some sources having very small values. One possible explanation for the relatively symmetric profiles of cluster LCBGs is if the star formation is induced by tidal forces instead of mergers. Unlike mergers that are expected to cause asymmetric structures (Conselice 2003), tidal forces drive the gas to the center of the galaxy resulting in a central, concentrated burst of star formation, which leaves a much more symmetric light distribution (Bekki 1999). Most of the galaxies have small concentration indexes, C_{2080} , indicative of exponential light-profiles. If the galaxies evolve along lines of constant concentration, these galaxies will end up in regions occupied by late-type disk galaxies or dwarf ellipticals.

3.5 Star-Formation Properties of LCBGs

Using the narrow-band data which samples the rest-frame [OII] λ 3727 flux at redshifts of each of our clusters, we are able to estimate the star formation rate (SFR) for all of our cluster LCBGs. The detailed measurements are described in Chapter 4. As illustrated in Figure 7, the SFR for LCBGs in the ACS images is, in general, less than the SFR for LCBGs in the field (Guzman et al. 1997) at the same redshift. In more detail, cluster LCBGs at $z \sim 0.55$ have SFR comparable to field LCBGs at $z \sim 0.4$, while cluster LCBGs at $z \sim 0.85$ have similar SFR as field LCBGs at $z \sim 0.6$. The lower redshift cluster LCBGs also display lower SFR than the higher redshift sample. Larger field samples and better estimates of the SFR in cluster LCBGs, including the effects of extinction,

are needed confirm this observed trend of “down-sizing” in the SFR of LCBGs (Cowie et al. 1996).

To estimate the $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ emission-line strength from the narrow-band imaging, we fit stellar-population synthesis model spectra to the observed broad- and narrow on- and off-bands. This process is necessary to derive accurate flux and EW measurements; the details of the procedure and models are described in Chapter 4. As a result of this process, we can measure the average age and extinction of the stellar population, which are given in Table 3.1 for each cluster for the full LCBG sample. The LCBGs in general show very small ages while displaying significant extinction.

If indeed these derived extinctions are correct, then the implied intrinsic color, surface-brightness, and star-formation rates are all significantly larger than we report here. In question, of course, is the absolute – and even relative – accuracy of these results. For example, there is a covariance between extinction and age; we have not verified the degree to which our “best” model fits are unique or even discriminatory between trades of age vs extinction, or to different values of the (effective) reddening curve. It is also suspicious that the mean age decreases with redshift as our bluest band-pass (U) shifts from being centered on rest-frame 240 nm at $z = 0.55$ to 195 nm at $z = 0.9$. What we can say is that with reasonable assumptions about star-forming histories, metallicity, and extinction curves, these galaxies appear to have spectral energy distributions that are consistent with very young bursts (2-8 Myrs) that are quite extincted (A_V of 1.5-2 mag). Independent verification of the extinction through, e.g., Spitzer Far-IR observations would allow us to test the uniqueness of this interpretation.

3.6 The Morphology-Density Relation for LCBGs

Here we compare the surface-density of cluster objects to the same objects in the field. We include all of our cluster fields in this analysis, including Cl 1325. We couch our comparison in terms of “enhancement:” the surface-density ratio of cluster to field. The cluster surface-densities are those calculated for Figures 3.2 to 3.4, i.e., the mean surface-densities within annular areas. Field densities are calculated by integrating field luminosity functions over same redshift interval as used to define the cluster samples. Red and BO galaxy field densities are calculated using the luminosity function of the DEEP2 data (Faber et al. 2005). These data are of excellent quality, and therefore yield a high-fidelity estimate of these field-population densities. The field luminosity function for LCBGs is somewhat less well mapped. With our selection criteria, the field LCBG surface density

derived from the P97 sample yields 1.2 and 5.44 Mpc^{-2} at $z = 0.5$ and $z = 0.90$, respectively, after applying corrections due to their selection effects, as discussed in §2.1. Independently using the foreground field LCBGs in the high-redshift clusters, and the background field LCBGs in the low redshift clusters we estimate the density of LCBGs at $z \sim 0.5$ and 0.9 to be 1.2 ± 0.3 and $2.0 \pm 1.2 \text{ Mpc}^{-2}$, respectively. In future analysis we can make estimates of the field red and BO densities from our own data in the same way, and compare to the DEEP2 results. This will provide a check on our foreground/background method used here for the LCBGs.

We find a much lower value for the space density of LCBGs at high redshift. The error quoted, based purely on number statistics, is likely an under-estimate of the true error due to the effects of the photometric redshift error caused by the faint apparent magnitudes associated with these objects. However, our values are estimated at the typical surface density calculated from the DEEP2 field luminosity function for each redshift bin. The HDF north field is known to have several over-densities at high redshifts with peaks in the redshift distribution at $z = 0.51, 0.56, 0.64, 0.85$, and 1.02 . The corresponding structures have velocity dispersions ranging from $\sigma = 500 - 700 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (Wirth et al. 2004). So the rapid evolution in this population observed by P97 may be a result of over-densities in the flanking fields at high redshifts. In fact, of the eight high redshift LCBGs in the P97 sample, three could be associated with the 0.85 peak based on their redshift. In this section, we estimated the field density of LCBGs as the average of the estimate from P97 and our own data.

The enhancement as a function of cluster-galaxy surface density of *all* galaxies down to $M_B < -18.5$, shown in Figure 3.8, reveals some dramatically different normalizations for the three different galaxy sub-populations. For all rich clusters the enhancement of the red population is the highest at all surface-densities probed (above 10 Mpc^{-2}). These densities are well above the typical field value (5 Mpc^{-2}) estimated from the field luminosity function at these redshifts. Moreover, the change in enhancement with surface-density rises *more* quickly than surface-density. The BO galaxies show only a modest enhancement, and the change of enhancement with surface rises only as or *less* quickly than surface-density. These basic results are qualitatively as expected according to the morphology-density relationship (Dressler et al. 1997), i.e., the early-type galaxy fraction rises in dense environments, while the late-type fraction declines.

In contrast to these two populations, LCBGs display a moderately large enhancement, intermediate between the BO and red galaxies. Likewise, the change in enhancement with surface-density is also intermediate between the red and BO galaxy trends. There is some indication that the enhancement of LCBGs drops precipitously at surface densities above 150 Mpc^{-2} . This is most pronounced for the lower-redshift clusters, but is indicated clearly in the formal model fits of the surface-density radial profiles. The drop in the enhancement or absence of data points about surface-densities of 150 Mpc^{-2} is statistically significant (2.5σ). A similar, but less pronounced and less significant result is seen for the BO galaxies. The interpretation of this result will be discussed below.

There are also some noticeable similarities between clusters, and trends with redshift. The striking similarity in enhancement between the two, rich clusters at $z \sim 0.5$ is apparent in the left panel of Figure 3.8. For the higher-redshift clusters, however, the red galaxy enhancement is down at a given surface-density, while the BO enhancement is slightly elevated. These are modest, 20% effects, and argue against a strong change in the over-all blue fraction with redshift at any given surface-density – at least for these clusters. The LCBG enhancement, again in contrast, appears to be much more erratic for the higher-redshift clusters. At a given surface-density, the range of enhancement increases from under a factor of two at $z \sim 0.5$ to almost a factor of 8 in the higher- z clusters. Much of this variation is caused by the difference between the rich cluster MS1054 and the other clusters. The higher redshift clusters in our sample show a broader range of enhancements that bracket the values seen at $z \sim 0.5$. Some of this variation is caused by imposing circular symmetry on the clusters: the poor clusters are far less concentrated than the rich clusters and have more visible filamentary structure. For this reason, further investigation of the LCBG enhancement will be confined to the local galaxy density.

3.6.1 Local-Density Enhancement of Cluster LCBGs: Trends with Local Density

To explore in more detail the trends of the cluster LCBG enhancement with redshift, we plot this enhancement and LCBG surface density as a function of local density for all of the clusters, binned into three redshift intervals of 0.1, in Figure 3.9. The local density of a cluster object, Σ_{10} , is defined as the inverse of the projected circular area (Mpc^{-2}) with radius equal to the distance to the tenth nearest neighbor at the cluster redshift and with $M_B < -18.5$. This is somewhat different

than the surface-density calculated and used in the previous section: Σ_{10} is a more local estimate of density, and makes no assumptions of circular symmetry or cluster center. A typical value of Σ_{10} for the field is 4.2 (4.7) Mpc^{-2} at $z = 0.5(0.9)$. The enhancement in this plot is calculated for each object as the ratio of the density of LCBGs in the Σ_{10} area divided by the field surface density at this redshift, and we measure the enhancement for both cluster and field LCBGs. Hence both the density and enhancement measurement in Figure 3.9 are much more local than that made for Figure 3.8. Unlike the previous section, we assume the field surface density of LCBGs from our data.

The surface density of LCBGs increases approximately (15%) between the low and high redshift samples. The rapid increase seen in the field estimate (66% increase) with redshift is not observed in the higher density regions. The slope of the $\log(\Sigma_{lcbg}) - \log(\Sigma_{10})$ relationship increases by 6% between $z = 0.5$ and 0.9. At higher redshift, the LCBGs are becoming more clustered, which has been observed with other samples of starbursting galaxies (Giavalisco et al. 1998, Cooper et al. 2006). At all redshifts, the relationship appears to turnover at the last point (i.e. excluding the highest density point produces a steeper slope to the relationship). The absence of LCBGs in the highest density regions contributes to this turnover.

For comparison to local populations, we plot the expected enhancement based on the $z=0$ morphology-density relationships. The measurement of the local morphology-density relationship for ellipticals, S0, and spiral galaxies is taken from Dressler et al. (1997). The relationship is converted to enhancement by multiplying the fraction of each population by the surface density and then assuming that the local surface density equals 3.9 Mpc^{-2} . The local surface density is based on the nearby luminosity function (Madgwick et al. 2002) and assuming that the sampling is over a similar volume as the intermediate redshift samples due to the selection in photometric redshifts. We also combine the Spiral and S0 fractions to calculate the fractions. The dE enhancement is based on data from Binggeli et al. (1989). They list the fraction of dE as part of a total population for a high and low density environment, but they do not specify the exact values. We assume the low density environment is equivalent to the field and the high density environment has $\Sigma_{10} = 100 \text{ Mpc}^{-2}$. If this assumption is an underestimate, the dE relationship will be steeper than what is plotted. Finally, we plot the ratio for all giant galaxies by assuming the enhancement is the surface density divided

by the field surface density (3.9 Mpc^{-2}).

The enhancement of the $z = 0.55$ LCBGs appear to increase more rapidly than the enhancement for giant galaxies in the local Universe before dropping at large galaxy densities. The low redshift LCBG population seems to prefer the moderate density regimes found either in groups or the wings of clusters, but LCBGs do not appear to survive inside the cores of rich clusters. At these redshifts, the mechanism triggering the formation of LCBGs are likely to be tidal interactions and mergers which have high efficiencies at these densities (Bekki et al. 2001, van Dokkum et al. 1999).

In the high redshift sample, the enhancement of LCBGs does not appear to exceed the enhancement for giant galaxies, and the suppression of LCBGs at the highest densities is still seen. The lowered enhancement of LCBGs is more indicative of the changing field density than the cluster density. The density at a given surface density appears to increase with redshift, but more rapidly at the level of the field. The average mass of LCBGs was seen to increase with redshift along with the density (P97), and an transition may be occurring between the low and high redshift populations to explain the different enhancements observed.

At first glance, the LCBG populations appear to fit the enhancement for the local Spiral + S0 population with the high redshift sample tending towards the spiral distribution. If LCBGs are an infalling population, there are likely affected by the same processes that remove gas for star formation in spiral galaxies. The turnover in the LCBGs population begins at $\Sigma_{10} \sim 40$, which approximately corresponds to a projected cluster radius of $R = 0.6 \text{ Mpc}$. Around this radius in these clusters is where ram-pressure stripping begins to become efficient (Fujita & Nagashima 1999, Homeier et al. 2005). Other processes may have begun the removal of gas available for star formation (e.g., tidal stripping, galaxy harassment, consumption of the gas by the intense star formation), but ram pressure stripping is expected to quickly remove any remaining gas at these high densities leading to the cessation of star formation. Once the star formation has ended, these galaxies will begin to fade and become redder; they will rapidly leave the region of parameter space that defines LCBGs. However, another possibility exists for the deficit of LCBGs in the center of the cluster: Tidal forces and ICM pressure could drive all of the gas into the center of the galaxy leading to large extinctions and red colors (Duc et al. 2002). Future exploration for obscured star formation in cluster LCBGs

with either Spitzer and/or radio data will differentiate between these two theories.

3.6.2 Cluster LCBG Enhancement as a Progenitor-Population Signal

The enhancement of intermediate-redshift LCBGs with galaxy density provides a unique test of various conjectures for what LCBGs will become by the present epoch. By comparison to the enhancement-density relations of possible descendants, we can constrain LCBGs role as their progenitors. We explore these constraints by examining the enhancement as a function of redshift (Figure 3.10).

The enhancement of any population is of course very sensitive to the presence of large scale structure. LCBGs are no exception. Peaks in the redshift distribution outside of the cluster redshift will introduce spurious “enhancements” at densities that are not particularly elevated above the mean field level. This is due to the fact that most of the redshift peaks are the intersection of the survey pencil-beam through modest-density sheets and filaments, not bona fide clusters. The resolution of our photometric redshifts alone is inadequate to distinguish between these density regimes. Spectroscopically confirmed redshift distributions exist for all of our cluster fields. Multiple redshift peaks exist most noticeably in the Cl 1322, Cl 1325, and Cl 1604 fields (Oke et al. 1998). Indeed, for Cl 1325, the evidence is that there is no true, rich cluster there at all (see, for example, the distribution of surface-densities in Figure 8). For this reason, we have over-plotted the spectroscopic redshift distribution from the literature for all cluster fields in Figure 3.10.

To calculate the enhancement over the full redshift range probed in our fields, we estimate the field density from the DEEP2 luminosity functions at intermediate redshift (Faber et al. 2005), and supplement this with the 2DF luminosity functions for local galaxies (Magdwick et al. 2002). We assume that field and cluster galaxies evolve in the same manner. The data is binned in redshift to roughly twice the estimated errors in the photometric redshifts.

In addition to the data, we plot the expected enhancement due to the luminous galaxy population, the spiral galaxy population, and the dwarf elliptical (dE) population of a Coma-like cluster appearing at the redshift of each cluster. The luminosity function for Coma is based on Beijersbergen et al. (2002), while the number of spirals is estimated from the morphology-density relationship (Dressler et al. 1997). The ratio of dwarf galaxies to giant galaxies in the field and clusters is es-

timated from Binggeli, Tarengi & Sandage, (1990). The models are binned to the same redshift resolution as the data.

Assessing Figure 10, first it is clear the enhancement of LCBGs traces the general large scale structure along the line of sight sampled by previous spectroscopic surveys, even in redshift regions where the true space-density is not as high as the massive clusters. Focusing on those redshift regions associated with a bona fide rich cluster, we see there is a relatively dramatic enhancement in the LCBG population. This enhancement is greater than what is predicted for all luminous galaxies, and significantly above that for only the spiral population. The best model is that for the dE population, although another alternative would be to require these clusters to be substantially richer than Coma. Clearly all of the models fail in the case of MS 1054, which could either be extremely rich overall, or have a rich dwarf population. If virialized, MS0451, Cl0016, and MS1054 are all more massive than the Coma cluster at their current redshift, and all the clusters are expected to increase their mass by factor of two (Eke, Navarro, & Frenk 1998).

Despite these uncertainties, the simplest interpretation in the context of this model is that LCBGs are most consistent with being low mass galaxies undergoing a burst of star formation, that will subsequently fade by several magnitudes to become part of today’s cluster dE population. This is a conclusion that has been reached independently for the field population of LCBGs. The suggestion, therefore, is that both field and cluster LCBGs are a manifestation of a similar burst-and-fade phenomenon occurring for relatively low-mass galaxies between intermediate-to-low redshift.

3.7 Discussion

We find LCBGs in intermediate redshift clusters compose a significant fraction of the BO populations despite the clusters’ different redshifts, environments (X-ray luminosities and projected densities), and relative blue fractions. At greater “richness,” there is clear segregation in the surface-densities of sub-populations (see Table 3.2). At luminous-galaxy surface-densities of 100 Mpc^{-2} , the enhancement of these different sub-populations relative to the field are a factor of 2-4 for BO galaxies, 8-20 for LCBGs, and 30-50 for red galaxies in both clusters. This is suggestive of LCBGs as progenitors of populations found preferentially in clusters today.

The LCBGs are small, luminous galaxies with very blue colors, strong emission lines, and

a young, enthusiastically star-forming population. Further IR imaging is required to determine anything about any underlying population as the optical imaging is dominated by the relatively young population. The morphology of the LCBGs range from normal disk-like galaxies to morphological disturbed to extremely compact. For the galaxies for which we can derive reliable measurements, the LCBGs have concentrations indicative of an exponential light profile with a mix of asymmetries. Without any structural evolution, the morphologies are similar to bulge-less disks or dwarf elliptical galaxies; only a very few galaxies do have high concentrations indicative of bulge systems.

The measurement of the enhancement reveals similarities to two different populations. As a function of redshift, the enhancement reveals a population that is best described as either evolving into a dwarf elliptical or a red (E+S0) cluster population. On the other hand, the spatial distribution of LCBGs is reminiscent of the local spiral+S0 distribution. However, if the LCBGs are in-falling into the cluster on mostly radial orbits, the observed spatial distribution is unlikely to be similar to the distribution of the descendent population today after the galaxies have interacted with the cluster environment for multiple cluster crossings. The redshift enhancement is a bulk measurement of the number of galaxies and its interpretation depends on the assumption that the cluster and field LCBGs will have similar evolutionary fates.

So far, our results do not conflict with the possible evolutionary sequence of Hammer et al. (2005)—that LCBGs represent a transition phase in gas-rich disk-galaxy mergers. This is in contrast to a notion where a more isolated dwarf progenitor undergoes a tertiary star-formation episode. In the Hammer et al. scenario, a major merger destroys the pre-existing disks, but a new disk reforms, phoenix-like, from a cold gas reservoir around the merger remnant. If this were to occur in, or during in-fall into a cluster, while the initial merger and compact star-burst may occur, it is unclear what will happen after that. Typically in clusters, cold gas won't be available for accretion, because it will swept away by the hot IGM. Furthermore, galaxy harassment may efficiently remove much of the outer regions of the two galaxies, decreasing their gas fraction prior to merging (Moore et al. 1996). Therefore the merger must occur early in the accretion process, if at all for the disk to reform. We conclude it is still plausible that cluster and field LCBGs are the result of the merger between massive galaxies ($\sim M^*$). If this is indeed the case, it is likely the end-products in clusters will be

prevented from re-forming their disks, and their descendants will be low-mass ellipticals, or dEs .

Recent observations of a sample of intermediate redshift clusters indicate a deficit of galaxies along the red sequence (de Lucia et al. 2005, Goto et al 2005). We suggested (Crawford et al. 2006) this was indirect evidence supporting the notion that LCBGs were the intermediate-redshift progenitors which filled in this red sequence by the present epoch. Our more recent analysis of our own cluster observations (Chapter 2) do not support the conclusions reached by de Lucia et al. (2005) and Goto et al. (2005). Specifically, we find that the red-sequence luminosity function (i.e., that for early-type cluster galaxies) is comparable in shape to local clusters to $M_B < -18.5$. Independent analysis of other clusters by Andreon (2006) agree with this. Since we already account for the majority of the bright red sequence seen in rich clusters at intermediate redshift, the possibility for LCBGs to evolve into L^* red-sequence galaxies by the present epoch is small unless these are super-Coma clusters. However, the above discussion does not rule out the possibility that the LCBGs fade substantially to fill the faint end of the red sequence, for which the luminosity function is not known at intermediate-redshifts.

The length of time these galaxies form stars at the observed “enthusiastic” level is the most significant factor in determining what they will become. Since the red sequence is already populated in the rich clusters (relative to our expectations for a Coma-like system), a short period of star formation completely eliminates the possibility that these galaxies become L^* descendants simply because there will be too many of them. Moreover, they would not be able to fade very much, which is rather unlikely given their extreme colors and light-weighted ages (Table 1). However, a longer period for the compact, star-forming phase increases the likelihood that we are witnessing massive mergers. Hammer et al. (2005) estimate that galaxies remain in the compact phase for ~ 1 Gyr. If true – and these galaxies only burst once – the expected number of descendants is 320 in one cluster if we assume LCBGs are produced in clusters at an exponentially decreasing rate between $z = 1.2 - 0.3$. Increasing the number of luminous red galaxies within R_{200} by even 10% of this value would produce too many galaxies for a Coma-like cluster at $z = 0$ when combined with the observed luminosity function of the red galaxies in these clusters. Alternatively, an L^* galaxy can lose 99% of its mass due to harassment in a cluster environment (Mastropietro et al. 2005) leaving a dwarf

elliptical remnant.

We can produce an improved estimate for the length of time expected for these galaxies to be in the LCBG phase from our data. First, we assume no size or concentration evolution for the population, ignoring any change in structural parameters that may occur while these galaxies virialize after merging (Conselice 2003). Second, we assume all blue galaxies are falling into the cluster and that all in-falling galaxies experience the same evolution, eventually landing on the red sequence. Take the case for MS 0451, where we have 27 emission line objects within 1.5 Mpc of the cluster center with $M_B < -18.5$, and 14 of these objects are LCBGs. Of the BO population, 40% are emission line galaxies. If the star formation in the emission-line galaxies is quenched and they fade toward the red sequence, the galaxies would remain blue for another 0.7 Gyr (Poggianti et al. 1999) and be classified as BO objects. If the galaxies spend approximately 60% of their time as BO galaxies as blue, non-emission line galaxies, then 0.45 Gyrs would be spent as emission-line cluster BO galaxies. Using the 0.45 Gyr lifetime for emission-line LCBGs, 350 galaxies are added to the cluster from $z = 0.3 - 1.2$ assuming the same decline in the population as for the previous estimate. Once again, the galaxies would have to significantly fade or be destroyed in the cluster environment otherwise low redshift clusters would have vastly different luminosity functions. In the end, the amount of fading will depend on the initial burst strength and length, the underlying population, and the amount of stripping caused by the cluster environment.

3.8 Conclusion

In this Chapter, we have identified a population of LCBGs in six intermediate redshift galaxy clusters. The LCBGs represent a significant fraction of the galaxies in the cluster ($\sim 20\%$), and cluster LCBGs are very similar in terms of size, color, and luminosity to their counterparts in the field. Further observations will be required to determine if their mass (both stellar and dynamical) indicate we are observing similar populations in the two environments.

The LCBGs appear to be distributed as a shell-like population around the cluster. The distribution of LCBGs are less compact than the distributions of any other population, and a deficit of LCBGs is seen in the cluster core. The lack of LCBGs in the cluster core is probably caused by the rapid quenching of the star formation in these clusters, but we can not rule out the possibility of

obscured star formation until FIR or radio observations are made of these clusters.

Most of our analysis has been couched in terms of the enhancement, the ratio of cluster objects to the number of objects expected in the field. LCBGs are more common in high density regions, although completely missing in the cores of rich clusters. As a function of surface density, the enhancement of LCBGs are most similar to the distribution of spiral plus S0 galaxies in local clusters, but as a function of redshift, the enhancement of LCBGs is very similar to dwarf elliptical galaxies or the red cluster population. These results can co-exist if the spatial distribution of LCBGs does not coincide with the final distribution of its descendants.

Despite their similar spatial distribution, LCBGs are an extreme sub-component of the BO population in terms of their cluster enhancement, color, and surface-brightness. Important questions still remain about this population, and future observations from a range of facilities will provide further constraints on both the origin of these objects and their eventual fate.

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Table 3.1. Median Spectral Properties of LCBGs^a

Cluster	z	Age Myr	A_V mags	SFR ^b $h_{70}^{-2} M_{\odot} yr^{-1}$
MS0451	0.53	8 ⁺² ₋₄	1.1 ^{+0.7} _{-0.8}	2.45 ^{+1.44} _{-1.67}
Cl0016	0.55	8 ⁺¹² ₋₆	1.8 ^{+0.3} _{-0.9}	2.23 ^{+3.05} _{-1.23}
Cl1322	0.75	2 ⁺⁸ ₋₁	1.9 ^{+1.2} _{-0.8}	2.25 ^{+2.10} _{-1.07}
MS1054	0.83	2 ⁺⁷ ₋₁	1.6 ^{+1.0} _{-1.3}	2.79 ^{+1.82} _{-1.60}
Cl1604	0.90	2 ⁺⁶ ₋₁	1.8 ^{+0.3} _{-0.6}	2.18 ^{+2.21} _{-0.99}

^aQuartile values are reported in subscript (0.25) and superscript(0.75).

^bMedian star formation rate for LCBGs with $EW > 10 \text{ \AA}$.

Table 3.2. Density of Sub-populations at $R = 1.5$ Mpc

Cluster	Red Mpc^{-2}	BO Mpc^{-2}	LCBGs Mpc^{-2}
MS0451	26.6	12.9	5.4
Cl0016	34.9	18.6	6.7
Cl1322	14.3	19.5	7.2
MS1054	21.8	20.6	12
Cl1604	8.9	15.8	8.5

Fig. 3.1.— Rest-frame B-band surface-brightness vs. color for cluster LCBGs (filled symbols) and field LCBGs found in the cluster HST images (open symbols). The symbols are coded by field: MS0451 (red squares), Cl0016 (green circles), Cl1325 (purple chalices), Cl1322 (cyan diamonds), MS1054 (black pentagons), and CL1604 (blue triangles). Field LCBGs from P97 are plotted as yellow stars. Other intermediate redshift cluster galaxies in our fields are grey points brighter than $M_B = -18.5$. Lines mark the selection criteria for LCBGs used here. Labels indicate approximate location of $z=0$ Hubble types from Bershady et al. (2000). The characteristic error bars for the measurements are given in the lower left-hand corner and are dominated by the error in photometric redshift.

Fig. 3.2.— Projected surface-densities for cluster galaxies in MS 0451 and Cl 0016 at $z \sim 0.55$. The top six panels are the differential distributions of (descending) red galaxies, BO galaxies, and LCBGs MS0451 and Cl1604. Model curves (see text) are for a King profile (solid curve) and shell models (dashed) based on the X-ray light profile. Dotted lines represent field densities for each class at the cluster redshift (see text). Solid lines are the LCBG field density as measured in our “off” image. The number, N_{200} , is the number of objects at R_{200} in each respective sub-sample. Bottom panels show mean surface-densities for all sub-samples, with symbols coded in the panels above.

Fig. 3.3.— Same as Figure 3.2 except for the clusters Cl 1325 and Cl 1322 at $z \sim 0.75$.

Fig. 3.4.— Same as Figure 3.2 except for the clusters MS 1054 and Cl 1604 at $z \sim 0.85$.

Fig. 3.5.— Magnitude-size relationship for LCBGs and other compact star forming galaxies. Symbols for cluster LCBGs are the same as Figure 3.1. Open pentagons represent LCBGs in the wings of MS1054, a region only probed by ACS in MS1054. Field compact star-forming galaxies are represented by grey symbols: open squares (local H II galaxies, Gallego et al. 1997), filled triangles (CNELGs, Jangren et al. 2006), stars (LCBGs, P97), and open diamonds (Lyman-break galaxies, Lowenthal et al. 1997). The solid line is the low redshift magnitude-size relationship for disk galaxies (Shen et al. 2003). Cluster LCBGs are comparable to field LCBGs at similar redshifts, are intermediate in luminosity between local H II galaxies and high-redshift star-bursts, and are elevated in surface-brightness relative to today’s normal spirals.

Fig. 3.6.— (Top) Asymmetry and concentration for the cluster LCBGs appearing in MS 0451, Cl 0016, and Cl 1604. Symbols for cluster and field sources are the same as previous figures with the addition of the Frei et al. (1996) sample of local galaxies (grey circles; Bershadsky, Jangren & Conselice 2000) and Conselice (2003) sample of dwarf elliptical galaxies (grey pentagons). The cluster LCBGs have larger range of asymmetry values than the LCBGs from the field. (Bottom) Rest-frame $(B - V)_0$ color and image-concentration of cluster LCBGs. Assuming no structural changes, the LCBGs will evolve vertically in this plane, becoming redder as they run out of fuel.

Fig. 3.7.— Star formation as a function of surface brightness for a sample of cluster LCBGs in the HST ACS images. Symbols are as in Figure 3.1. The field sample of LCBGs from P97 has been split into low ($z < 0.5$), medium ($0.5 < z < 0.7$), and high ($z > 0.7$) redshift samples. The higher redshift cluster LCBGs have large SFR than the lower redshift clusters, but the cluster sample is missing the galaxies with large SFR seen in some of the high redshift galaxies in the Guzman et al. (1997) sample.

Fig. 3.8.— Cluster galaxy enhancement relative to the field for different galaxy types as a function of surface density for all cluster galaxies with $M_B < -18.5$. Surface-densities are calculated as in Figures 3.2-3.4 within circular annuli about the cluster center. The two $z \sim 0.5$ clusters (MS 0451 and Cl0016) are plotted in the left panel; the 4 $z > 0.7$ clusters (Cl 1325, Cl 1322, MS 1054, Cl 1604) are plotted in the right panel. Curves are the best fit models to the radial surface-density distributions for each population (Figures 3.2-3.3), again normalized to the field surface-densities. Linear fits in log space to the red (dotted), BO (dashed), and LCBG (solid) populations are given as straight lines.

Fig. 3.9.— (Top) Density of LCBGs as a function of the local density as measured by Σ_{10} . (Middle) Enhancement of LCBGs as a function of Σ_{10} . Also plotted are models of the expected enhancement for different local populations as indicated by the key. (Bottom) Comparisons of different models as a function of Σ_{10} . $\rho_{E\Sigma}$ is defined as the difference between the observed enhancement and the enhancement of giant galaxies divided by the enhancement of giant galaxies. In all of the plots, each point is constructed from the average properties of 250 galaxies from all of the fields, except the $z = 0.35$ data where each point represents the average of 50 galaxies. Errorbar-bars represent the dispersion in enhancement within this bin, i.e., not the estimated error in the mean. The declining enhancement with increasing redshift indicates the number density of cluster LCBGs is not as rapidly evolving as the field population, i.e., LCBGs are present in greater numbers in clusters at lower

Fig. 3.10.— Enhancement of LCBGs relative to the field as a function of redshift for all galaxies within a $9' \times 9'$ field of view. The measurement is made for LCBGs in 0.1 bins in redshift space. Symbols for each cluster are as in Figure 3.1. Lines represent expected models for the enhancement of possible progenitor populations at redshifts of $z=0.55$ (top), 0.75 (middle), and 0.85 (bottom). The populations are luminous galaxies (dotted line), luminous spirals only (dashed line), dwarf ellipticals (solid line).

Chapter 4

Observations of Star Formation Induced by the Hierarchical Growth of Galaxy Clusters

Abstract

We present rest-frame [OII] λ 3727 narrow-band imaging of six intermediate redshift galaxy clusters from the WIYN Long-Term Variability Survey (WLTV): MS0451.6-0305 ($z=0.538$), Cl 0016+1609 ($z=0.55$), Cl 1325+3010 ($z=0.72$), Cl 1322+3027 ($z=0.755$), MS1054.3-0321 ($z=0.823$), Cl 1604+1609 ($z=0.90$). WIYN 3.5m UBRIZ broad-band and two, tailored narrow-band observations per cluster provide a complete measurement of the un-obscured star formation rate to levels as low as $0.1M_{\odot}yr^{-1}$. We describe the observations, the technique to measure high precision line fluxes, and the method to identify cluster emission-line sources from other sources which appear to have flux excess in the narrow, on-band.

For all clusters, the [OII] λ 3727 luminosity function displays a larger normalization relative to the field at these redshifts down to $L_{[OII]} \sim 10^{40}$ ergs s^{-1} , but the *fraction* of [OII] λ 3727 emission-line objects is low relative to the field. The fraction of blue galaxies (defined with the classic Butcher-Oemler criterion) with detected [OII] λ 3727 emission at the cluster redshift, $f_{oi:b}$, is under 60% for the $z \sim 0.55$ clusters. This is comparable to the field at these redshifts. The higher redshift clusters ($z > 0.7$) have similar $f_{oi:b}$, in contrast to the field where $f_{oi:b}$ is near unity. However, this particular result is subject to considerable uncertainty due to redshift-dependent contamination arising from strong evolution in the field. For all clusters, the star formation rate per galaxy averaged over the total population declines at higher densities and smaller cluster radii, but the average star formation of the star-forming galaxies show little variation with these parameters or when compared to the field. These results are consistent with a picture where the morphology-density relation is still largely in place in the cores of rich clusters to $z \sim 1$, cluster star-formation comes largely from an accreting field population, and this star-formation is soon snuffed out upon galaxy in-fall. The total mass-normalized star formation rate within $0.5 R_{200}$ mimics the decline in the comoving star formation rate if also normalized by Ω_{matter} .

For the clusters as a whole we find the total cluster star formation rate shows no correlation with cluster X-ray properties, mass, or redshift, but does display a distribution similar to the upper limit in [OII] λ 3727 fraction and stellar mass seen in other populations. The mass-normalized total star formation rate shows the strongest evidence for correlation with the ‘‘luminosity gap’’ statistic,

the magnitude difference between the first and second ranked cluster members within R_{200} . If the luminosity gap statistic is related to cluster growth, as suggested by previous studies, our correlation provides evidence that indeed star formation is enhanced in merging structures.

4.1 Introduction

Since the first observations by Butcher & Oemler (1978, 1984; hereafter “BO”), the evolution of cluster galaxies has been a subject filled with controversy. In particular, the fraction of blue cluster galaxies as a function of cluster redshift has been a matter of debate, and the very definition of a BO galaxy has shifted with time from being photometric to spectroscopic, e.g., the k+a galaxies of Dressler & Gunn (1982). Despite numerous photometric and spectroscopic confirmation that, in general, there are more blue galaxies in clusters at high redshifts (Rakos & Schombert 1995, Ellingson et al. 1999, Goto et al. 2003), the variation seen in individual cluster populations hinders any simple explanation for the phenomenon (Koo 1981, Andreon & Ettori 1999, de Propris et al. 2003). Further conflicts arise when comparing cluster populations with other properties besides redshift, such as richness, mass, and X-ray luminosity (Margoniner et al. 2001, Goto et al. 2003, de Propris et al. 2004, Goto 2005).

Nonetheless, the change in galaxy populations with density and redshift is real. The morphology-density relationship provides clear evidence that galaxies in higher density environments¹ are dominated by early type galaxies, whereas those in lower density environments tend to be spirals (Dressler 1980, Goto et al. 2004). While the fraction of elliptical galaxies does not change with redshift, the lenticular population disappears in favor of spirals in the highest redshift clusters (Dressler et al. 1997, Smith et al. 2005, Postman et al. 2005). The morphology-density relationship can also be restated as the star-formation–density relationship: The star formation per galaxy is lowest in high density regions (Balogh et al. 1999, Lewis et al. 2002, Gomez et al. 2003). Likewise, the fraction of star forming galaxies is also lower in dense regions. However, at least in the local Universe, the average star-formation rate for star-forming galaxies shows little variation between cluster and field environments (Balogh et al. 2004, Kodama et al. 2004, Rines et al. 2005), particularly after accounting for the different morphological mix between the two environments (Biviano et al. 1997).

¹For our purposes, environment refers to the differences between clusters, groups, and the field. For example, two galaxies in the same local environment in terms of density could either be in the core of a group or the wings of a cluster, which are two different environments in terms of relative velocity and gas density.

However, some properties of galaxies in rich environments do appear to be different to field samples. For example, the [OII] λ 3727 equivalent-width (EW) distribution between field and cluster galaxies are different (Balogh et al. 1999, Martin et al. 2000), while the $H\alpha$ EW distribution between low and high density environments is barely distinguishable (Balogh et al. 2004). The morphology of galaxies in rich environments often display truncated sizes, concentrated star formation, and smoother profiles (Caldwell et al. 1993, Moss & Whittle 1993, McIntosh, Rix, & Caldwell 2004, Koopman & Kenney 2004, Moss & Whittle 2005), and cluster galaxies often are deficient in HI (Giovanelli and Haynes 1985, Solanes et al. 2001).

Substantial evidence for the evolution of cluster populations is provided by the evolution of the fraction of the total cluster population with strong [OII] λ 3727 emission. The [OII] λ 3727 fraction increases with redshift, but remains below the field value at $z = 1$ (Nakata et al. 2005). The distribution of [OII] fraction with environment changes between intermediate redshifts and today (Poggianti et al. 2006) with fewer emission-line galaxies found in lower-mass structures at lower redshift. As such, the fraction of [OII] galaxies in structures with $\sigma_v > 500$ km/s is less than 20% today, whereas fractions that low are only found in the most massive structures at large redshift.

Recent observations of cluster total star formation rates (SFR) and the fraction of [OII] λ 3727 emission-line galaxies provide evidence for redshift evolution in intermediate redshift clusters ($0.2 < z < 1$). These star formation rates have been measured via narrow-band imaging (Balogh & Morris 2000, Finn et al. 2003, Kodama et al. 2004, Finn et al. 2005) and spectroscopy (Couch et al. 2001, Balogh et al. 2002, Homeier et al. 2005). The sample of intermediate-redshift clusters with measured total star formation rates still remains small, but within this sample, correlations are observed with other cluster properties, such as dynamical mass, X-ray temperature, and X-ray luminosity (Finn et al. 2005, Homeier et al. 2005). However, investigation of a large sample of local clusters reveal no correlations with mass (Goto 2005), so it is important to confirm the trends seen at intermediate redshifts through the investigation of a larger sample.

Further evidence for the evolution of cluster galaxies is provided by the changing mix of galaxy spectral and morphological types. For example, a fraction of the galaxies found in intermediate redshift clusters ($0.3 < z < 0.5$) exhibit blue colors without any emission lines (Dressler & Gunn

1982, Dressler et al. 1999); these post starburst galaxies require a small starburst with an abrupt extinction of the star formation to explain their spectral features (Barger et al. 1997). The centrally concentrated starburst in the progenitor galaxies may be optically obscured (Poggianti et al 1999, Smail et al. 1999). Another example of the changing properties of star forming galaxies is the large number of merging galaxies seen in high redshift clusters (van Dokkum et al. 1999), as compared to the relatively smooth profiles and unperturbed morphologies seen at lower redshifts (McIntosh et al. 2004).

Many explanations have been put forth for the build-up of early type galaxies and the decrease in star formation in higher density regions including ram-pressure stripping (Gunn & Gott 1972), starvation (Larson, Tinsley & Caldwell 1980), harassment (Moore et al. 1996), tidal effects (Merritt 1983), or mergers (Lavery & Henry 1994). Ram-pressure stripping occurs in the highest density regions of clusters (Fujita et al. 1999), efficiently removing the gas in a time scales as low as ~ 50 Myrs (Quilis, Moore, & Bower 2000). Starvation provides a gentle process for transforming galaxies into late type galaxies over a long time scale and at low densities (Bekki et al. 2002) by removing the cold gas reservoir from which a galaxy draws fuel to drive star formation; possible explaining the similarity in the morphology-density relationship over different densities in different environments (Abraham et al. 1996, Balogh et al. 1999, Treu et al. 2003). High speed interactions can rip mass from a galaxy, especially low surface brightness or low mass galaxies, and transform it into an S0 or dwarf elliptical, usually within a few Gyrs (Moore et al. 1999). Tidal truncations by the cluster potential would occur over similar time scales as galaxy harassment (Treu et al. 2003). Finally, major merger events are expected to quickly transform spiral galaxies into ellipticals, with any evidence of the original progenitors fading after in less than a Gyr (Mihos 1995).

The developing meme on galaxy formation is that pre-processing and mergers play a dominate role in the formation of the density relations. Mergers and interactions accelerate the star formation in close pairs (Barton et al. 2000), and by the time the galaxies have joined a group, they have already processed most of their gas. Any further evolution is driven by the interactions in the group or the edges of galaxy clusters, since merging is unlikely to occur within the high velocity structures of the clusters (Zabludoff & Muchaey 1998). The pre-processing of material accounts for the consistency

of the density relationships with environment if structures grow through hierarchical merger as all galaxies, at some point, would have been in a low density environment that encourages galaxy merging (Balogh et al. 2004). Combined with λ CDM models where the most massive halos form earliest akin to the “downsizing” predicted by Cowie et al. (1996), this theory is able to reproduce the observed distribution of the fraction of [OII] λ 3727 emission line galaxies at intermediate redshifts and today (Poggianti et al. 2006).

Many of these process may also induce star formation at the same time. Pressure from the Inter-cluster medium (ICM) can induce star formation along the rim of a disk galaxy (Dressler & Gunn 1983, Fujita & Nagashima 1998). Tidal forces from the cluster or other galaxies can force gas into the center of the galaxy inducing a centrally concentrated starburst (Byrd & Valtonen 1990), while starbursts are often seen in the mergers of gas rich galaxies providing a mechanism to transform spirals into S0 galaxies (Bekki et al. 1998). The induction of star formation or AGN activity in cluster galaxies may exacerbate the rapid transformation observed in cluster as the increase in gas ejection through galactic winds, supernovae, or jets will quickly remove any gas not being removed by other processes (Combes 2003), although some of the gas may remained trapped or induce further star formation in small clumps due to the ICM pressure (Murakami & Babul 1999).

When clusters merge, many of these process are expected to be enhanced. The time varying tidal forces as the clusters merge can increase the star formation more than a factor of five, and quickly burn through the majority of gas in the galaxy (Bekki 1999). The increased density of objects in the outer regions of the cluster can increase the probability of a major merger event or galaxy harassment. As a lower mass cluster enters a more massive halo, a bow shock may form offering momentary protection for the sub-clusters population (Roettiger, Burns, and Loken 1996) and increasing the blue fraction of the more massive cluster as it moves toward the center (Fujita & Nagashima 1999). The sub-cluster galaxies will pass through this shock as it nears the center, and the galaxies will experience a dramatic increase in pressure that is likely to initiate a starburst while rapidly removing all of the galaxy’s gas (Dressler & Gunn 1983, Roettiger et al. 1996).

The observed effects of merging clusters have provided some clues to the variation in cluster properties. Many of the clusters with the highest blue fractions are also undergoing massive mergers

(Owen et al. 1999, Owen et al. 2005, Tran et al. 2005a), and virialization has been invoked to explain the different populations seen at $z \sim 0.3$ (Couch et al. 1998). A851, a massive cluster at $z = 0.41$, has more [OII] $\lambda 3727$ emission line galaxies than MS1512, a cluster at similar redshift, due to the massive merger it is currently undergoing (Lotz et al. 2003). Since 20% of clusters are expected to have undergone a massive merger in the last 2.5 Gyrs (Cole & Lacey 1993), quantifying the effects of merging clusters provides key insight into the evolution of cluster populations.

In this paper, we present the measurements of the total star formation from narrow-band rest-frame [OII] $\lambda 3727$ imaging of five intermediate redshift clusters. The [OII] $\lambda 3727$ measurements provide an estimate of the un-obscured SFR for the cluster galaxies. This will allow us to explore a complete sample of star forming galaxies over a redshift range still relatively unexplored as compared to the nearby Universe. In this work, we will primarily focus on the number and distribution of star forming galaxies to see if low redshift relationships with density and environment remain consistent at higher redshifts. We will also explore different cluster properties to see if they do show any correlation with cluster properties at these redshifts by comparing our sample with previous measurements. The paper is organized as follows. In §4.2, we present a description of our observations, basic data reductions and initial data analysis. In §4.3, we present the techniques used to measure and identify cluster emission line objects. The luminosity function and fraction of emission line galaxies is presented in §4.4, followed by the distribution of star forming galaxies in the cluster and the comparison of the total star formation rate from the cluster to different cluster properties. The cluster sample is described in Chapter 1, and the broad band observations and data reduction are described in Chapter 2. Finally, we discuss some of the implications of our observations. Throughout this work, we assume the standard cosmology of $\Omega_0 = 0.3$, $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$, and $H_0 = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. For comparison to other Hubble constants, $SFR \propto h_{70}^{-2}$.

4.2 Narrow-Band Observations

Narrow-band observations sampling rest-frame [OII] $\lambda 3727$ in each of the six clusters were obtained at the WIYN² 3.5m telescope with the Mini-Mosaic camera from Sept 2004-June 2005.

²The WIYN Observatory is a joint facility of the University of Wisconsin-Madison, Indiana University, Yale University, and the National Optical Astronomy Observatories.

Mini-Mo is constructed from two 4096×2048 Site CCDs, has a scale of $0.14''$ per pixel, and has a $9.6' \times 9.6'$ field of view.

Custom narrow band filters that sample the [OII] λ 3727 line at the rest-frame of each cluster were designed to detect [OII] λ 3727 emission line from sources within $\pm 1.7\sigma_v$ of the cluster redshift, where σ_v is the velocity dispersion of the cluster. We contracted with Omega Optical³ for manufacture of these filters. The filters have resolutions of $\lambda/\Delta\lambda \sim 70$; further details are presented in Appendix 4.9. Each cluster was observed with its narrow-band filter and one narrow off-band filter, which sampled the continuum near the redshifted line. For the higher redshift clusters, the closest custom narrow-band filter was used as our off-band filter; for CL0016 and MS0451, the Kitt Peak filter, KP1528 with a resolution of $\lambda/\Delta\lambda \sim 20$, was used as the off-band filter. The response curves (transmission of the filters convolved with the CCD response) for the narrow band filters and the broad band curves are presented in Figure 4.1.

We developed a pipeline for the reduction of Mini-Mo data that includes standard reduction techniques and processes unique to deep imaging data with Mini-Mo. These reductions include IDL routines to account for a striated overscan and bias region and to mask ghosts caused by cross-talk between the amplifiers (A. Saha, private communication), standard IRAF⁴ MSCRED algorithms for bias and flatfield reductions, and fringe and sky subtraction software, designed specifically for use in deep images taken with Mini-Mo. In the narrow-band images, the saturated stars have a large halo associated with them. In the flattened images, we azimuthally averaged the halo and subtracted it from the images. Once reductions were complete, the Mini-Mo images were flat to within 1% of their initial sky values. Some artifacts from the sky/fringe subtraction may remain, but the effect of these artifacts were small in the narrow-band images. Nonetheless, the artifacts are masked along with the ghosts from cross-talk and cosmetic defects on the CCDs.

Images from photometric nights were combined into deep mosaics. Each image was transformed onto a standard frame using more than 100 stars to calculate the transformations. Masks for each image were made to account for cosmic rays, transient objects, artifacts from the reduction, ghosts,

³Omega Optical, INC.; 210 Main St., Brattleboro, VT, 05301

⁴IRAF is distributed by the National Optical Astronomy Observatories, which are operated by the Association of Universities for Research in Astronomy, Inc., under cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation.

and cosmetic detects. The mosaics are a weighted average of the data, where the weight is calculated from the ratio of the flux from an average star to the square root of the sky deviation and seeing for that image (Bershady, Lowenthal, & Koo 1998). Astrometric solutions were calculated for each mosaic frame based on the USNO A2 catalog (Monet et al. 1998).

The narrow-band data were calibrated from Massey et al. (1988) spectrophotometric stars observed during each night. Standard magnitudes were calculated by convolving our filter set with the spectra of the standard stars. Solutions for each night were calculated and then applied to the target data. The uncertainty in the calibration of the narrow-band data is approximately 0.03 for any night and verified through comparing calibrations from two different runs. All magnitudes are on the Vega system.

4.2.1 Data Analysis

Object detection was accomplished with SExtractor (Bertin & Arnouts 1998) with detection parameters set to optimize the detection of objects while minimizing any contamination. For each target, detection was performed on the on-band image, off-band image, and an image that is the sum of the broad bands. Completeness was determined in all images through Monte-Carlo simulations by reinserting objects into the image, and Figure 4.2 displays the completeness in each of our on-band images.

For the purposes of photometry, we degraded the seeing in all images to match that in the worse band for that cluster. The worse seeing that our images were degraded to was $1''$. For all sources, we measured the photometry using fixed and tailored apertures. We compute the total magnitude based on the measurement of the Petrosian Radius (Petrosian 1976) and the concentration index, C_{2080} (Bershady, Jangren, & Conselice al. 2000). From this total magnitude, we also determine a half-light radius for the galaxy based on the curve of growth of the light profile. For each galaxy, we also measured the magnitude within two fixed aperture. The size of the first aperture is set to maximize the signal to noise ratio from a galaxy with an 8 kpc half-light radius at the redshift of the cluster. The second aperture includes 98% of the light from that galaxy. The size is set for the upper limit on the size distribution for galaxies at our redshifts (Simard et al. 1999). By using fixed apertures, we minimize the contamination from other objects and the sky background that can

affect tailored apertures. The advantages of the two apertures will be explained in the next section. Individual stars were identified through their half-light radius in all of the images and the colors of the individual objects. If an object was unresolved in all frames and well-fit along the Gunn & Styrker (1982) stellar locus, it was flagged in the catalog for latter exclusion in tertiary analysis.

4.3 Emission-Line Flux Measurements

To determine the strength of an emission line from narrow-band imaging requires the subtraction of the continuum flux from the observed flux. Narrow-band studies of galaxy clusters have used three techniques to estimate the continuum over the wavelength range of the narrow-band filter:

- Method 1. The continuum is estimated from a broad band filter near or covering the narrow-band filter (Iglesias-Páramo et al 2002, Finn et al. 2004, Kodama et al. 2004, Finn et al. 2005);
- Method 2. The continuum flux at the line is determined by interpolating between two broad band filters (Umeda et al. 2004);
- Method 3. A narrow-band with a small offset from the on-band filter provides a measurement for the continuum (Martin et al. 2000, Lotz et al. 2003).

The first two methods have primarily been used in $H\alpha$ studies, whereas the latter has been used in $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ studies as well. However, significant deficiencies exist for each of these methods in measuring the continuum level at $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$. To illustrate this, in Figure 4.3 we present normalized spectral energy distributions (SEDs) for model stellar populations near the $H\alpha$ and $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ spectral regions. The models presented here, and used throughout this paper, were created using the GALEV program (Bruzual & Charlot 2003; hereafter BC03) and represent a range of star formation histories, ages, metallicities, and internal extinction. The behavior of the SEDs near the $H\alpha$ line allow an accurate measurement of the continuum level from broad band filters, but the complexity near $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ prevents a simple estimate of the continuum. As an aside, we note that this is an argument in favor of pursuing $H\alpha$ into the near-infrared with suitably-developed instrumentation.

As an example of the effect of the SED structure on the measurement of EW, the $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ equivalent width (EW) measured for a subset of our extinction-free and nebular-free stellar-population

models (i.e., no emission-lines) are presented via the off-band filter method in Figure 4.4. If the off-band method (3) were a perfect estimate of the continuum level, the EW for all these models would be zero. Estimates from a single broad band filter (Method 1) suffer from similar, and indeed worse, problems, whereas the error associated with two broad bands (Method 2) can be an improvement compared to Method 1 depending on the correction and broad bands. However, we have developed a superior algorithm which ameliorates much of the difficulties found with the above methods:

- Method 4. The strength of the continuum is estimated from fits to the observed multi-band spectral energy distributions (SEDs) using higher-resolution models and observed SED templates. This technique is similar to what has been done in narrow-band surveys in the field (Hippelein et al. 2003, Wolf et al. 2003). In essence, this method is a more sophisticated rendering of Method 2.

To account for the shape of the SED at [OII] λ 3727, we determine the best model SED by fitting the UBRIZ and off-band photometry from the normalized χ^2 distribution:

$$\chi^2/\nu = \frac{1}{\nu} \sum \frac{(f_i^{obs} - n \times f_i)^2}{w_i^2}. \quad (4.1)$$

In this equation, f_i^{obs} is the observed flux in the i th filter, f_i is the model flux of the template at the cluster redshift, ν represents the degrees of freedom (here the number of filters, $\nu = 6$, as we exclude the on-band filter from the fit), w_i is a weighting function, and n is the normalization of the model. The normalization is calculated to minimize the χ^2 for any given fit for each weighting scheme. The first scheme sets w_i to the flux error in the i^{th} filter. The second scheme emphasizes the contribution of the filters closest to the on-band filter such that w_i is the flux error normalized by the absolute difference between the central wavelength of the i th filter and the on-band filter. This weighting assures the model will be normalized to the continuum near the on-band filter and reduces catastrophic errors that occur due to poor fits. Three cluster galaxies are provided in Figure 4.5 as examples of the fitting process.

Production of an accurate estimate of the continuum depends on two factors: estimate the level of the continuum and account for any spectral features which may overlap with the on-band filter. For the first factor, the physicality of the fit is irrelevant—only the level of the continuum matters. The

distance weighting method assures that the continuum estimate is not adversely affected by bands that may have small photometric errors, but produce unrealistic normalizations for the model SEDs near the wavelength of the on-band filter. This may occur for objects not actually at the redshift of the cluster, objects with SEDs not well-matched by our template set, or objects with poor photometry in one or more bands. In our simulations, we found the level of the continuum far more important than accounting for underlying spectral features in measuring accurate photometry. However, by including the other bands in the fits, the accuracy in identifying the true stellar distribution underlying the observed SED is improved, and this leads to a more refined continuum estimate. When discussing the quality of any fits, we will primarily refer to the reduced χ^2 value determined from the error-only method, which produces a more physically reasonable description of the observed SED due to the broad wavelength coverage.

Once the best fit model SED is determined, we convolve the normalized model SED with the response of our on-band filter to produce the continuum flux estimate, f_c . To find the line flux, f_l , we subtract f_c from the observed flux in the on-band, f_{on} , to give:

$$f_l = \Delta_{FWHM}(f_{on} - f_c), \quad (4.2)$$

where Δ_{FWHM} (\AA) is the width of the on-band filter. In this equation, the units of f_{on} and f_c are given as $\text{ergs s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{\AA}$, and the units of f_l are $\text{ergs s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The error on f_l includes the error from the observed on-band flux and the error in determining the normalization of the model. For each object, we also compute a rest-frame equivalent width

$$EW = \frac{f_l/f_c}{1 + z_c}, \quad (4.3)$$

where z_c is the cluster redshift.

In Figure 4.6, we present the measurement of EW for a number of observed template spectra (Kinney et al 1997) and model spectra with added emission lines. The emission lines were added to the spectra to simulate a range of EW and were not physically motivated by the underlying stellar SED. For example, we added strong emission lines to old stellar populations which would not necessarily have any means of producing them, but allows us to test the methods under the full range of apparent parameter space. Obviously, the performance of the different methods are more

important for young stellar populations and/or small EW which are closer to reality. Each template was redshifted to the observed wavelength of [OII] λ 3727 for each custom narrow-band filter, and then the redshifted spectra were convolved with the full filter set. Using methods (1)-(4), we measured the EW for each model SED. The SED fitting method (4) out-performs the all methods in both accuracy and precision. The random and systematic errors for method (3) and (4) are presented in Table 4.2. Method 4 also does not have any systematic offset with color, a weakness of the off-band method (3). Furthermore, Monte-Carlo simulations of the SED fitting method (4) at different signal-to-noise (S/N) levels imply this method can reliably measure the EW down to small S/N defined by the R-band magnitude at the half-light radius as shown in Figure 4.7 for cluster sources.

As a final demonstration of the accuracy of our Method 4, we plot the photometric EW vs. the spectroscopic EW in Figures 4.8 (Method 4) and 4.9 (Method 3). The dispersion in this measurement is $\sigma = 17\text{\AA}$, with a systematic offset of $\delta = 0.1\text{\AA}$ for all objects. For objects with spectroscopic $EW > 10$, $\sigma = 29.5\text{\AA}$ and $\delta = 10.5$. After excluding 3σ outliers for the same ranges of EW, respectively, we find $\sigma = 8.65, 11.2\text{\AA}$ and $\delta = -2.1, 1.7$. Using the continuum method (3) measurement for the same objects, we find dispersions of $\sigma = 21, 35\text{\AA}$ and offsets of $\delta = -3, 7\text{\AA}$ for all objects and only objects with $EW > 10$, while we find values of $\sigma = 15, 35\text{\AA}$ and offsets of $\delta = -4, 7\text{\AA}$ once removing 3σ outliers.

4.3.1 Selection of Cluster Objects

Bona fide cluster emission-line sources are identified by requiring a significant detection of the line flux, but depending on the underlying shape of the SED, sources at number of different redshifts may have significant detections regardless of how the line flux is determined. Because we initially assume all objects are at the cluster redshift for the purpose of SED fitting, many objects that are not at the redshift and are not legitimate emission line objects will have detected emission lines due to poor fits of the templates. As can be seen in Figure 4.10 through Figure 4.15, significant detections of apparently-positive EW can occur at a range of redshifts for any of our filters sets via our method. Besides the other obvious emission lines such as $H\alpha$ and [OIII] λ 5007 at lower redshifts and Lyman- α at higher redshifts, a number of other spectral features may appear as emission.

To identify cluster emission line galaxy, we calculate the probability that an individual galaxy

is in the galaxy cluster. We define this probability as a product of 7 probability distributions:

$$P = P(k)P(\chi^2)P(z)P(color)P(Ly\alpha)P(M_B)P(*). \quad (4.4)$$

The first four terms are $P(k)$, the significance of the detection in the on-band; $P(\chi^2)$, the quality of the SED fit; $P(z)$, the probability from photometric redshifts the object is in the cluster; and $P(color)$ involves different color cuts. We discuss each of these in more detail below. The last three terms have binary distribution functions, as follows.

$P(Ly\alpha)$ is the probability the emission is from either Lyman- α or Lyman break by requiring a 3σ measurement of the flux above the background level in the bands bluer than the on-band. $P(M_B)$ limits the absolute magnitude of the object to reasonable values (i.e. $M_B > -25$ based on the redshift of the cluster). Finally, $P(*)$ removes any stellar objects by examining their size and color.

4.3.1.1 $P(k)$

For all sources with spectroscopic redshifts (Ellingson et al. 1998, Postman et al. 1998, Dressler et al. 1999, van Dokkum et al. 1999), we plot k , the ratio of the emission line flux to its error, as a function of observed R-band magnitude, B-R color, and EW for the SED-fitting method and the off-band filter method in Figure 4.16. Cluster sources are identified by filled symbols, and as can be seen, both methods have significant non-cluster detections. As a first pass though, the requirement of a significant detection reduces the number of possible candidates. For a conservative estimate of cluster emission-line candidacy, we require the galaxy have $k > 3$ (i.e. $P(k)=1$ when $k \geq 3$).

As described in 4.2.1, the significance of the detection is calculated using the smaller fixed aperture. At this aperture, the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) for a galaxy at the redshift of the cluster with an 8 kpc radius is maximized (see Figure 4.17). A larger aperture will have smaller significance due to the inclusion of sky noise, whereas a smaller aperture will go undetected due to the smaller amount of flux. For galaxies at these redshifts, this aperture size ($r \sim 1''$) is also comparable to the slit size typically used in the spectroscopic observations. However, the total SFR from these galaxies will be underestimated due to the exclusion of flux in the outer wings of these galaxies. For large galaxies, this can be up to a factor of 2. For this reason, we use the larger fixed aperture for the measurement of emission line flux for these galaxies.

4.3.1.2 $P(\chi^2)$

The normalized χ^2 distribution for the error-only weighted fit does have a distribution around 1 for cluster objects with spectroscopic redshifts. Objects with poor fits are far less likely to be cluster objects or emission-line star-forming galaxies. As such, we calculate the probability of the fit, $P(\chi^2)$, to apply to each object. Since we do not include quasar or other AGN templates in our models, cluster AGN are typically removed at this stage although we will further discuss their contamination in §4.3.3. This step, along with the redshift probability removes a large number of non-cluster objects.

4.3.1.3 $P(z)$

We calculate the probability that an object is in the cluster from our photometric redshifts. For each object, we have calculated photometric redshifts using all of our filters via a hybrid of the template and training set method similar to Csaibai et al. (2003). The random errors associated with this process are $\sigma = 0.03$ for red galaxies and $\sigma = 0.05$ for blue galaxies with $S/N > 10$. Then, we calculate the probability of an object being a cluster member following the prescription of Brunner and Lubin (2000). The redshift of each object is recalculated 100 times after applying the observed error distribution to its photometry. The probability of being in the cluster, $P(z)$, is then the number of times the absolute difference between the calculated photometric redshift and cluster redshift is less than the 1σ photometric redshift error.

4.3.1.4 $P(\text{color})$

After the fitting and photometric redshift cuts, we apply color cuts to cull the data of any remaining contamination seen in the spectroscopic sample. We present the color distribution as a function of redshift for a number of observed models for all our filter combinations in Figures 4.18 and 4.19. The primary requirement is that the observed on-band flux be above the continuum flux. For example, in CL1604, that requires $O5 - O6 > 0.15$. On each figure, we plot the color limitation imposed on the data. The color limitation is calculated based on the stellar SED template models and the observed colors of the spectroscopic sample. To further cull the sample, we also excluded galaxies with $(B - V)_o > 0.7$, which is discussed below.

4.3.1.5 Discussion

Calculations of the probability distributions were tuned through examination of the spectroscopic sample. For each source with a spectroscopic redshift, we calculated the probability of being a cluster emission-line galaxy. The spectroscopic information for any one source was not used in measuring its photometric redshift or template fit—mimicking the measurement for a typical galaxy. The color limitation was refined to exclude any contamination that was not removed by this point through the examination of the spectroscopic sample. Finally, the probability for cluster membership was set based on the spectroscopic sample for each field. In all fields, we found a final $P > 0.1$ indicated a good likelihood of being a bona fide cluster emission-line galaxy.

Although our method produce accurate EW for cluster objects regardless of galaxy color, the majority of our remaining interlopers are red galaxies. One reason for this is that the spectra of a quiescent population will have features that may show up in the on- or off-band when the redshift is shifted slightly ($\Delta z < 0.1$) from the cluster redshift. These data will still have acceptable fits and appropriate photometric redshifts, but the significant detection will not be due to $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ but another spectral feature. We require galaxies to have rest-frame $B - V < 0.7$ in order to be identified as star-forming cluster galaxies. With this requirement, we reduce the total number of identified emission-line galaxies up to $\sim 25\%$. Moran et al. (2005) estimate 10% of the red galaxies in Cl0024 have emission lines within the inner 1 Mpc, and so we could be missing a population of red galaxies with low levels of star formation.

The application of the full set of probabilities minimizes the detection of spurious sources. In Figure 4.20, we show the redshift distribution for all spectroscopically confirmed galaxies, for objects with a significant detection ($k > 3$), all likely emission line candidates including red galaxies, and our most conservative selection of objects. Of the sample with spectroscopic equivalent widths, we identify 22 of the 24 cluster sources with emission, but out of a sample of 69 identified cluster objects with spectroscopic measurements, we detect 8 sources not at the cluster redshift. Most of these sources have photometric redshifts that are, within error, at the cluster redshift.

4.3.2 Equivalent Width Completeness

Due to our method for calculating the EW and identifying cluster emission-line objects, calculating a completeness limit for the EW is a complex task. Empirically, the completeness limit depends on the signal to noise of the measurement, the quality of the redshift measurement, and the color of the source. As a reminder, our method involves identification and measurement using apertures of different sizes. Fundamentally, the equivalent width only depends on the ratio of current star formation ([OII] λ 3727 line flux) to past star formation (continuum level). However, this simple interpretation is complicated by a number of different factors (especial at [OII] λ 3727) including, but not limited to: the star formation history, the strength of the star formation, the obscuration of the star forming population and the [OII] λ 3727 line, the metallicity of the gas and underlying continuum, and the spatial distribution of the star formation.

While trying to consider all these different factors but not necessarily accounting for them, we express an estimate for the completeness limit for the EW as a function of redshift based on our photometric errors. For four different absolute B-magnitudes (-20.5 -19.5 -18.5 , and -16), we estimate the lowest EW we could detect based on the photometric error in the corresponding apparent magnitudes via the equation:

$$EW = \frac{k\sigma_l}{f_c(1+z_c)}. \quad (4.5)$$

We set $k = 3$, and σ_l is a function of the on-band error, the continuum error, and the width of the filter. Rest-frame magnitudes are converted to apparent magnitudes by assuming the galaxies have an SED similar to NGC 4449. The calculations indicate, as can be seen in Figure 4.21 that at the brightest magnitude we are complete to $EW = 5 \text{ \AA}$, but at $M_B = -18.5$, we are incomplete in the highest redshift clusters for sources with $EW < 14 \text{ \AA}$.

4.3.3 Contamination

Despite our selection requirements, we may still expect some contamination from objects not in the cluster. Primarily, we expect to detect emission line from $H\alpha$, [OII] λ 5007, $H\beta$, and $Ly\alpha$ and different spectral features such as the 4000\AA break and Lyman break over a range of redshifts depending on the filter set. In Table 4.3, we list the number of galaxies we expect to detect from

these different emission line features at different redshifts to the limits of our data. We also list the number of galaxies we identify in our fields as possible candidates. Compared to the large number of emission-line sources that we do find, the expected contribution from non-cluster emission-line sources is relatively small ($< 10\%$) due to our cleaning.

In CL1604, we have 11 objects with significant on-band detection with no significant flux in the U- or B-bands. In addition, these objects have I-z colors appropriate for Lyman α galaxies at a redshift of $z \sim 4.82$. From the deep narrow-band studies of Hu et al. (1998) and Rhoads et al. (2000), we estimate that we should detect between 3-7 Lyman α galaxies. Our results are consistent with these previous measurements and await spectroscopic follow-up for confirmation. The number densities of Lyman α galaxies are highly sensitive to their clustering. Lensing by the cluster could also amplify the magnitudes of these background sources as well (Lotz et al. 2003). Therefore the high number of possible Lyman α galaxies we detect is not inconsistent with previous measurements.

Another source of contamination to the star forming cluster galaxies are AGN. In the literature, we have only found 3 quasars at the redshifts of our clusters and have removed these from the sample (all three are detected as emission line sources, but poor spectra fits already removed all three). We reserve the full cross-correlation of our sample with the X-ray sample for future work, but for objects with redshifts from the CHAMPS sample (Silverman et al. 2005), we do not detect any of the hard X-ray sources either due to poor χ^2 fits (since we do not include any AGN templates), red colors, or absorption spectra. For example, most of the radio sources seen in Best et al. (2002) are rejected due to their red colors. Nonetheless, recent observations by Martini et al. (2006) indicate a significant fraction of AGN in galaxy clusters—up to 5% in some clusters from X-ray identification. However, optical spectroscopy indicated only 11% of the AGN had optical signatures, which is in line with the AGN contamination estimate by Homeier et al. (2005) for Cl0152 at $z = 0.83$. For these reasons, we do not remove any other objects as AGN. Further spectroscopic investigations will have to determine if this assumption was appropriate.

4.4 The [OII] Luminosity Function in Galaxy Clusters

For each cluster, the [OII] luminosity function for galaxies within R_{200} is presented in Figure 4.22. We define R_{200} following Finn et al. (2004):

$$R_{200} = 1.73 \frac{\sigma_v}{1000 \text{ km s}^{-1}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\Omega_\lambda + \Omega_o(1+z)^3}} h_{100}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}. \quad (4.6)$$

For objects that satisfy our probability limits on being an [OII] λ 3727 cluster galaxy, we convert the observed line flux into the [OII] luminosity by assuming the object is at the redshift of the cluster and according to our assumed cosmology. We construct the luminosity function by summing the number of emission line galaxies as a function of [OII] λ 3727 luminosity within R_{200} for each cluster and normalizing by the volume sampled by the narrow-band filter. We also apply two corrections to the data: (1) We correct for incompleteness in the on-band filter as calculated in §4.2.1, and (2) we correct for the probability of detecting the line flux. The second correction is estimated from Monte Carlo simulations of the continuum and line flux measurements based on the observed magnitudes errors. This correction is typically very small (less than 10%) since most sources are significant detections, and the correction is typically largest for bright sources with small line fluxes. Since emission line galaxies are identified in the smaller apertures, some sources will have lower SFR due to photometric errors or color gradients. These sources represent the faint tail seen in the luminosity functions, hence the turnover seen at faint luminosities is an artifact of the measurement process.

4.4.1 The $z \sim 0.55$ [OII] luminosity function

The [OII] luminosity functions for the low redshift clusters agree very well with each other, and with the luminosity function for Abell 851, a similar cluster to Cl0016 and MS0451 at $z = 0.41$, observed by Martin et al. (2000). Compared to MS1512 which is at lower redshift ($z = 0.37$) and less massive (Lotz et al. 2003), the normalization of the [OII] LF in the $z \sim 0.55$ clusters is almost a factor of ten greater. For comparison, we also show the [OII] field luminosity function from Hogg et al. (1998) measured from $0.3 < z < 1.2$ from the HDF. The normalization of the cluster luminosity function is ~ 10 times greater than the field sample, but as Martin et al. (2000) point out, the volume sampled by the filter is much greater in depth (~ 72 Mpc) than the breadth ($\sim 3 \times 3$ Mpc) of our field of view. If all the emission line galaxies are within 3 Mpc of the cluster, the normalization of

the luminosity function would be $\sim 25\times$ larger than it currently is.

The measurement of the [OII] galaxy density in the off-band at $z \sim 0.41$ for these fields is consistent with the field measurement at these redshifts. In each of our fields, the off-band flux is measured in exactly the same way as the on-band, except assuming the emission is in the off-band. We repeat the process of fitting the SED, except now excluding the off-band from the fit instead of the on-band. The [OII] LF is calculated in the same way, but with the completeness correction based on the off-band data. In most cases, the off-band data is not as deep as the on-band data. For the low redshift clusters, the off-band filter (KP1582) is wider than the on-band filters and samples a larger volume. In the plots, the completeness corrected off-band data are plotted as lines for the purpose of clarity.

4.4.2 The [OII] Luminosity Function at $z > 0.70$

The higher redshift clusters also have a greater number of star forming galaxies than the field. All three clusters have similar distributions, and their normalizations are well above the field value as well. Deeper imaging is required to determine if there is any turnover in the luminosity function as our data become incomplete at these low luminosities. The off-band sample is similar to the field represented by the luminosity function from Hogg et al. (1998), which is measured over $0.3 < z < 1.2$, and Hippelein et al. (2003), which is measured over $0.87 < z < 0.89$. The one exception is the off-band imaging of C11604, which appears similar to the cluster samples. Large scale structure around this cluster, identified and described as a sheet by Oke et al. (1998), is expected to fall into our off-band; it is likely we are measuring an over-density associated with this structure.

4.5 Fraction of OII Emission Line Galaxies

The fraction of cluster emission-line galaxies to the total number of cluster galaxies, f_{oii} , is an important constraint on the evolution of galaxies with environment. Two recent surveys reported measurements of f_{oii} across a range of cluster redshift and environment, but with two very different selections for emission line galaxies. Nakata et al. (2005) identified strong emission line galaxies ($EW > 10\text{\AA}$) within the cores ($R < 0.7$ Mpc) of predominately rich clusters. Poggianti et al. (2006) had a much lower EW limit ($EW > 3\text{\AA}$) and included all galaxies within R_{200} . Both studies

relied on spectroscopic data and have bright magnitude limits ($M_B < -19.5$ for Nakata et al. and $M_V < -20.1, -20.5$ for the low and high redshift sample for Poggianti et al.).

In Table 4.4, we present f_{oii} calculated for each cluster according to the definitions of Nakata et al. (2005) and Poggianti et al. (2006). To the limits of Nakata et al. (2005), we are complete in terms of both magnitudes and EW for our full cluster sample of galaxies. However, we do not reach the low EW limits of Poggianti et al. (2006) for any of our clusters. Converting their magnitude limits to the B-band assuming the colors of an irregular galaxy (Fukugita et al. 1995), our data are complete to $EW \sim 5 - 7 \text{ \AA}$ at their magnitude limits. We report the fraction calculated to our completeness, but as can be seen, our values are slightly underestimated as compared to Poggianti et al. (2006). Examination of the spectroscopic data set reveal that the difference is primarily due to the higher EW completeness limit of our data. For the calculation of the emission line fractions under either definition, we require the emission-line galaxies to have blue colors, which further lowers the fraction that we will find compared to the spectroscopic samples which included red galaxies with emission lines.

In Figure 4.23, we plot f_{oii} as a function of cluster radius for each cluster. The fraction of emission line galaxies is calculated by following the Nakata et al. (2005) definition: the galaxy is required to have $M_B < -19.5$ and $EW > 10 \text{ \AA}$. In addition, we also plot the blue fraction, f_b . We adopt the Butcher & Oemler (1984) definition that f_b is the ratio of blue galaxies (galaxies 0.2 mag bluer than the red sequence in the rest-frame B-V color-magnitude relationship for the cluster) to the total population brighter than $M_B < -19.5$. The slope of the red sequence is calculated for each cluster, accounting for color evolution in the passive population between redshifts. To calculate the total number of galaxies and the number of blue galaxies, objects are selected in our deep R-band images to prevent selection effects due to red galaxies being undetected in the narrow-band images in the highest redshift clusters.

Biviano et al. (1997) emphasize the importance of accounting for the morphological mix of galaxies in the cluster. In particular, they find no difference in the fraction of emission line objects between field and cluster environments as a function of morphological type in the local Universe. We do not have morphological data for our entire sample, but can quantify the fraction of blue cluster

galaxies with emission lines, $f_{b:OII}$. Colors are not a perfect match for morphology, as some late-type galaxies will have blue colors especially at these redshifts (Koo et al. 2005), but we only compare the fraction to field samples calculated in a similar manner. The solid line in Figure 4.23 represents the fraction of blue galaxies with observed $[OII]\lambda 3727$ emission.

We have not corrected the sample for any contamination. For each of three different cluster populations (red galaxies, blue emission-line galaxies, and blue galaxies without emission lines), we have very different errors in the photometric redshifts ($\sigma_z = 0.03, 0.02, 0.06$). While we nominally select all sources from the same volume, the contamination will come effectively from three different volumes, increasing with photometric redshift error. Likewise, we will miss more true cluster galaxies for those populations with the largest photometric errors. Hence completeness and reliability are not the same across these sub-samples.

To quantify the reliability of the fractions, f_{oii} , f_b , and $f_{oii:b}$, we simulated the distribution for two representative clusters, one at $z = 0.55$ and one at $z = 0.90$, mixed with a realistic field distribution estimated from observed luminosity functions from 2DF (Madgwick et al. 2002), DEEP2 (Faber et al. 2005), and Lyman-Break surveys (Shapley et al. 2001). We populated the clusters using the luminosity function for Coma (Trentham 1998), with a range of normalizations. Field galaxies were distributed randomly, red cluster galaxies were distributed with a King profile (King 1972) with the core radius set by the X-ray distribution, and blue cluster galaxies were distributed by a King profile with $R = 1Mpc$ as observed by Crawford et al. (2006). We also assumed different blue and $[OII]\lambda 3727$ fractions for the cluster. We then applied the observed photometric error to the different cluster populations, and re-applied our selection. For the richest clusters (MS0451, CL0016, MS1054), the amount of contamination is small relative to the number of cluster galaxies and the fractions do not suffer much deviation ($< 10\%$). In all cases, the initial trend implanted in the data was reproduced in the simulations even for the worse errors. At high redshift, poorer clusters suffer more due to the rising population of blue galaxies in the field, the weaker “signal” due to fewer cluster galaxies, and the larger errors in photometric redshifts due to fainter magnitude limits. We are still able to reproduce the original trends, but the blue $[OII]\lambda 3727$ fraction may be underestimated by 25%. The presence of large scale structure within $\Delta z \sim 0.1$, as for both Cl1322 and CL1604, also

contributes to the overestimation of the number of blue galaxies and is difficult to quantify.

Both f_{oii} and f_b generally decrease toward the center of the cluster. This is expected due to the distribution of red galaxies, which have a much smaller scale radius than the blue galaxies. At a given radius, the lower redshift and more massive clusters have smaller fractions. In all cases, f_{oii} is less than the field value, which is expected to range from $f_{oii} = 70 - 90\%$ over the redshift range of these clusters (Nakata et al. 2005). The low redshift clusters display blue [OII] λ 3727 fractions similar to field values at $z \sim 0.5$ beyond the inner core, but at high redshifts, the fraction of blue cluster galaxies is well below the field value. At $z \sim 0.9$, nearly 100% of the blue galaxies are expected to have active star formation.

4.5.1 Star Formation in Galaxy Clusters

4.5.2 Star Formation Rates

The star formation rate for individual galaxies can be estimated from the strength of the [OII] λ 3727 emission line. For our purposes, we use the relationship of Kewley, Geller, & Jansen (2004) to estimate the SFR rate:

$$SFR(M_{\odot}yr^{-1}) = (6.58 \pm 1.65) \times 10^{-42} L([OII])(ergs^{-1}), \quad (4.7)$$

where the OII luminosity, $L([OII])$, requires a correction for the extinction at [OII] λ 3727. Previous studies have adopted extinction values around $A_{H\alpha} \sim 1.0$, which, for consistency, we also adopt here. For a Calzetti (1996) extinction curve, this implies a correction of 5.27 at [OII] λ 3727. A significant amount of scatter in the [OII]-SFR relationship involves the reddening occurring at [OII] λ 3727 (Kewley et al. 2004, Moustakis et al. 2006), and we hope to improve our measurement in the future by constraining the extinction through fits to the SED and comparisons to the flux near 2800Å, which also correlates with star formation. At the completeness limit of our data, we expect our limits to be $SFR = 0.066, 0.20 M_{\odot} yr^{-1}$ for the $z = 0.55, 0.9$ clusters, respectively.

4.5.3 Distribution of Star Forming Galaxies

We plot the average star formation rate for [OII] λ 3727 emission line galaxies and the total population as a function of density and radius in Figure 4.24. The surface-density, Σ_{10} , is computed

by finding the distances to the 10th nearest neighbor with $M_B < -18.5$ (See Chapter 2 for a full definition). The average SFR is computed in bins of 25 and 100 galaxies for the [OII] λ 3727 population and the total population for both the radius and density calculations and the typical variance in any bin in SFR is $1.8M_{\odot}yr^{-1}$.

A significant amount of variation is seen from cluster to cluster, although the average star formation in the lower redshift clusters is lower than the higher redshift clusters. The average total star formation for all objects does show evidence for being suppressed at the highest densities and smallest radii similar to spectroscopic and narrow-band results for clusters at intermediate redshift (Balogh et al. 1999, Kodoma et al. 2004) and the nearby Universe (Gomez et al. 2003), although Cl1604, both at the highest redshift and the smallest velocity dispersion in our sample, does not exhibit this behavior. Once again, we have not applied any field subtraction, but have purely relied on the cuts in photometric redshift. Due to the nature of our errors, (i) the clusters with a richer red sequence will have more accurate values of Σ_{10} and $\langle SFR \rangle$ than the high redshift, less rich clusters; and (ii) mean SFR measurements purely for the star forming population will be more accurate than the full population when considering the effects of field contamination.

None of the clusters show any trends with radius or density when averaging only the star forming galaxies. In fact, they have a very similar value as the average star formation found in our field measurements from Cl1325 and the off-band filters in the other clusters. Similar measurements in nearby environments (Balogh et al. 2004) and clusters (Kodama et al. 2004) reveal a similar pattern. However, the equivalent width distribution for our star forming galaxies is very different when compared to the field values for our sample, in agreement with previous measurements of intermediate redshift clusters (Balogh et al. 1999, Martin et al. 2000). In Figure 4.25, the cluster distribution is significantly different than the field distribution, and a K-S test eliminates the possibility they were drawn from the same parent distribution. The off-band sample, is in general, not as deep as the on-band sample and has a lower EW completeness limit, but the differences in the distribution are predominately observed at large EW where the two samples are presumable complete.

4.5.4 Total Star Formation Rate

We also calculate the total star formation rate, ΣSFR , from all star-forming galaxies within $0.5 R_{200}$ for each cluster. The mass normalized total star formation from clusters has shown evidence of correlating with cluster properties (Finn et al. 2004, Homeier et al. 2005), although previous measurements have relied on a small number of clusters. For each of our clusters, we sum the star formation from all sources within $0.5R_{200}$. For the measurement of R_{200} we use the equation 4.6 and base it on the observed velocity dispersion. This allows a comparison to previous work, but in general the value of R_{200} may be over-estimated due to substructure in the cluster in this definition. For this reason, we supply the integrated star formation rates as a function of radius in Figure 4.26. The total star formation rate does appear to vary significantly at smaller radii for these clusters, while most of the clusters agree at the largest radii.

The error estimate for the total star formation rate is based on the observed data and corrections, but does not reflect a number of factors that may increase the uncertainty including contamination, calibration error, and error associated with the estimate of R_{200} . First, we assume that all detected galaxies are associated with the cluster despite the fact that we are sampling approximately 70 Mpc around the cluster. Second, in any of the clusters, we may not be sampling far enough along the luminosity function to quantify the affects of low luminosity galaxies. If the luminosity function is well-described by a Schechter function with a faint end slope of $\alpha = -1.4$ as blue galaxies in the field are at these redshifts (Hippelein et al. 2003, Faber et al. 2005), galaxies beyond our flux limit may contribute more than a factor of two to the total star formation rate. Third, we assume an average extinction value based on the local galaxy sample for the calculation of the star formation rate which may be an under-estimate of the true value. These, among other affects not considered here, may contribute more than a factor of two to the total star formation rate measured for these clusters. However, our assumptions are similar to those made in other works and allow a comparison of our data with those previous studies.

For each cluster, we estimate a mass within $0.5 R_{200}$. In order of preference, we derive masses from the following sources: High precision lensing estimates are the preferred mass, but if they do not exist, we rely on a mass estimate based on the X-ray luminosity and the local $L_x - \sigma$ relationship.

If neither exist, we then use the spectroscopic velocity dispersion for the mass estimate following Carlberg et al. (1997).

For MS0451, Cl0016, and MS1054, we use the isothermal sphere velocity dispersion from the weak lensing analysis of Clowe et al. (2000), and calculate the mass at R_{200} from the equation $M(r) = 2\sigma^2 r/G$ (Wright & Brainerd 2000). Cl0016 also has a much smaller lensing mass than predicted from either its spectroscopic velocity dispersion or from its X-ray luminosity, although the three estimates are within the reported 3σ errors.

For CL1604, Margoniner et al. (2005) determined a velocity dispersion of 1004 ± 199 km s^{-1} based on a weak lensing estimate, which agrees well with the observed spectroscopic velocity dispersion. No lensing estimate exists for Cl1322. However, Cl1604 and Cl1322, have under-luminous X-ray luminosities for their observed velocity dispersions—unlike our other clusters. If the X-ray light is tracing the true mass of these objects, than the mass of Cl1604 is overestimated by a factor of 4 by the spectroscopic velocity dispersion according to the local $L_x - \sigma$ relationship (Wu et al. 1999). The large error associated with the lensing estimate in Cl1604, which could be significantly affected by the presence of any large scale structure behind the cluster, provides little constraint on the appropriate mass of the cluster.

In addition to our clusters, we also include the following clusters from the literature: A1689 (Balogh et al. 2002), AC114 (Couch et al. 2001), A2390 (Balogh & Morris 2000), Cl0024 (Kodama et al. 2004), Cl0023 (Finn et al. 2004) and Cl0152 (Homeier et al. 2004). We also include Cl1040-1155, Cl1054-1245, and Cl1216-1201 from Finn et al. (2005). We have determined in the cluster mass for these samples in the same way as our sample at a radius of $0.5R_{200}$.

Previous studies have either assumed the mass from the velocity dispersion or at radii different from the one in which the ΣSFR is measured. We emphasize the difficulty of determining the mass for some of these clusters as they are merging systems—some merging along the line of sight. For example, the initial velocity measurements for Cl0024 indicated a very massive system with extremely high velocity dispersion. The x-ray properties of the system indicated a far less massive system (Ota et al. 2004), but the weak lensing estimates agree with the massive system interpretation. Until a large spectroscopic sample was obtained, the double peaked nature of the velocity distribution could

not be resolved (Czoksie et al. 2002). Now, Cl0024 is believed to be two systems, with the larger system having a velocity dispersion near 562 km/s, merging along the line of sight. A1689 may suffer from a similar complex distribution with another structure only 50 Mpc in front of it along its line of sight (Łokas et al. 2005), while the lensing mass of Cl1054-1245 may be overestimate from structure along the line of sight as well (Clowe et al. 2005). The X-ray properties of the cluster may not provide a simple relief from this problem either: the un-virialized gas is expected to undergo heating and cooling producing substantial offsets from the $L_x - T_x$ relationship (Ricker & Sarazin 2001). To appropriately determine the mass of a system, a full synthesis of a large spectroscopic survey, X-ray observations, and weak lensing measurements are required for the more complex merging systems. This analysis is beyond the scope of the current work, but the mass for each system was estimated following the same prescription for our clusters.

In Table 4.5, we list the properties of all clusters in our sample and the sources in the literature where the properties were obtained. We transform all the cluster properties into our fiducial cosmology with $H_o = 70$ km/s Mpc⁻³. In Figure 4.27, we plot ΣSFR and $\Sigma SFR/M_{0.5}$ as a function of redshift for the full sample, where $M_{0.5}$ is the mass within 0.5 R_{200} . In addition, we also plot the uncorrected average star formation for a sample of 115 low redshift clusters from Goto (2005) as a single point. This spectroscopic sample from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey has a brighter limiting magnitude than our sample and may require significant correction(up to 80%), but provides an estimate of the average star formation in clusters in the nearby Universe. Since the correction for this point is unknown, we do not include this point in calculating any relationships with cluster property.

There is no apparent correlation of the total star formation with redshift in the clusters, but the mass normalized sample shows a significant correlation with redshift (the null hypothesis (no correlation) can be eliminated with 72% confidence according to the Spearman Rank test). Despite the increased number of clusters in our sample compared to previous studies, a strong selection bias may still exist. Our sample is composed of some of the richest clusters at high redshifts, and only the sample of Finn et al. (2005) from the EDISCs sample can claim any homogeneity in selection. A K-S test between the mass distribution of the high redshift clusters ($z > 0.6$) and low redshift clusters indicates a significant difference between the samples as a function of mass. More detailed

simulations are required to assess whether the high redshift sample will accumulate enough mass to have comparable masses at $z = 0$ as the low redshift sample, but the trends observed in the data may partially be a remnant of the mass disparity in the samples.

We have plotted the global star formation rate, ρ_* , normalized by the mass density of the Universe, $\rho_m(z) = \rho_m(0) * (1 + z)^3$, where $\rho_m(0) = \Omega_m * \rho_c(0)$. $\rho_c(0)$ is the critical density of the Universe and $\Omega_m = 0.3$. For ρ_* , we use the extinction corrected values from Lilly et al. (1996) published by Steidel et al. (1999) for $z = 0$ to 1. The decrease in the star formation rate in the clusters mimics the decrease in the global star formation rate. If the blue galaxies are recent additions to the cluster, then the decreasing trend in total star formation rate is related to the decreasing amount of star formation seen in the field.

The observed correlation between redshift and mass-normalized star formation rate is not initially intuitive, especially in terms of comparison to the global star formation rate. Since we are normalizing the clusters by their total dynamical mass (which is dominated by dark matter while the stellar mass is mostly in luminous, early-type galaxies) within the observed aperture, the mass-normalized SFR can also be expressed as the ratio of the average SFR to the average dynamical mass of the population. The global star formation rate is the average star formation rate per unit volume, and when normalized by the mass density of the Universe, also becomes the ratio of the average star formation rate to the average object mass. We refer to this as “object mass” since the clusters and field are being normalized by the total mass (baryon plus dark matter), whereas a baryon-mass-normalized global SFR would be approximately a factor of 6 higher. Since the average star formation rates of star forming galaxies are the same in cluster and field environments, the average mass of an object in the cluster must be smaller than the field. At these redshifts, the star forming population of many of these clusters are dominated by a bursting dwarf population (Martin et al. 2000, de Propris et al. 2001).

4.6 Global Cluster Properties

A significant amount of scatter between the clusters and the global star formation relationship exists. A portion of this scatter is due to the variety of measurement techniques (spectroscopy, $H\alpha$ narrow band imaging, and [OII] λ 3727 narrow band imaging) and corrections applied to the data.

Even within our sample where the corrections and techniques are self-consistent, a significant amount of scatter exists between the clusters. We emphasize, once again, that this sample is hardly representative and predominately samples the richest clusters and densities at each redshift. Nonetheless, we examine the full sample of clusters for any correlation among cluster properties within it.

4.6.1 Cluster Mass

Goto (2005) found no trend in star formation rate with cluster mass for a sample of 115 nearby galaxy clusters. We confirm this finding for the high redshift sample of clusters. No significant correlation exists within the sample either between the total star formation rate and either the cluster velocity dispersion or the cluster mass estimate (usually a lensing estimate) within $0.5 R_{200}$.

The mass normalized total star formation rate does correlation with the cluster mass. However, as a function of mass, the distribution of mass normalized total star formation rates are more aptly described as having an upper limit, rather than a linear correlation. Poggianti et al. (2006) used a similar description to explain the distribution in the [OII] fraction of cluster emitters as a function of mass, while a similar parameterization is used to describe the specific star formation rates observed in lower mass systems (Feulner et al. 2006). At lower masses ($< 2 \times 10^{14} M_{\odot}$), a range of total star formation rates exist, although the small normalized total star formation of the more massive sample were not observed.

4.6.2 X-ray Properties

The X-ray properties, shown in Figure 4.29, have a significant anti-correlation with the mass normalized ΣSFR . With the greater number of clusters, we find a much stronger correlation than Homeier et al. (2005). Removing the low X-ray luminosity clusters from the sample diminishes the significance of this correlation. Since the X-ray properties only show a correlation with the normalized star formation, the correlation may simply be a restatement of the relationship between the X-ray properties and mass.

Many of these clusters display complex structures in the X-ray morphologies indicating the gas may not be fully virialized. In addition, some of the geometries mentioned earlier will also affect the measurement of the X-ray properties. We tried to select X-ray measurements, listed in Table 4.5,

from the best possible data, but we may have been better served by selecting from a single source as many of the measurements have different instruments, techniques, and decompositions of the gas distribution to measure the X-ray properties (see Gioia et al. 2003 for an example for MS1054). A consistent measurement between the X-ray observations and the star-formation observations in similar apertures may provide a cleaner picture of what is occurring.

4.6.3 Luminosity Gap Statistic

The luminosity gap statistic is the difference in luminosity between the brightest and second brightest galaxy within the inner core ($< 0.5Mpc$) of a galaxy cluster (Milosavljević et al. 2006). A recent merger of two halos will leave two bright, massive galaxies in one halo until those galaxies merge. Hence, clusters with a large difference between the first and second rank cluster galaxies will not have had any recent major mergers. The measurement of the luminosity gap statistic has been shown as a reasonable indicator of merger history in simulations and in comparison with Sloan cluster samples (Milosavljević et al. 2006).

We have measured the magnitude difference, Δm_{12} , for all of our clusters. One change we make to the definition is that we measure the difference between the two brightest galaxies with $0.5 R_{200}$. By doing this, we measure Δm_{12} for the clusters in the same region that we measure the total star formation rate. For most of the clusters, we have spectroscopic redshifts for the two brightest cluster galaxies. For these cases, the error only includes errors in the measurement of the rest-frame B magnitude. For the clusters which spectroscopic redshifts do not cover the brightest two galaxies, we use photometric redshifts to select those galaxies. The error then reflects the difference in Δm_{12} if the third brightest galaxy is selected rather than the second brightest—indicating the second brightest galaxy is merely contamination.

Calculations of Δm_{12} for the other clusters in the literature have a range of precision due to the availability of different data. Where possible, we limited ourselves to spectroscopic data with observations in a filter that approximated the rest-frame B magnitude. For A2390 (Yee et al.1996), Cl0024 (Moran et al. 2005), Cl1040, Cl1054-12, and Cl1216 (Halliday et al. 2000), Δm_{12} was estimated from spectroscopic catalogs with either R, r, or I magnitudes (a crude approximation for M_B at most redshifts). The other sources were estimated from published color magnitude diagrams

and may suffer significant errors. Cl0023, at $z=0.83$, is the only cluster without some estimate. The error bars on the literature sources reflect the confidence of the measurement: the size of the error bar reflects the magnitude difference between the BCG and to where the bulk of the galaxies on the red sequence begins. The derived values, are listed in Table 4.5.

A strong anti-correlation exists between Δm_{12} and the mass-normalized total star formation rate (the Spearman rank test rejects the null hypothesis at 95% significance), and the total star formation shows a weak (2σ) anti-correlation for clusters with spectroscopic measurements of Δm_{12} . In this sense, clusters currently undergoing major mergers with small mass-ratios between their merging halos have the largest star formation rates. Our results do depend on the radius chosen for this measurement as a larger or smaller radius can quickly change either the total star formation rate or Δm_{12} . For example, within $R < 0.5$ Mpc, MS0451 has $\Delta m_{12} = 1.3$, but within $0.5 R_{200}$ ($R = 1.25$ Mpc), that value drops to 0.25. However, within that small radius, MS0451 has little star formation ($30 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$), whereas the number of star forming galaxies climbs rapidly in the wings of this cluster ($\sim 200 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ at $0.5 R_{200}$).

The full cluster sample shows the strongest correlation with Δm_{12} than any other cluster property measured so far. The Δm_{12} statistic shows no apparent correlation with redshift, but there are some trends with other cluster properties, such as mass: More massive clusters have lower measurements of Δm_{12} , but there is significant dispersion around a linear fit to this relationship. In addition, a correlation still exists if we divide our clusters into a low, medium, and high mass—although a greater number of clusters at different masses are needed to confirm these trends as any one bin only has four clusters in it. A greater number of clusters would improve the confidence of the results as well as allow investigation for trends within other cluster properties.

4.7 Discussion

If we assume the growth of structure based on Λ CDM scenario, the clusters will continue to accumulate mass from the field through mergers. Some of the mergers will be with structures of similar mass, whereas most of the mass will be accreted in the form of groups or smaller structures (Gottlöber et al.1999). Combining the framework of the Λ CDM paradigm for galaxy formation and assuming the star formation is quenched in in-falling galaxies, we can produce a simple model to

explore the total star formation rate in these clusters as a function of redshift.

The definition for the total star formation rate from a cluster is

$$\Sigma SFR = \sum_{i=0}^N \psi_i = N \langle \psi \rangle, \quad (4.8)$$

where ψ_i is the star formation rate of an individual galaxy. If the average star formation rate of an accreted galaxy at the redshift of accretion is the same as the field average, the observed radial trends in the cluster are reproduced if the star formation is extinguished once the galaxy enters a halo with $\sigma > 500$ km/s (Balogh et al. 1999, Poggianti et al. 2006). In the case the cluster star-forming galaxies began as normal field galaxies, the average star formation can be estimated from the global star formation rate and the mass density of the Universe:

$$\langle \psi \rangle = \frac{\dot{\rho}_*}{\rho_m} \langle m \rangle, \quad (4.9)$$

where $\langle m \rangle$ is the average mass of an accreted object. The number of accreted objects can be given by

$$N = f_{ext}(M_{cl}, z) M_{cl} / \langle m \rangle, \quad (4.10)$$

where $f_{ext}(M_{cl}, z)$ is the fraction of the total cluster mass accreted in the time it takes for the star formation to be extinguished. The accretion rate and fraction of mass accreted can be predicted from analytical Press-Schechter formalism (Cole & Lacey 1993). By combining the previous three equations, the total star formation rate of the cluster is

$$\Sigma SFR / M_{cl} = \frac{\dot{\rho}_*}{\rho_m} f_{ext}(M_{cl}, z). \quad (4.11)$$

The typical time scales expected for star forming galaxies to last in a rich cluster environment are on par with 50 Myrs if ram-pressure stripping is effective (Quillis, Moore, & Bower 2000) and up to a 1 Gyr for other processes (Treu et al. 2003). In either case, the time scale for extinction is far greater than the time scale required for the mass to double (Cole & Lacey 1993). For example, MS1054 is expected to double in mass between its observed epic 7 Gyrs ago and today (Tran et al. 2005b). For $t_{ext} = 1$ Gyr, we expect $f_{ext} \sim 0.1$ (Tormen 1998), which would yield values of ΣSFR approximately equal to the smallest values found. However this is likely to be an overestimate. Approximately 20% of clusters are expected to have undergone 1:1 mass mergers in the last 2.5 Gyrs (Cole & Lacey 1993)

while the fraction of major mergers is expected to increase to $z = 1$ for all but the most massive clusters (Cohn, Bagla & White 2001). The average star formation in an accreted massive cluster is expected to be less than that in the field except for relatively low mass halos due to the SFR-density relationship, so the total star formation rate might be overestimated by 10% if the average object in a high density environment has 1/2 the star formation of a typical field galaxy.

The observed distribution of $\Sigma SFR/M_c l$ with redshift decreases with redshift when considering the full sample of clusters in qualitative agreement with the global star formation rate, but many of these clusters appear to have mass normalized star formation rates greater than the field value—in conflict with our simple prediction for the total star formation rates. Maintaining the same framework, we can examine several possible explanations for the difference.

Extending the lifetime of star forming objects provides one mechanism for higher total star formation rates. This is certainly promising to explain the large star formation rates seen for low X-ray luminosity clusters, but provides little relief for the high mass clusters to explain the high normalized star formation rates seen in some objects. In clusters like MS0451 and Cl0016, the high density of hot gas is expected to efficiently strip a galaxies reservoir of gas for star formation (Gunn & Gott 1972). The segregation of star forming galaxies from the inner regions of clusters is further evidence that the ICM is suppressing the star formation (Homeier et al. 2005), and the small star formation rates measured within the cores of the most luminous x-ray clusters (Figure 4.26) also supports this segregation. Due to the density of hot gas in some of these clusters, the abrupt termination of star formation is expected to occur up to 1 Mpc from the core (Fujita & Nagashima 1999).

Another possibility to extend the accretion time is the contribution of “backsplash” galaxies to the measurement. Gill et al. (2005) find 50% of the galaxies beyond the virial radius in simulations of galaxy clusters have passed within the virial radius and have lost up to 40% of their mass. As these galaxies rebound to the outer wings of the cluster, they may recover some of their gas to re-initiate star formation (Fujita et al. 1999). Due to this process, they are expected to have smaller masses and star formation rates than a pristine sample of in-falling field galaxies. However, 98% of the backsplash galaxies exhibit only a single orbit outside of the virial radius indicating that the maximum increase

in t_{ext} is a crossing time while the average star formation rate and mass of these galaxies is less than those from the field.

If the average star formation rate of the cluster galaxies is above the field, this would provide another mechanism for boosting the total star formation rate in clusters. However, the average properties of star forming galaxies show little difference between the field and clusters (Balogh et al. 2003, Kodama et al. 2004), but there is evidence for differences between the field and cluster environment in the distribution of equivalent widths (Balogh et al. 1999, Martin et al. 2000). Indeed, the distribution of equivalent widths for our clusters and the field are significantly different as seen in Figure 4.25. The tail of high EW measurements are missing in the cluster environment but a greater number of low equivalent width emission line objects are seen. If a greater number of mediocre star forming galaxies are found in clusters due to a combination of suppression and enhancement, this would explain the large total star formation rate seen in some clusters.

A mechanism that has been invoked to explain the differences in the populations of different clusters is the merging of clusters (Couch et al. 1998, Owen et al. 1999, Tran et al. 2005a). The violent process of merging galaxies is expected to both boost and extinguish star formation. As the clusters merge, a bow-shock is initially produced between the two clusters protecting their galaxies from any increase in the ram pressure stripping (Roettiger, Burns, and Loken 1996). A cluster merging with a lower mass cluster will have an increase in its blue fraction because the lower mass group has more blue galaxies, which have not been stripped yet of its gas reservoir because of this protective bow shock, moving into the central regions of the cluster (Fujita et al. 1999). Once galaxies pass through this bow shock, they will have a burst of star formation while much of their remaining gas is stripped (Roettiger et al. 1996). Further starbursts can be caused by the expansive shocks introduced by the merging events (Roettiger et al. 1996). Starbursts can also be induced due to the increased and time-varying tidal forces, which are expected to cause a centrally concentrated starburst in cluster galaxies (Bekki 1999). Finally, an increase number of mergers are expected in the sub-cluster population due to the smaller velocity dispersion of the group.

The offset between the field and cluster normalized total star formation rates shows a strong correlation with Δm_{12} as shown in Figure 4.31. The clusters with the smallest difference in luminosity

between the two brightest members (hence undergoing the most significant merger) have the largest offset from the global star formation rate. However, clusters with large offsets in Δm_{12} , indicating no recent major merger events, have normalized total star formations smaller than the field value as expected. One problem with this sample is that it includes far too many merging clusters; it would be illuminating to include less active systems to strengthen this correlation. Another issue is the inconsistent measurement techniques and estimates of properties of the clusters. Even with these caveats, the merging of large structures appear to momentarily induce star formation. The star formation is unlikely to be long lasting, and we leave exploring the exact mechanisms (tidal forces, galaxy mergers, ram-pressure) of the star formation for future work.

We have only used the luminosity gap statistic to quantify the merging activity of the galaxy clusters, but a number of different methods have been used to quantify the assembly history of these clusters. Many of the clusters show evidence for interactions—especially in the shape of the galaxy or gas distributions. For example, MS1054 has extensive substructure in the gas distribution (Gioia et al. 2003), but it is not reflected in the measurement of the total star formation rate as compared to other clusters with substructure. In addition, MS1054 has a large fraction of merging galaxies (van Dokkum et al. 1999) and radio sources (Best et al. 2003), but a relatively small amount of star formation within the inner 1 Mpc. The stage of the merger, mass of the merging components, and geometry of the merger may all affect the amount of star formation induced. Furthermore, Δm_{12} does not quantify the number of mergers the cluster is undergoing and only has a slight relationship to the mass ratio of the merger if the luminosity of the two BCGs correlates with their initial halo’s mass. For a cluster about to undergo merging, tidal forces can begin to affect the populations of the galaxies while the clusters are still quite far away from each other, which may explain the higher blue fractions seen in substructures around large clusters (Tran et al. 2005a). For post merged clusters, the tidal forces and shock waves can affect the population of galaxies for several Gyrs after the event.

Throughout this study, we have neglected the possibility of obscured star forming galaxies. Miller & Owen (2003) estimate that 20% of the galaxies in their sample of nearby Abell clusters have star formation which is completely obscured at $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$, while as much as 90% of the star formation activity in A1689 may be obscured (Duc et al. 2002). This problem is likely to be worse

at high redshift if trends in the field (Hammer et al. 2001) apply to cluster star forming galaxies. A second interpretation of the low fraction of star forming, blue galaxies in the high redshift clusters is that we are missing the obscured population. If true, this would significantly increase the cluster star formation rates at these redshifts.

4.8 Conclusions

We have provided narrow-band [OII] λ 3727 measurements for six intermediate redshift galaxy clusters. The measurements were made from WIYN 3.5m imaging, which also includes UBRIZ broad band imaging. We have measured high-quality photometry in each of the clusters, measured photometric redshifts, and measured rest-frame properties for all of the cluster galaxies.

We have detailed an algorithm to produce high quality line flux estimates from narrow-band imaging by fitting model spectral energy distributions. Cluster emission line sources were identified by estimating the probability the galaxy was an emission line source at the cluster. This probability is based on the significance of the [OII] detection, the probability of cluster membership based on photometric redshifts, quality of SED fit, and color and magnitude requirements. Based on a subset of galaxies with spectroscopic observations, our sample has small contamination from field sources and has high quality EW estimates. We estimate star formation rates for our galaxies from the observed line fluxes, and the total star formation rate for the clusters as well.

- The normalization of the luminosity function for our clusters is well above the field value at all redshifts. The excess number of star forming galaxies is smallest in the high redshift clusters. This is primarily due to the increase in the field luminosity function, as the luminosity function shows little variation between the different clusters, and hence little variation with redshift.
- The fraction of blue cluster-galaxies with [OII] λ 3727 emission is consistent with the field fraction at $z \sim 0.5$. At high redshifts, the fraction remains near 50% for large cluster radii, although this fraction may be an underestimation if a significant number of the blue galaxies are beyond the transmission window of our filters. This value is well below the fraction of emission line blue galaxies seen in the field at these redshifts.
- The average star formation rates for star forming galaxies with $M_B < -18.5$ in the cluster

appear constant with both cluster radius and density. However, the distribution of EW does vary with density. The star formation rate averaged over *all* cluster galaxies with $M_B < -18.5$ shows the same decline observed in other studies, except for the highest redshift cluster in our sample: Cl 1604. The average star formation rates for the star forming galaxies have similar values for a given redshift between the clusters and the field estimated from our off-band images.

- For each cluster, we have computed the total star formation rate within $0.5 R_{200}$. The total star formation shows no correlation with redshift within our own sample of 6 clusters, but there is considerable scatter. The situation is unchanged when we include sources from the literature. However, once the total SFR is normalized by the mass within $0.5 R_{200}$, we find a strong correlation with redshift. In fact, $\Sigma SFR/M_{cl}$ declines at the same rate as the global star formation rate.
- We find no correlation between the mass of the cluster and ΣSFR similar to results at low redshift (Goto 2003). The distribution of the total star formation rate with mass may be qualitatively described as having an upper envelope similar to the fraction of [OII] emission line objects seen by Poggianti et al. (2005) or estimates of the specific star formation rate made for lower mass objects (Feulner et al. 2006).
- The $\Sigma SFR/M_{cl}$ shows the strongest correlation with the luminosity gap statistics, an estimate of the merger status of the cluster. Furthermore, the scatter between the mass-normalized global star formation rate and that of the cluster can be accounted for primarily by the merger status of the cluster.

Star formation, especially as a function of environment, still remains a complex topic. Further study is required to understand the subtle differences between field and cluster populations that are hidden by gross generalizations like the average star formation rate. In the current paradigm of galaxy formation, clusters are a mix of a very old quiescent population and an accreted population being transformed onto the red sequence. The accretion of large structures onto the cluster appears to have noticeable effects as a burst in star formation—similar to the starbursts seen in the merger of gas-rich galaxies. The merging event is expected to induce star

formation through several different processes, it provides a means to produce the population of post starburst galaxies observed in many intermediate redshift clusters (Barger et al. 1997). However, the exact mechanism responsible for the burst (mergers, shocks, tidal forces, ram-pressure) and the subsequent extinction in the star formation have yet to be fully understood.

4.9 Narrow-Band Filters

We describe here the technical attributes and pass-band calibration of the six custom, narrow-band designed for the Mini-Mosaic camera on the WIYN 3.5m telescope, and manufactured by Omega Optical. The filters are four inches square with thicknesses of 8mm. The central wavelengths of the filters were designed to detect [OII] λ 3727 from objects at the redshift of each cluster, with these cluster redshifts determined from spectroscopic measurements in the literature. Five of the six clusters have enough spectroscopic redshift to accurately determine velocity dispersions for the clusters. As previously noted, filter band-widths were designed to detect [OII] λ 3727 emission from galaxies within $\pm 1.7\sigma_v$ of the cluster redshift. Filter transmission response was specified for the f/6.3 beam of the WIYN imaging port to have these primary attributes: (1) flat over the width of the filter in order to provide uniform response to all emission line galaxies, (2) to have peak throughput greater than 70%.

Upon delivery, Omega Optical provided optical scans of each of the filters at room temperature. To verify filter performance, we measured their response curves with the λ -9 spectrophotometer at NOAO headquarters (Tucson, AZ) with the assistance of G. Jacoby and A. Saha. We probed the filters over a range of wavelengths, spatial positions, and beam angles. These measurements were made with the filters at room temperature, although operating conditions at the telescope can be 25° C cooler. We expect little variation in performance for the filter at operating temperatures. We estimate the central wavelength of our narrow-band filters will shift by approximately -3 Å at the lowest temperatures observed (0° C). For the typical band-pass, this is equivalent to 0.0008 shift in redshift.

While our scans were made in an collimated beam, the filters were designed to operate at the speed of the WIYN telescope ($f/6.3$). According to Omega Optical (2006), the shift in the

central wavelength for these filters due to changes in the angle of incidence is given by:

$$\lambda_{\theta} = \lambda_0 \left[1 - \left(\frac{n_e}{n_f} \right)^2 \sin^2 \theta \right]^{0.5} \quad (4.12)$$

In this equation, λ_{θ} is the new central wavelength, λ_0 is the central wavelength at normal incidence, n_e is the refractive index of the external media (air), n_f is the refractive index of the filter, and θ is the angle of incidence. Assuming $n_f = 1.3$, the maximum shift in wavelength for any of our filters over the full range of incidence is 0.13%.

In Figure 4.32 we plot the total estimated response function versus wavelength associated with these filters, along with the histogram of cluster galaxies with spectroscopic redshifts. In all cases, the filter performed within, or better than, specifications. Typical peak throughput of the filters are 70% and there is less than 5% variation across the peak. Characteristics of the filters are listed in Table 4.6.

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Table 4.1. Observed Fields

Cluster	RA (J2000)	DEC (J2000)	z	On-band ^a Exp. Time (s)	Off-band ^b Exp. Time (s)
MS0451	04:54:10.81	-03:00:56.85	0.538	13200	5400
CL0016	00:18:33.52	+16:26:16.01	0.55	18000	10800
CL1325	13:25:18.70	+30:09:57.09	0.72	10800	7200
CL1324	13:24:50.13	+30:11:18.49	0.75	14400	7200
MS1054	10:56:59.50	-03:37:28.39	0.83	21600	6000
CL1604	16:04:18.27	+43:04:38.42	0.90	27000	11400

^aOn-band filters for each cluster: MS0451 (O1), CL0016 (O2), CL1325 (O3), CL1322 (O4), MS1054 (O5), and CL1604 (O6)

^bOff-band filters for each cluster: MS0451 (KP1528), CL0016 (KP1528), CL1325 (O4), CL1322 (O3), MS1054 (O6), and CL1604 (O5)

Table 4.2. Error in the Measurement of the Continuum

Cluster	Δ_3	σ_3	Δ_4	σ_4
MS0451	0.50	0.40	0.11	0.15
CL0016	0.26	0.23	0.05	0.08
CL1325	0.34	0.14	0.10	0.04
CL1322	0.21	0.16	0.17	0.08
MS1054	0.42	0.31	0.12	0.05
CL1604	0.07	0.08	0.02	0.05

Table 4.3. Contamination from other Emission Line Objects

Cluster	$H\alpha$	[OIII] λ 5007	$Ly\alpha$
MS0451	0(0)	< 1(3)	22(13)
CL0016	0(0)	< 1(2)	22(30)
CL1325	0(0)	3(3)	8(6)
CL1324	0(0)	3(2)	8(15)
MS1054	0.1(0)	6(10)	6(4)
CL1604	0.5(4)	4(9)	3-7(11)

^aThe estimated number of $H\alpha$ emission line objects was calculated from Gallego et al. 1995.

^bThe estimated number of [OIII] λ 5007 emission line objects was calculated from the KISS survey (Salzer et al. 2002) and the CADIS survey (Hippelein et al. 2003)

^cThe estimated number of $Ly\alpha$ emission line objects was calculated from Cowie & Hu 1998, Rhoads et al. 2000, and Hu et al 2004.

Table 4.4. Contamination from other Emission Line Objects

Cluster (1)	z (2)	$f_{oii,N}$ (3)	$f_{oii,N}$ (4)	$f_{oii,P}$ (5)	$f_{oii,P}$ (6)
MS0451	0.53	0.10 ± 0.02	0.30	0.17 ± 0.03	...
Cl0016	0.55	0.17 ± 0.01	0.08	0.12 ± 0.02	0.14 ± 0.07
Cl1325	0.75	0.26 ± 0.02	0.18	0.19 ± 0.04	0.47 ± 0.14
MS1054	0.83	0.08 ± 0.01	0.03	0.10 ± 0.03	0.31 ± 0.06
Cl1604	0.90	0.33 ± 0.03	0.42	0.29 ± 0.02	...

Note.—notes—(1) Cluster name (2) Cluster redshift (3) OII fraction measured from our data following the definition by Nakata et al. (2005) (4) OII fraction measured by Nakata et al. (2005) estimated from their Figure 4. (5) OII fraction measured from our data following the definition by Poggianti et al (2006) (6) OII fraction measured by Poggianti et al. (2006).

Table 4.5. Properties of Clusters

Cluster	z	σ_v km/s	M_v $10^{14} M_\odot$	$M_{0.5}^a$ $10^{14} M_\odot$	R_c Mpc	R_{200} Mpc	L_x 10^{44} erg/s	T_x keV	ΣSFR M_\odot/yr	m_{12}	ref. ^b
A1689	0.183	1660 ± 127	2.6 ± 0.3	1.3 ± 0.15	...	3.14 ± 0.29^c	34.4 ± 0.2	9.31 ± 0.40	81 ± 37.8	1.00 ± 0.20	1
A2390a	0.228	1023 ± 102	19.9 ± 5.4	12.5 ± 1.20	...	2.26 ± 0.23	40.8 ± 0.8	9.21 ± 1.20	159 ± 17.0	0.80 ± 0.25	2
AC114	0.320	1429 ± 139	34.6 ± 10	7.3 ± 0.80	...	2.67 ± 0.23^c	15.2 ± 0.3	7.85 ± 0.91	43 ± 28.2	0.50 ± 0.50	3
CL0024	0.395	561 ± 89	8.8 ± 2.2	2.8 ± 1.10	...	1.13 ± 0.18	2.9 ± 0.1	3.52 ± 0.17	248 ± 34.0	0.36 ± 0.10	4
MS0451	0.535	1354 ± 40	12.0 ± 3.6	5.4 ± 1.60	0.19 ± 0.02	2.50 ± 0.07	40.0 ± 1.1	10.2 ± 2	299 ± 30	1.25 ± 0.30	5
CL0016	0.550	1230 ± 50	6.5 ± 2.0	3.2 ± 0.97	0.22 ± 0.04	2.25 ± 0.09	37.0 ± 0.8	9 ± 2	247 ± 15	0.50 ± 0.07	6
CL1040	0.704	418 ± 50	0.97 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.15	...	0.70 ± 0.08	61 ± 18.5	0.25 ± 0.20	7
CL1054	0.748	504 ± 89	8.4 ± 2.7	1.5 ± 0.50	...	0.82 ± 0.14	26 ± 7.8	0.44 ± 0.40	8
CL1322	0.76	1016 ± 50	1.5 ± 0.5	1.5 ± 0.10	0.12 ± 0.02	1.64 ± 0.08	1.4 ± 0.7	2.9 ± 0.7	181 ± 30	0.47 ± 0.13	9
CL1216	0.794	1018 ± 75	4.9 ± 1.0	4.8 ± 0.50	...	1.61 ± 0.12	313 ± 94.1	0.02 ± 0.05	10
MS1054	0.83	1170 ± 70	24.1 ± 5.0	9.5 ± 0.10	0.41 ± 0.20	1.81 ± 0.11	16.3 ± 0.8	8.6 ± 1.5	92 ± 11	1.44 ± 0.10	11
CL0152	0.837	952 ± 500	7.8 ± 1.4	3.5 ± 0.50	...	1.47 ± 0.77	16.0 ± 2.0	0.70 ± 2.00	96 ± 19.2	1.00 ± 0.30	12
CLJ0023	0.845	415 ± 82	0.8 ± 0.08	0.46 ± 0.25	...	0.64 ± 0.13	77.9 ± 7.1	...	13
CL1604	0.90	982 ± 141	13.6 ± 3.0	1.5 ± 0.15	0.14 ± 0.01	1.46 ± 0.21	2.0 ± 0.2	2.5 ± 1	115 ± 11	0.27 ± 0.03	14

^aThe mass within $0.5R_{200}$.

^bReferences: (1) Girardi et al. 1997, Finn et al. 2005, Lokas et al. 2005, Ota & Mitsuda 2004, Balogh et al. 2002 (2) Carlberg et al. 1996, Squires et al. 1996, Broadhurst et al. 2005, Ota & Mitsuda 2004, Balogh & Morris 2000 (3) Mahdavi & Gellar 2001, Natarajan et al. 1998, Finn et al. 2005, Ota & Mitsuda 2004, Couch et al. 2001 (4) Czoske et al. 2002, Kneib et al. 2003, Zhang et al. 2005, Diaferio et al. 2005, Kodama et al. 2004 (5) Carlberg et al. 1996, Clowe et al. 2000, Ota & Mitsuda 2004, Schindler 1999 (6) Carlberg et al. 1996, Clowe et al. 2000, Donahue et al. 2003 (7) Halliday et al. 2004, Clowe et al. 2005, Finn et al. 2005 (8) Halliday et al. 2004, Clowe et al. 2005, Finn et al. 2005 (9) Lubin, Oke, & Postman 2002, Lubin et al. 2004 (10) Halliday et al. 2004, Clowe et al. 2005, Finn et al. 2005 (11) Tran et al. 1999, Hoekstra et al. 2000, Jee et al. 2005, Goia et al. 2003, Schindler 1999 (12) Demarco et al. 2004, Jee et al. 2005, Maugan et al. 2003, Homeier et al. 2005 (13) Postman, Lubin, & Oke 1998, Finn et al. 2003 (14) Gal & Lubin 2004, Margoniner et al. 2005, Lubin et al. 2004

^c R_{200} is estimated from the X-ray luminosity and not the velocity dispersion (Finn et al. 2005)

Table 4.6. Narrow Band Filters

Cluster	Filter Name	z^a	CWL \AA	FWHM \AA
MS0451	O1	0.538	5732	84
CL0016	O2	0.546	5763	85
CL1325	O3	0.719	6410	94
CL1324	O4	0.749	6522	96
MS1054	O5	0.831	6824	100
CL1604	O6	0.899	7081	104

^a z is the redshift of [OII] λ 3727 at the central wavelength (CWL) of the filter.

Fig. 4.1.— Response-functions for all pass-bands used for this study. These functions are the convolution of the filter transmission curve, the response function of the Mini-Mosaic CCD, and the transmission of the atmosphere (1 airmass).

Fig. 4.2.— Completeness curves for each of the on-band filters. Each plot shows the completeness in our on-band image for galaxies of three different sizes. The galaxies used for the calculation are selected from bright galaxies in each image and represent the range of sizes for all objects in the image.

Fig. 4.3.— Model spectra (see text) normalized at $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ (left) and $H\alpha$ (right). The models show far more structure and slope near the $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ line than they do near the $H\alpha$ line. A 20 Myr (blue), 0.5 Gyr (green), and 15 Gyr (red) old spectra for a simple stellar population are highlighted.

Fig. 4.4.— Equivalent-width measurements using the the off-band continuum method (3) versus *apparent* color of model spectral energy distributions for a range of stellar populations (see text). These models have *no* line-emission, and hence these EW’s represent the potential systematic errors in the measurement of the true, emission-line EW. Each of the model SEDs has been shifted to the redshift of each cluster. These “systematic” equivalent-widths show significant variation as a function of SED shape, as given by their apparent $B - R$ color. Trends in systematic EW vary with cluster redshift and filter combination, as indicated by different symbol colors (coded by cluster, as labeled). Note the general curvature of the EW with $B - R$. Most cluster-relations exhibit positive curvature with color. Because off-band filters for MS1054 and CL1325 are red-ward, instead of blue-ward, of the on-band filter, these two clusters have Δ EW trends with negative curvature. The contribution of this systematic EW error to the measurement of emission-line EW will depend on the strength of the emission line.

Fig. 4.5.— Three examples of template-spectra fits to observed, broad-band spectral energy distributions. The top two templates are for emission-line, star-forming systems, while the bottom one is an old, quiescent stellar population. In addition to the measured equivalent width, we also list the age and extinction of the best fit model.

Fig. 4.6.— Variation in EW vs apparent $B-R$ color for all clusters using two different EW measurement methods. The models are either observed template spectra from Kinney et al. (1996) or model SEDs with emission at rest-frame $[OII]\lambda 3727$ added with strengths ranging from $EW = 3-50$. Measurements are made at $S/N = 100$ in the small detection aperture. Filled symbols represent the SED fitting method (method 4); open symbols represent the off-band filter method (method 3). Method 4 yields much smaller variance (random error) and systematic error, as further quantified in Table 4.2. Clusters are represented by different colors, as given in Figure 4.4.

Fig. 4.7.— Mean systematic error in EW (ΔEW) and random errors (error bars) as a function of S/N for a range of observed SEDs. Observed SEDs include NGC 4449 (BC03) and starbursts (Kinney et al. 1996). Errors are deduced from Monte Carlo simulations. Systematics are negligible above $S/N = 6$. At $S/N = 10$ the random error is 11 \AA in EW. A source with $S/N = 10$ has approximately $R \sim 24$ in our data.

Fig. 4.8.— Comparison between spectroscopic and photometric EW for objects in our fields. The method used to measure the photometric EW is the SED fitting procedure (method 4). Clusters with published EW are C10016 (green circles), C11322 (aqua diamonds), MS1054 (black pentagons), and C11604 (blue squares).

Fig. 4.9.— Same as Figure 4.8, except for the off-band EW method (method 3).

Fig. 4.10.— EW measured for the Cl0016 filter set (method 4) for a range of SEDs simulate between $0 < z < 2$. The cluster is located at $z = 0.55$. SEDs used are NGC4449 (blue; BC03), an elliptical and S0 (red), Sa and Sb SED (green), and starbursts models (purple). All the models are from Kinney et al. (1996) except NGC 4449. The dotted line at $EW = 10 \text{ \AA}$ is for reference.

Fig. 4.11.— Same as Figure 4.10 but for MS0451 at $z = 0.535$.

Fig. 4.12.— Same as Figure 4.10 but for CL1325 at $z = 0.72$.

Fig. 4.13.— Same as Figure 4.10 but for CL1322 at $z = 0.75$.

Fig. 4.14.— Same as Figure 4.10 but for MS1054 at $z = 0.83$.

Fig. 4.15.— Same as Figure 4.10 but for CL1604 at $z = 0.90$.

Fig. 4.16.— Distribution of detection significance ($k = f_l / \sigma_l$) with apparent magnitude, apparent color, and EW for all objects with published spectroscopy. Top panels are measured using method (4), and bottom panels use method (3). Different colors represent the different clusters as in Figure 4.4. Filled symbols are confirmed cluster members whereas open symbols are confirmed field objects.

Fig. 4.17.— Detection significance (S/N of the integrated light) for the $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ line and measured star formation rate as a function of radius for two spectroscopically confirmed cluster star forming galaxies. The two galaxies, selected from the MS1054 field, represent extremes in our sample: one with the largest measured half-light radius ($R_h = 1.10$ arcsec) for the cluster while the other is unresolved ($R_h = 0.55$ arcsec). Vertical lines indicate the size of the two “fixed” apertures in which the photometry is measured. These correspond to 8.3 and 4.2 kpc at $z = 0.83$. The smaller aperture has higher detection significance for the smaller galaxy, but does not sample all of the star formation for the larger galaxy.

Fig. 4.18.— Narrow-band colors for template spectra as a function of redshift (left) for different observed SEDs. Templates included in the right-hand panel are normal galaxies [Elliptical(red), S0, Sa (green), Sb] from Kinney et al. (1996), and NGC 4449 (blue curve; BC03). Right-hand panels show an expanded region about (and reference to) each cluster redshift. The models used in the right-hand panels are NGC 4449 (blue), an elliptical model (red), and the Kinney starburst models (black). We included the Kinney starburst models to show the range in colors produced by different emission line galaxies with a range of stellar populations and extinctions. The grey straight line in the figures represents the imposed color cut.

Fig. 4.19.— Broad-band color distribution for observed SEDs of normal and star forming galaxies.

Fig. 4.20.— Redshift distribution of spectroscopically-confirmed sources (black), significant $[OII]\lambda 3727$ detections (lavender), cluster emission line candidates (red), and high-fidelity emission-line cluster sources (blue).

Fig. 4.21.— The EW completeness as a function of redshift. Each point is calculated for the photometric errors of the over-density associated with the redshift (i.e. the point at $z = 0.538$ is calculated based on the photometric errors in the observations of MS0451). We assume the sources have an SED similar to NGC 4449.

Fig. 4.22.— [OII] λ 3727 luminosity function for our low and high redshift clusters, left and right panels, respectively. The solid points are for the corrected counts, and the symbols represent the different clusters as follows: MS0451 (red squares), Cl0016 (green triangles), Cl1322 (teal diamonds), MS1054 (black pentagons), and Cl1604 (blue triangles). We also plot the measured densities from our off-band images are presented as lines with the same colors as the points. The on-band of the extended field of Cl1322 is presented as purple diamonds. The luminosity function for A851 (grey hexagons) and MS1512 (grey stars) are plotted from the data in Lotz et al. (2003). In addition, we plot the field sample of Hogg et al. (1996, solid grey line) and Hippelein et al. (2003, dashed grey line).

Fig. 4.23.— Blue fraction (blue:total, dashed), OII fraction (OII:total dotted), and blue OII fraction (OII:blue, solid) as a function of cluster radius normalized to R_{200} for each cluster.

Fig. 4.24.— Average star formation rate as a function of radius and density. Colors and symbols are the same as in Figure 4.22. The top panels represent the average star-formation per cluster galaxy, and the lower panels represent the average star formation only including the emission line galaxies. Each symbol represents the average of 100 and 25 galaxies for the full and star forming samples, respectively. For comparison with previous work, these values are calculate for objects with $M_B < -19.5$ which is above the detection limit for all cluster sources. In all of the plots, the average star formation rate increases with redshift.

Fig. 4.25.— Distribution of EW (right) and SFR (left) for all detected cluster (solid line) and field (dashed line) emission line objects. The field and cluster distributions have been normalized by the total number of galaxies within each environment. The EW distributions have only a 3% chance of being drawn from the same parent population.

Fig. 4.26.— Integrated star formation rate for each of our clusters. The error bar in the lower right hand corner represents the typical expected error at $0.5 R_{200}$. A significant amount of variation exists at the smaller radii, whereas the clusters tend to have similar values at large radii.

Fig. 4.27.— Total star formation rate and normalized star formation rate as a function of redshift. Symbols are the same as Figure 4.22. Sources from the literature are included as grey squares. The un-corrected average of 115 low redshift clusters from the SDSS is presented as a grey circle (Goto 2005). The solid line is the global star formation rate measured from Steidel et al. (1999) normalized by the total mass density of the Universe ($\Omega_{\text{matter}} = 0.3$).

Fig. 4.28.— Total star formation rate as a function of cluster velocity dispersion and lensing mass. Symbols are the same as Figure 4.27. No correlation between total star formation and mass is observe.

Fig. 4.29.— Total star formation rate and normalized star formation rate as a function of cluster X-ray properties. The X-ray luminosity and dispersion are derived from sources in the literature. Symbols are the same as Figure 4.27. According to the Spearman rank test, the null hypothesis (no correlation) cannot be disqualified for any relationship between the X-ray properties and the total star formation rate.

Fig. 4.30.— Total star formation rate and normalized star formation rate as a function of the luminosity gap. The luminosity gap is the magnitude difference between the first and second ranked cluster members within $R < 0.5$ Mpc. The hypothesis that the total and mass-normalized total star formation rate are uncorrelated with the luminosity gap can be ruled out with confidence levels of 80% and 99%, respectively.

Fig. 4.31.— The scatter between the mass normalized cluster star formation rate and the global star formation rate displays a strong correlation with the luminosity gap. Symbols are the same as in 4.22. Clusters in the middle of major mergers have relatively larger star formation rates than clusters with greater virialization.

Fig. 4.32.— Response functions for the on-band, rest-frame $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ filters used for cluster observations. The curves are the convolution of the filter transmission curves, the Mini-Mosaic CCD quantum efficiency. These high resolution scans were produced with the $\lambda - 9$ spectrophotometer at NOAO, as described in the Appendix. The redshift histogram for each cluster, as found in the literature, is plotted as well, assuming all sources have $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ emission at their spectroscopic redshift. This assumption is for illustration purposes only to highlight the suitability of the band-pass. The histogram for Cl1322 is plotted in the bandpass used for Cl1322 since the redshifts for this field are, as of yet, unpublished.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

In this thesis, we have investigated the galaxy populations in five intermediate redshift galaxy clusters. Using a unique data set that includes narrow band imaging, we have focused on the distribution of star forming galaxies in the clusters. In particular, we have attempted to measure the distribution of Luminous Compact Blue Galaxies in order to establish them as a progenitor to a present-day population of galaxies.

5.1 Technical Achievements

The analysis made use of an extensive imaging data set obtained at the WIYN 3.5m telescope. UBRIZ broad-band imaging was obtained for 11 fields which targeted rich galaxy clusters at intermediate redshifts ($0.3 < z < 0.9$). A sub-sample of six fields containing the five richest, highest redshift clusters in our sample were further imaged in two narrow-band filters. The narrow-band filters were custom designed to measure $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ at the redshift of each cluster. In addition to the WIYN 3.5m observations, the data are supplemented by calibration observations at the WIYN 0.9m and imaging data from the Hubble Space Telescope archive.

Several technical achievements are described in this thesis. Total galaxy magnitudes were derived from an adaptive aperture method which set the aperture size based on a metric size and profile measurement. This photometric technique is an improvement over other methods used for galaxy photometry because it is able to correct for the profile differences observed in

the galaxy distribution and produce an accurate total magnitude. Photometric redshifts have been calculated through a hybrid of the template and training set methods. We are able to account for systematic effects like calibration error and template incompleteness while not being constrained by the size and breadth of the training set. Finally, emission-line flux is determined through an SED fitting methods. This accounts for the range of underlying SEDs around the [OII] λ 3727 line and produces accurate equivalent widths with small random errors.

5.2 Scientific Results

The following is a summary of the important scientific results of this work:

- In the five rich clusters, we identified a distinctive red sequence of galaxies. In terms of shape, the luminosity function for the red sequence is qualitatively the same as the red sequence found in local clusters. No apparent deficit is observed to $M_B = -18.5$ in contrast to previous results (de Lucia et al. 2004, Goto et al. 2005), but comparable to analysis for one of our clusters (Andreon 2006). The spatial distribution of the red galaxies is well described by a King profile with a core radius set by the distribution of the ICM.
- We have identified a population of extreme star-bursting galaxies in these clusters. This is the first survey for LCBGs in galaxy clusters, and the number density of LCBGs indicate they are a significant (13 – 28%) portion of the cluster population at these redshifts.
- The distribution of blue galaxies appears much less concentrated than the red galaxies. In particular, LCBGs are best described as a shell-like distribution with a deficit of star-forming galaxies in the cluster core. The deficit for all star-forming galaxies is observed in agreement with previous studies (Homeier et al. 2005), and the absence of LCBGs is significant within the core radius for the clusters.
- The morphology of LCBGs in the cores of the clusters indicate that they are qualitatively similar to field LCBGs in terms of magnitude, size, and concentration. Some cluster LCBGs appear smoother than field LCBGs via measurements of their asymmetry index,

while cluster LCBGs appear to have lower star formation rates than field LCBGs. In the wings of the MS1054 cluster, we do observe LCBGs with sizes and luminosities more indicative of Lyman-break galaxies rather than intermediate redshift field LCBGs.

- In bulk, LCBGs, especially at $z \sim 0.55$, are found predominately in moderately dense environments. Analysis of the enhancement of LCBGs relative to the field leads us to conclude that they are most likely associated with dE galaxies rather than spiral galaxies. However, we can not currently rule out differential evolution between field and cluster LCBGs.
- We have measured the $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ luminosity function in clusters and the field at redshifts between $z \sim 0.55-0.9$ through narrow-band imaging. The number of emission-line objects in clusters is much greater than what would be found in a similar volume in the field. The fraction of $[\text{OII}]\lambda 3727$ galaxies is depressed relative to the field values, but a correction for the color differences between cluster and the field samples reveals similar fractions of blue galaxies with emission lines in the $z \sim 0.55$ clusters. In terms of fraction of blue galaxies with emission lines, the high redshift sample shows a deficit as compared to the field at these redshifts.
- The average star formation rate of the cluster emission-line galaxies shows no difference with the field. The depression of star formation rate with density or cluster radius is observed for the full cluster sample. However, the equivalent widths between the cluster and the field samples measured from the narrow-band imaging reveals two different distribution.
- We have explored for any trends between cluster properties and the total star formation rate (the summation of star formation rate from all galaxies within each cluster). The total star formation rate shows little to no correlation with redshift, mass, or x-ray properties. The mass-normalized total star formation rate does correlate with redshift. As a function of mass (or mass proxy like x-ray property or velocity dispersion), the mass normalized total star formation rate displays a distribution which appears well defined

by an upper envelope with a lower maximum mass-normalized total star formation rate at higher masses. The mass normalized total star formation rate does show the strongest correlation with the luminosity gap statistic, which is an indicator of the recent merger history of the cluster.

5.3 Conclusions

We have couched our interpretation of many of these results in terms of the hierarchical growth of structures. Clusters are still expected to accumulate a significant portion of their mass between the observed epoch and today according to Λ CDM models (Eke, Navarro, & Frenk 1998, Poggianti et al. 2006). Simulations of the growth of structure through the accumulation of dark matter halos are able to reproduce many of the relationships observed today, but the simulations still have difficulty transferring the behavior of the dark matter to observations of real galaxies due to poor understanding of the processes that drive galaxy evolution.

The origin and fate of blue, star-forming galaxies was the initial impetus for this work. The scenario where these galaxies are in-falling into the cluster for the first time seems a plausible explanation of the observed shell-like spatial distribution. The kinematics of this population will have to be explored to verify the in-falling hypothesis, but if true, it provides a source (the field) for the population of star-forming galaxies. The most significant difference between the field and cluster is the number of star forming objects—which appears to increase more rapidly than the density of all luminous ($M_B < -18.5$) galaxies especially for LCBGs at intermediate redshifts. This would indicate that the cluster environment is inducing star formation in these galaxies (Moss & Whittle 2000, Rose et al. 2001).

However, the interpretation of the star formation in these galaxies is complicated by the different morphologies, asymmetries, and equivalent width distribution observed for cluster star-forming galaxies. Combined with the deficit of star-forming galaxies seen in the cluster cores, a rapid cessation of the star formation appears probable. Even as star formation is induced by the cluster environment, the available gas for star formation is removed from the galaxy either by the consumption by the intense star formation; galactic winds resulting from the star forma-

tion (Combes 2003); stripping through ram-pressure (Gunn & Gott 1972), galaxy harassment (Moore et al. 1996), or tidal forces (Merrit 1983); evaporation caused by the hot ICM (Bekki et al. 2002); and/or ejected during major galaxy mergers (Mihos 1995). All or some of these process are likely to contribute at different radii, but the rapid disappearance of LCBGs in the cores of clusters would point to ram-pressure stripping as a primary culprit due to the short timescale and high efficiency of the process in the cores of rich clusters (Quillis, Moore, & Bower 2000).

The most plausible descendant for the LCBGs seen in clusters are dE galaxies. The enhancement of LCBG in terms of bulk cluster populations is very similar to that expected for dE galaxies from their local morphology density relationship (Binggeli et al. 1990). If no evolution occurs in these parameters, the concentration index and size are similar to cluster dE galaxies (Conselice 2003), which have a range of star formation histories including some with recent ($< 2.5Gyrs$) bursts of star formation (Conselice et al. 2003). The cluster environment, through the aforementioned processes, is expected to strip a significant amount of material from a galaxy. Depending on the orbit, the initial mass, the strength of the burst, and the morphology of the galaxy, the observed LCBG may be 5-10 magnitudes fainter today (Martin et al. 2000, Mastropietro et al. 2005), which would result in a dE galaxy. The number density of the descendants of LCBGs based on reasonable estimates of the lifetime reveals a significant quantity of galaxies, which would produce an unrealistic red sequence luminosity if they galaxies do not significantly fade.

We have not fully explored other explanations which could possible explain the observed trends including the obscuration of the star formation (Duc et al. 2002), “backsplash” (Gil et al. 2005), or the evolution in the mechanisms that extinguish the star formation with redshift (Ellingson et al. 2001). Significant work is still required to confirm this hypothesis of in-fall and transformation and we outline some of that work in the next section.

5.4 Future Work

A substantial amount of work still remains within the WLTV data set, while a full exploration of the evolution of blue galaxies requires an extension of the current data set. Besides the obvious necessary expansion to a larger sample exploring a greater range of environments and redshifts, we briefly present how this problem will be explored in the future with data acquired to explore these specific clusters.

- **LCBGs at low redshift and different environments** The full WLTV sample includes six more fields: three low redshift clusters (one cluster has two pointings), one high redshift group environment, and one pure “field” sample. Completing the survey will allow further exploration for trends in the LCBG population with redshift and environment.
- **Morphology of Star forming galaxies** The excellent seeing of the WIYN narrow-band imaging resolves structure in the largest star forming galaxies in the clusters. Detailed analysis of the morphology of the star forming galaxies can quantify structure which may be induced by the cluster environment. For example, centrally concentrated star formation induced by tidal forces (Bekki et al. 2003) would look different than ring-shaped star formation related to ram-pressure, which would look different than irregular morphologies related to merging (Conselice 2003).
- **LCBG properties** Spectroscopic observations obtained with DEIMOS on the KECK telescope for the two $z \sim 0.55$ clusters allows the measurement of LCBG properties such as star formation rates, metallicity, extinctions, and velocity widths. Comparison with the field sample of LCBGs will further quantify the differences between cluster and field LCBGs. Due to the high blue throughput of PFIS, future observations with the SALT telescope will produce high quality measurements of the extinction through multi-slit observations of cluster sources via the rest-frame UV flux.
- **Cluster Kinematics** A vital assumption in our analysis has been that the star forming galaxies are in-falling into the cluster for the first time. This can be tested via unique observing modes with PFIS including Fabry-Perot imaging or massively multiplexed slitlets.

Future analysis will have to determine the relative efficiencies for either technique for the measurement of the cluster kinematics.

- **Stellar Masses for LCBGs** Stellar masses for the LCBGs will require deep NIR imaging. Publically available data covering most of the WIYN field of view is already available for one cluster (MS1054), and we can examine for any evolution in stellar mass with cluster radius. For the other clusters, future observations must be obtained as only shallow observations of the central regions exist.
- **Obscured Star Formation** The deficit of LCBGs and star forming galaxies depends on the star formation not being obscured once the galaxy enters into the cluster core region. Many of these cluster have Spitzer archive or VLA archive observations and the obscured star formation hypothesis can be explore through the analysis of this data.
- **AGN/Starburst connection** The connection between AGN and starbursts are not well understood (Combes 2003). AGN in our fields can be identified through the optical variability data available from the WLTV survey, but also through correlation of our data set with point sources in deep X-ray imaging or radio observations of the clusters.

Obviously a significant amount of work still exists for this data set alone, not to mention the vast amount of observations and data analysis that is capable in the future. The original goal of this thesis was to establish an extreme class of star-bursting galaxies as a progenitor population via the morphology density relationship, but the most definitive result after extensive analysis is that more questions about this population and other star forming galaxies at intermediate redshifts exist then at the beginning of this project.

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